
The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) as an educational tool to effectively teach World History to Grade 8 students during in-person classes at Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School. This study used pre-test and post-test group designs together the relevant data from 160 Grade 8 students who served as the respondents. The pre-test was given prior to the students' use of the materials whilst the post-test was given after their successful exposure to DIMs.

The following findings were gathered: During the pre-test, almost half (46.87%) of them scored *fairly*, 39.38% *satisfactory*, and 3.75% *very satisfactorily*. However, 10% *did not meet expectations*, and none got an *outstanding* score. In contrast, the post-test showed that 41.25% got an *outstanding* score, 38.75% *very satisfactory*, and 20% *satisfactory*. All respondents met the expectations of the subject this time.

The comparative data that showed a significant difference between the pre- test and post-test scores of the respondents proved that the remarkable improvement in their post-test scores was due to the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs).

Finally, the Pearson r computation resulted in a very strong positive correlation between the perception of students in the use of DIMs through its four key elements: content, process, product, affect/environment, and their corresponding post-test scores thus, a significant relationship between the said perception of the students and the obtained post-test scores. These proved that the higher the level of perception, the higher the correlation.

The scope of this study was limited to the Grade 8 students of Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial National High School and World History (AP 8) subject only.

KEYWORDS: Differentiated instructional materials, in-person classes, content, process, product, affect/environment, pre-post-test.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The implementation of the K to 12 curriculum under Republic Act 10533 emphasized inclusive education, requiring teachers to address learners' diverse needs. Despite these reforms, challenges persist in teaching Araling Panlipunan (AP), particularly World History, where learners often perceive the subject as unengaging and difficult.

At Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School, the consistently low Mean Percentage Scores (50–60) in AP8 indicate the need for innovative strategies. The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated learning gaps, reducing students' motivation and comprehension. As schools returned to full in-person classes, there emerged a strong demand for learner-centered approaches that could bridge these gaps.

Differentiated Instruction (DI), anchored on Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, Constructivist Learning Theory, and Tomlinson's Differentiated Instruction Framework, provides opportunities to design instructional materials (DIMs) tailored to students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles. By integrating DI in AP8, teachers may transform classroom instruction, improve student achievement, and foster more inclusive learning environments.

Statement of the Problem

This study attempted to determine the efficacy in the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials in teaching World History (Araling Panlipunan 8) for in- person classes of Grade 8 Learners in Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the Grade 8 respondents in the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) as to:
 - a. Content

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- b. Process
- c. Product
- d. Affect / Environment
2. What are the Pre-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period before being exposed to the use of DIMs?
3. What are the Post-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period after being exposed to the use of DIMs?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of Grade 8 respondents during the Second Quarter period before and after being exposed to the use of DIMs?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 Learners in the Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product and Affect/Environment and their Post- test Scores in World History (AP 8) for the Second Quarter Period?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores in World History (AP 8) among Grade 8 respondents during the second quarter period.

Ho: That there is no significant relationship between the Perception of Grade 8 Learners in the Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product and Affect/Environment and their Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) for the Second Quarter Period.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Multiple Intelligences, Constructivist Learning Theory, and Tomlinson's Differentiated Instructional Framework serve as the foundation for this research study.

Gardner (1999) proposed that an individual's intelligence is not a single quantifiable quality, but rather a collection of different forms and facets. Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences inspired the researcher to investigate this topic further. Furthermore, this theory proposed that there are eight intelligences that emphasize the importance of problem-solving. This theorized that not all learners learn in the same way and that each human being is unique and different. Enriching classroom instruction by providing a diverse range of techniques and strategies would provide opportunities for all students by fostering the development of their individual strengths (Gardner, 1999).

Teachers are challenged to cater instruction in such a way that it addresses the individual needs of the learner who learns in different ways by viewing learners as unique individuals. This may not appear to be a difficult task for the teacher, but careful planning of lessons and how these lessons will be carried out necessitates careful preparation. Furthermore, the uniqueness of each learner suggested that the teacher should first consider the students' knowledge or what the students already know.

Constructivist Learning Theory backs up the idea that students' knowledge and experiences should be taken into account during the teaching and learning process. Constructivist Learning Theory has historical roots in the works of Dewey (1929), Vygotsky (1962), and Piaget (1963). (1980). According to Dewey (1938), as cited by Bada (2015), learning differs for each individual based on how they construct meaning from their experiences. As a result, rather than being passive recipients of knowledge, learners are active agents in the teaching and learning process, creating and attaching their own meaning to the new concept or information presented to them.

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Figure 1. Differentiated Instruction Framework by Tomlinson (2013)

According to Tomlinson (2013), Differentiated Instruction (DI) allows teachers to address the students' varying needs by recognizing the range of differences or uniqueness among students and allowing teachers to cater to each student's unique learning style by adjusting what they teach and how they teach it.

Teachers may differentiate their lessons through the content or the access to the lesson or topic at hand, process or how the learners make sense of the information presented to them, product or learning artifacts, evidence or outputs, and affect/environment or the physical and affective climate in the classroom (Tomlinson, 2009). These four components of Differentiated Instruction (DI) allow teachers to address students' varying needs by recognizing the range of differences or uniqueness among students and allowing teachers to cater to each student's unique learning style by adjusting what they teach and how they teach it, according to Tomlinson (2013).

Teachers can differentiate their lessons based on the content or access to the lesson or topic at hand, the process or how learners make sense of the information presented to them, the product or learning artifacts, evidence or outputs, and the affect/environment or the physical and affective climate in the classroom (Tomlinson, 2009). Teachers are expected to be able to attend to the individual needs of each student using these four methods of differentiating the teaching and learning process.

Teachers are guided in the implementation of differentiated instruction by their understanding of the student's needs, interests, and learning profile. According to Tomlinson and Imbeau (2010), readiness is defined as a student's current familiarity with specific knowledge, understanding, and skills. Student interests are defined as "that which engages a student's attention, curiosity, and involvement" (Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2010, p. 16). A learning profile is defined as "a preference for absorbing, exploring, or expressing content" (Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2010, p. 17). By taking into account the differences among learners, teachers can successfully incorporate differentiated instruction into the teaching and learning process with the help of this framework. Finally, affect or environment refers to the rapport or relationship that exists between the teacher and his or her students. It also refers to the overall tone or atmosphere of the classroom. Furthermore, by determining students' perceptions of teaching and learning- process, the researcher will be able to understand how students perceive the use of such an approach for refinement and improvement of its application.

According to Qiong (2017), perception has three stages: selection, organization, and interpretation. The definition and stages of perception will guide the researcher in developing an instrument that can determine whether or not differentiated instruction was evident in in-person classes.

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Conceptual Paradigm

Figure 2. IPO Model for DIMS

The research paradigm depicts all the variables related to the study in order to provide a clearer perspective of the study.

The IPO (Inputs-Process-Output) Model is depicted in Figure 2 as the study's Conceptual Framework. This model explains how INPUTS, when PROCESSED, can result in an OUTPUT.

INPUTS are represented in this research study by the Pre-Test Scores of Grade-8 students in World History (AP8) during the Second Quarter Period. These inputs will go through a PROCESS such as the Implementation of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through the use of a Survey Questionnaire. The responses of the learners vary according to the extent to which they agree or disagree with the Four Key Elements of Differentiated Instructions, such as Content, Process, Product, And Affect/Environment. Furthermore, once the respondents' perceptions become significantly reliable and acceptable, the OUTPUT of this research study are the respondents' Post-Test Scores and their Improved Performance with the use of the DIMs in learning World History (AP8) during in-person classes.

Significance of the Study

The researcher hopes that the findings of the study are beneficial for the following:

To the students. This research study will investigate whether the use of differentiated instruction has a positive impact on the improvement of students' performance.

To the teachers. This research study will investigate a teaching strategy that can be used in in-person classes. It can improve classroom instruction, lesson planning, and achievement of the curriculum guide's targeted student learning outcomes.

To the school heads. This research study once adopted and used by the school will be useful to the school administrators because it will guide them in developing school policies regarding curriculum and instruction to improve students' performance.

To the researcher. This research study may fulfill the researcher's pursuit of the positive impact of differentiated instruction in a novel delivery of instruction, particularly during the return of in-person classes following the restrictions imposed by the CoViD-19 pandemic in Philippine education. This research study will open many doors in the field of instruction for future use in rapidly changing educational settings.

To future researchers. This study may serve as a guide for future researchersto use as a reference. They may also obtain a literature review from this researchstudy. Based on the findings of this study, they can design a new study.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study was limited to 160 Grade 8 learners of Col. Lauro D. Dizon MIHS during SY 2022–2023. It covered their perceptions of DIMs, pre-test and post-test scores, and the implementation of differentiated strategies in teaching AP8 during the second quarter.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined conceptually and operationally for better understanding and benefit of the readers.

Academic Achievement. Academic achievement in this study refers to academic outcomes that indicate how well a student has met their learning objectives. (either in the short or long term). Exams or continuous assessments are frequently used to assess students, so grades are used to assess them.

Affect/Learning Environment. This refers to how the teacher organizes the class in the classroom environment in this study. This includes establishing rules and expectations, establishing procedures or groupings, establishing rapport between the teacher and the students, and establishing an overall climate in the teaching and learning process.

Content. This refers to the learning competencies that students must master in this study. It also refers to the method by which students

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can gain access to learning competencies.

Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs). These are teaching materials that cater to the various needs of students while taking their interests, learning profiles, and readiness into account. DIMs enable the differentiation of lessons based on content, process, product, and affect/environment. They are also referred to as an educational intervention or treatment.

In-Person Instruction. This refers to the conduct of classes through instructional interaction that occurs physically and in real-time between teachers and students in the actual classroom setting in this study.

Perception. In this study, this refers to the extent to which respondents agree or disagree that certain indicators of Differentiated Instruction are visible in in-person classes.

Pre-test It refers to a 25-item test administered prior to the administration of an experimental treatment or educational intervention in order to determine the similarity of the one experimental group. It also determines the student's level of comprehension at the start of the treatment.

Post-test. It refers to a 25-item test administered to the same group of respondents (comprised of 160 respondents from seven sections handled by the researcher) after the treatment was administered using Process Oriented Guide Inquiry Learning.

Process. This refers to the sets of activities or learning tasks that enable students to make sense of the content in this study.

Product. This is the method or way students will present their output to demonstrate learning of the content in this study.

CONCEPTUAL LITERATURE

Differentiated Instruction. The Philippines received the lowest reading comprehension score among the 79 countries in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment, according to the report entitled: "Capturing the Complexity of Differentiated Instruction" (PISA). It is a global assessment of students' Reading, Mathematics, and Science proficiency administered by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. And while it is disheartening to score the lowest in reading comprehension, we must recognize and accept that the quality of education in the Philippines is declining to find an effective and sustainable solution to the problem.

Teachers are encouraged to address student heterogeneity in their daily teaching practice to address their constantly increasing learning demands. One of the best remedies to enhance and modify our learning practices is Differentiated Instruction (DI). It is a popular and practice-proven approach tailored to efficiently meet the diverse and distinctive needs of learners (Coubergs, Struyven, Vanthournout; et al., 2017). It also promotes inclusive education and aims to support academic learning and foster the social and emotional development of the students. This further means that students can learn and acquire content and competencies using varied resources and strategies, allowing them to demonstrate knowledge, values, and skills based on their unique needs and preferences.

The effectiveness of DI is frequently linked to the best learning outcomes in terms of academic performance and achievement because it can be described as a collection of instructional strategies that enable teachers to ensure that all students, regardless of their characteristics, have positive and successful learning situations (Loreman, 2017). Until now, however, there are still varying definitions studies on the effects of DI and motivating research into several DI frameworks (Jennek et al., 2019; Lindner and Schwab, 2020).

Holland (2017) stated that Differentiated Instruction is associated with increased student engagement and motivation; and identified specific classroom management strategies that supported the effective implementation of differentiated instruction, such as flexible grouping, clear expectations, and student of the instructional method, making it difficult to compare the findings of various choice.

McCarthy (2016) offered a comprehensive guide to implementing differentiated instruction in academically diverse classrooms, including classroom management strategies that support successful implementation. She also highlighted the importance of establishing a positive classroom culture, setting clear expectations, and developing practices and procedures that support student independence and accountability.

Deunk et al. (2018) conducted a meta-analysis to examine the effects of DI on the cognitive abilities of primary kids in light of this. The analysis of 21 studies revealed that DI generally has a beneficial impact on the pupils' academic achievements (Deunk et al., 2018). However, no meaningful overall effect was discovered when DI was operationalized only through grouping techniques. The findings of a meta-analysis by Steenbergen-Hu et al. (2016) indicated that there were no appreciable impacts of DI on student performance when grouping methods were used. A parallel study by Nusser and Gehrler (2020) showed positive progress in the German reading competence of secondary students. But it could not be defined as an effect of teachers' use of DI (Nusser and Gehrler, 2020).

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There is a need to explore how teachers differentiate their instruction, particularly from large-scale studies on DI (Prast, van de Weijer-Bergsma, Kroesbergen, et al., 2018; Ritzema, Deunk, and Bosker, 2016). The systematization of the DI concept and the categorization of potential instructional strategies used to handle the wide range of student differences are necessary due to several intrinsic limitations on its efficient application. Pozas and Schneider (2019) offered a taxonomy of DI practices to close the gap between educational theory and common instructional practice. The taxonomy is anchored within the current DI literature and research and built on existing works by giving teachers helpful and specific guidance on planning and differentiating their instruction to resolve classroom diversity.

A study by Jennek, Gronostaj, and Vock (2019) revealed that, on average, the overall use of DI does not differ significantly between school tracks. Even with a deeper look into the particular single implemented DI practices, like tiered assignments and learning aids, the authors found no evident variances among the school tracks. The application of DI, in summary, may be influenced by the subject domain and school track. As such, contextual factors must not be taken for granted when examining teachers' use of DI.

Al-Shehri (2020) studied the effect of DI on the critical thinking aptitude of grade six students, and evidence showed that an instructional program based on DI generated a much better performance of the students in terms of their critical thinking skills.

"Perception is the process of organizing, identifying, and interpreting sensory data to represent and understand the information or environment presented" (Schacter, 2011). There are three stages of perception, according to Qiong (2017): (1.) selection, (2.) organization, and (3.) interpretation.

Selection is the initial stage of perception wherein student makes meaning from the stimuli they experience in their learning environment. Learners only include stimuli that have relevance to them and have a habit of neglecting others that are irrelevant to their experiences.

The final stage of perception is the interpretation stage, wherein the learners give meaning to the sensed experience. Learners assign meaning to the pattern; however, different people may interpret the same stimulus differently due to differences in background and belief system.

In 2018, Parsons et al. stated that adapting Differentiated Instruction is "the cornerstone of effective instruction" and "the gold standard teachers should strive for." Truly, differentiating instruction is a challenging teaching ability (M. van Geel, T. Keuning, J. Frèrejean, D. Dolmans, J. van Merrinboer, and A. J. Visscher, 2019).

Another study by Moosa and Shareefa (2019) revealed a link between the teachers' knowledge of DI and its implementation; and between the teachers' sense of efficacy and DI implementation. Based on the regression analysis of their study, the teachers' expertise as facilitators affected the application of DI because they steer the flow of the teaching and learning processes that can encourage students to become achievers. Consequently, their role has a substantial impact on the general performance of the students.

At the same time, every teacher faces the challenge of determining the level of knowledge, understanding, and motivation individual students require. Strategies for Differentiating Instruction: A Practical Manual for Using Multiple Intelligence Approaches is an excellent source for teachers to attain and professionally use multiple intelligences in their classrooms. The revised edition contains all new projects and examples of proven and reliable methods for today's diverse learners, including young children. (Roberts, J. L., and T. F. Inman (2021). Based on the study conducted by Suprayogi, M. N. et al., the primary factor considered in "Teaching and Teacher Education" was the growing diversity of student needs that require appropriate instructional strategies. A strategic solution is the provision of activities or instructions relevant to their skills and potential through DI, albeit challenging. Considerably, it appears to be difficult not only on the part of the learners but more on the part of the teachers thus, they need to be further involved in complex teaching variables such as teachers' DI self-efficacy, teaching beliefs, teaching experience, professional development, teacher certification, and classroom size (Suprayogi, M. N., Valcke, M., & Godwin, R., 2017).

A specific learning model or method can help teachers develop the analytical thinking skills of the learners. While there is no one size fits all teaching strategy, there are pedagogy models that may improve the thinking skills of learners, most especially when the teacher assesses their individual needs (Sartika, 2018).

Now, according to Carol Tomlinson (2003), a frontrunner in the field of differentiated learning and professor of educational leadership, policy, and foundations at the University of Virginia, teachers can differentiate instruction through four ways: 1) content, 2) process, 3) product, and 4) affect/learning environment.

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RESEARCH LITERATURE

Teaching practice to address their constantly increasing learning demands. One of the best remedies to enhance and modify our learning practices is Differentiated Instruction (DI). It is a popular and practice-proven approach tailored to efficiently meet the diverse and distinctive needs of learners (Coubergs, Struyven, Vanthournout; et al., 2017). It also promotes inclusive education and aims to support academic learning and foster the social and emotional development of the students. This further means that students can learn and acquire content and competencies using varied resources and strategies, allowing them to demonstrate knowledge, values, and skills based on their unique needs and preferences.

The effectiveness of DI is frequently linked to the best learning outcomes in terms of academic performance and achievement because it can be described as a collection of instructional strategies that enable teachers to ensure that all students, regardless of their characteristics, have positive and successful learning situations (Loreman, 2017). Until now, however, there are still varying definitions studies on the effects of DI and motivating research into several DI frameworks (Jennek et al., 2019; Lindner and Schwab, 2020).

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Based on the study conducted by Suprayogi, M. N. et al., the primary factor considered in "Teaching and Teacher Education" was the growing diversity of student needs that require appropriate instructional strategies. A strategic solution is the provision of activities or instructions relevant to their skills and potential through DI, albeit challenging. Considerably, it appears to be difficult not only on the part of the learners but more on the part of the teachers thus, they need to be further involved in complex teaching variables such as teachers' DI self- efficacy, (Steenbergen-Hu et al., 2016; Deunk et al., 2018; Smale-Jacobse et al., 2019)

Exploring how inclusion affects students' academic results is just one goal of development has been highlighted in policy discussions (Zurbriggen et al., 2018).

Students' well-being, social inclusion, and academic self-concept are three critical student outcome factors thoroughly investigated in research and literature (DeVries et al., 2018; Venetz et al., 2019). These three student outcome variables have been observed for a long time now because of their relationship to students' academic learning and performance, including their overall satisfaction and development (Schwab et al., 2020). Furthermore, assessing students' subjective welfare, societal inclusion, and academic self-concept are variables that can reflect educational quality (Guillemot and Hessels, 2021).

The quantitative study by Alnahdi et al. (2021) revealed that the perceptionthe students' non-academic outcomes (Alnahdi et al., 2021). A more recent study In North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany, children from 872 primary schools and 47 inclusive groups evaluated the frequency of usage of inclusive instructional strategies by their teachers. The results based on the data gathered showed high use of methods for meeting the needs of students with special educational needs (SEN) (K. T. Lindner, G. H. Alnahdi, S. Wahl, and S. Schwab, 2019).

The research study of Angela Mae S. Castro (2020) revealed that the developed twister games or gamification in teaching Araling Panlipunan is more effective than the traditional lecture method. On a similar note, Veny Rose Garcia- Acojido (2021) published a journal about the Merits and Demerits of AP Teachers in Using Instructional Resources. The journal cited that the merits and demerits reverberate the strengths and weaknesses of AP teachers in teaching the subject. An article by Oka Agus Kurniawan Shavab (2018) disclosed that gamification is a successful technique for educating learners in history classes. It emphasizes how gamification is used as a learning method to capture the students' interest. Furthermore, Potenciano Conte Jr. (2017) cited that using games as a

According to Rachma Hasibuan and Nur Ika Sari Rakhmawati (2017), developing new learning strategies like the twister game

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is essential to improve a child's learning ability. Miran Sakhatov (2019) also revealed that didactic games are duly endorsed learning strategies for history classes. Similarly, Polona Jančič (Faculty of Education, University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia) and Vlasta Hus (Faculty of Education, University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia) (2018) discovered that students are enthusiastic about game-based learning in AP. Unfortunately, the article also showed that AP teachers seldom use this method and prefer traditional learning practices, although students barely participate in the discussion due to a lack of interest. In conclusion, learning improves learners' outputs and academic accomplishments (Qudsyi, 2017); therefore, AP teachers are encouraged to get out of their comfort zones to make the World History learning environment fascinating and lively to win the active participation of students that will ultimately lead to their enhanced learning and skills development.

Studies show that rote learners are limited in their analytical thinking, profound insight, creativity, and problem-solving skills (Madden et al., 2017).

guidelines for the slow reopening of in-person classes five days a week and the steady transition to standard operational capacity during the pandemic. DepEd defines in-person classes as conducted through instructional interaction that occurs physically and in real-time between teachers and students in the actual classroom setting. The Department of Education allowed schools to use blended distance learning for the opening of classes in August 2022. However, all private and public schools must conduct five-day-a-week in-person-classes in November of the same year, except those under the Alternative Delivery Modes (Department of Education Order No. 34, Section 2022).

In a study conducted by Delgado, et. al (2022), even though online learning platforms serve as an alternative to in-person classes, students of all ages and the educational system faced challenges in adapting to new and innovative ways of Lewis (2021) cited that the absence of in-person classes, distance learning, and instruction brings social isolation. Children lose the opportunity to develop their social skills and collaborate with others, thus has a detrimental effect on their capacity to learn and retain information. Absenteeism has also become a crucial problem during distance learning, where students cannot conform to the requirements and tasks needed to accomplish as opposed to those attending in- person classes. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) revealed persistent absenteeism was more common in students who participated in remote distance learning.

In a study conducted by Fuzéki, et. al. (2022), in-person classes cannot be replaced by online exercise classes that are inadequate. While online education provides no risk in terms of health and safety during the pandemic and is a readily accessible mode, its appeal is very different and restricted for some groups of people. The lack of social interaction and guidance from the mentors, including their teachers, worsened the situation. In addition, the motivation on the part of the students is not high compared to those who attend in-person classes. Indeed, more efforts are necessary during the pandemic to keep in-person classes accessible and safe for everyone.

Educational offers, is critical because teachers play a significant role in the development of educational contexts (Decristan et al., 2017; Pit-ten Cate et al., 2018). Teachers are inevitably faced with the professional mandate to instigate aptly modified teaching practices that are suitable to their student's needs, given that a heterogeneous class composition serves as the pedagogical work base for teaching and learning processes (Vaughn et al., 2007b; Pozas et al., 2020; Kärner et al., 2021).

Diverse student characteristics and educational requisites call for proper didactic responses that provide learning for every student while being free of exclusion and discrimination (McMurray and Thompson, 2016; Petersen, 2016; Ainscow and Messiou, 2018). From this perspective, inclusive teaching strategies are frequently discussed as a didactic approach to preventing learning barriers for students who are predisposed to experiencing disadvantages in educational situations as a result of personal traits like a diagnosis of having special education needs (SEN) (Lindner and Schwab, 2020; Schwab et al., 2020; UNESCO, 2020).

SYNTHESIS OF REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The reviewed conceptual literature establishes Differentiated Instruction (DI) as a teaching framework grounded in theories of learner diversity and inclusivity. Authors such as Tomlinson and Loreman emphasized that DI allows teachers to address varied learning needs by modifying content, process, product, and learning environment. Similarly, theories of perception and cognition highlight how students organize, interpret, and respond to instructional stimuli, supporting the rationale for adapting instruction to individual differences. These conceptual foundations provide the theoretical basis for understanding DI as both an inclusive and effective pedagogical approach.

The reviewed research literature, both foreign and local, provides empirical evidence on the application and effects of DI. International studies (Deunk et al., 2018; Nusser & Gehrer, 2020; Pozas & Schneider, 2019) generally reveal positive outcomes of DI on student learning, motivation, and classroom engagement, although findings vary depending on context and implementation strategies.

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Local studies, such as those by Castro (2020) and Delgado et al. (2022), affirm similar results in the Philippine setting, demonstrating DI's potential to improve learners' academic performance and critical thinking skills. Despite these findings, some research suggests mixed results when DI is operationalized only through grouping methods, indicating that DI's effectiveness depends heavily on the quality of planning and execution.

Taken together, the conceptual and research literature collectively support the role of DI in addressing diverse learner needs and improving educational outcomes. However, while its general effectiveness is well established, there is limited exploration of its application in specific subject areas such as World History within the Philippine in-person classroom context. This gap highlights the relevance of the present study, which aims to investigate the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials in teaching World History to Grade 8 learners. By focusing on this underexplored area, the study intends to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on DI and offer practical insights for enhancing classroom instruction.

CHAPTER 2 METHODS

Research Design

Because the Pre-test and Post-test scores were studied before and after the experimental manipulation, this research study used a quasi-experimental research design. In this study, respondents were subjected to experimental manipulation in the Use of Differentiated Materials in AP 8. Take note that the term

"quasi-experimental" simply means that the respondents were not assigned at random. Furthermore, the quasi-experimental research design, as defined by Cook and Campbell (1979) and mentioned by Jhangiani et al. (2019), resembles a type of experimental research but is not true experimental research because it lacks the random assignment of the subject of study, which is a feature of true experimental research. The manipulation of the independent variables comes before the manipulation of the dependent variables in this design (Jhangiani et al., 2019). In terms of internal validity, a quasi-experimental research design falls somewhere between an observational or non-experimental design, such as a descriptive or correlational design, and a true experimental design. It is the most applicable and appropriate in the context of this study because random assignment among subjects is impossible because the subjects are already classified into sections. These are non-random conditions to which subjects have already been assigned (Cook and Campbell, 1979).

In this study, the ethical consideration of randomly assigning subjects to experimental and comparison groups posed a challenge. The difficulty of randomizing the subjects brought on by the current pandemic compelled the researcher to use this design. Furthermore, quasi-experimental research designs are frequently used to determine and investigate the efficacy of a treatment, such as an educational intervention (Jhangiani et al., 2019).

Furthermore, this study used a One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design. It is a type of quasi-experiment in which the responses were measured twice: once before and once after a non-random group of participants is exposed to a specific intervention/treatment.

The goal was to assess the impact of the intervention, which could be a training program or a policy, or a curriculum shift. This is a quasi-experimental research design in which only one group of participants will receive the pre-test, treatment (educational intervention), and post-test. It is important to note that the one-group pretest-posttest design has these three major characteristics:

1. The group of respondents who receive the intervention is chosen at random, making it a quasi-experimental design.
2. The lack of a control group against which to compare the outcome, and
3. The intervention's effectiveness is determined by comparing pre-and post- intervention measurements.

The study's methodology included data collection and analysis. The quantitative data were derived from the subjects' responses to the survey questionnaire, as well as their pre-test and post-test scores in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period. To draw conclusions and recommendations for the study, data were encoded, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Respondents and Sampling

The respondents were 160 Grade 8 learners purposively selected from seven sections handled by the researcher. Sample size determination was based on Raosoft calculations. Below is the table showing the distribution of the respondents.

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Table 1. Distribution of Respondents Per Section

Section	Number of Students in a Class	Number of Respondents during Pilot Testing	Number of Respondents during the Survey
A	40	7	23
B	38	7	23
C	39	7	23
K	39	7	23
M	38	7	23
N	39	7	23
S	38	8	22
Total	271	50	160

The researcher used the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator to determine the sample size from the population (seven sections handled by the researcher). The screenshot revealed that the exact and appropriate sample size is 160 students out of 271 students.

Figure 3. Sample Size Computation Using Raosoft Calculator

Research Instruments

1. Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs): Teacher-made activity sheets, worksheets, multimedia, and performance tasks based on Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).
2. Survey Questionnaire: Researcher-made and validated, covering the four DI components: content, process, product, affect/environment. Cronbach's Alpha confirmed reliability.
3. Pre-test and Post-test: 25-item teacher-made tests validated by subject experts.

Data Gathering Procedure

- Validation of instruments by experts.
- Pilot testing with 50 students.
- Administration of pre-test before instruction.
- Implementation of DIMs across eight weeks.
- Post-test and survey administration.
- Ethical clearance and parental consent were secured.

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Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics such as *frequency and percentage* were used to determine respondents' perceptions using a survey questionnaire. The *mean and standard deviation* were also employed to calculate the respondents' pre-test and post-test scores.

For the One-Group Pretest-Posttest instrument, the T-test: Paired Two Samples for Means was used. The researcher was able to compare the mean scores of the respondents on their pre-test and post-test assessments, as well as determine whether there was a significant difference between the means of the pre-test and post-test scores.

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to assess the degree of correlation between respondents' perceptions of the Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) and Post-test Scores in AP 8 following exposure to the educational intervention.

CHAPTER 3 RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the gathered data, thus, includes the findings in tabular form with their respective interpretations. The data are analyzed and interpreted so that conclusions and recommendations can be drawn from the study.

1. What is the perception of the Grade 8 respondents in the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) as to:
 - a. Content, b. Process, C. Product, and
 - d. Affect/Environment

Table 2. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials as to Content

Statement		MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
The teacher.....				
1.	provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.	3.63	0.49	Highly Observed
2.	enhances visual presentations to add appeal to the lecture notes by means of <i>pictures, tables, diagrams, graphic organizers, and the like</i> .	3.58	0.50	Highly Observed
3.	uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.	3.56	0.50	Highly Observed
4.	presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
5.	utilizes <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson.	3.64	0.48	Highly Observed
6.	designs the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.	3.66	0.47	Highly Observed
7.	explains words that are not familiar to the learners.	3.65	0.48	Highly Observed
8.	applies enrichment activities with varying difficulties.	3.64	0.48	Highly Observed
9.	gives various resources, materials, and worksheets the learners can utilize.	3.74	0.44	Highly Observed
10.	sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.	3.76	0.43	Highly Observed
General Assessment		3.64	0.48	Highly Observed
Legend:		3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree / Highly Observed	1.76 – 2.50
		2.51 – 3.25	Agree / Observed	Disagree / Less Observed
				1.00 – 1.75
				Strongly Disagree / Not Observed at All

Table 2 illustrates the perceived use of differentiated instructional materials as to content. It can be noted from the above table that the statement wherein the teacher sets a time frame in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished yielded the most highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.76. On the other hand, the statement that the teacher uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes yielded the lowest highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.56. It can also be concluded that the respondents highly observed all indicators shown in Table 1 with an average mean of 3.64. Furthermore, the result implies that learners highly observed the employment of differentiated instruction in terms of providing varied ways by which contents of the lesson may be provided to the students and diverse avenues from which the learners can gain knowledge about the lesson at hand.

According to the Revised Bloom's Taxonomy by Anderson and Krathwohl (2001), teachers can differentiate the content by designing

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activities for groups of students that involve six levels of intellectual behavior ranging from lower-order thinking skills to higher-order thinking skills: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating and creating. The students who are unaccustomed to a lesson may be instructed to complete tasks on the lower levels: remembering and understanding, those with some mastery could be tasked to apply and analyze the content, and learners with expertise in the lesson may be required to complete tasks on evaluation and creation. The HOT skills: analyze, evaluate, and create are soft skills that have been the primary focus of the global curriculum and are the in-demand skills desired in the current workplace.

The World Economic Forum (WEF) listed analytical thinking and innovation as one of the top 10 skills in 2025 based on the Future of Jobs Report 2020 (WEF Future of the Jobs Report, 2020). Consequently, Future Learn Report (2019) revealed that data analysis is one of the top skills in the Philippines for employment, while according to Fresh Graduate Reports of Jobstreet.com (2018), analytical thinking is one of the top three skills employers are looking for during job interviews of potential candidates, together with work ethics and communication skills.

Table 3. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials as to Process

Statement		MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
The teacher.....				
1.	presents each lesson in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners.	3.65	0.48	Highly Observed
2.	uses visual materials such as pictures, maps, tarpapel, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.	3.53	0.50	Highly Observed
3.	makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.	3.57	0.50	Highly Observed
4.	gives various examples about the lesson.	3.61	0.49	Highly Observed
5.	encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.	3.55	0.50	Highly Observed
6.	designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well to the lesson.	3.62	0.49	Highly Observed
7.	gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.	3.63	0.49	Highly Observed
8.	provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners' unique talents and skills.	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
9.	allows the class to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.	3.60	0.49	Highly Observed
10.	encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.	3.70	0.46	Highly Observed
	General Assessment	3.60	0.49	Highly Observed
	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree / Highly Observed		1.76 – 2.50
Legend:	2.51 – 3.25	Agree / Observed		1.00 – 1.75
				Disagree / Less Observed
				Strongly Disagree / Not Observed at All

The table above demonstrates the perceived use of differentiated instructional materials as to process. Moreover, the statement that the teacher encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson is the most highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.70, whereas the statement that the teacher uses visual materials such as pictures, maps, tarpapels, diagrams, graphic organizers, videos and PowerPoint presentations to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class is the lowest highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.53. Overall, the Tomlinson (2017) described "process" as the way students interact with "content"; and emphasized the importance of providing students with multiple pathways for learning, including varied instructional strategies, flexible grouping, and opportunities for student choice learning by offering support based on individual needs. In 2016, Hudson discussed the usage of varied journal prompts as a tool for differentiated instruction in the language classroom. She suggested that using different types of prompts like a personal reflection, creative writing, and critical analysis can help teachers cater to different learning styles and preferences while allowing students to explore their interests and develop their language skills in many ways.

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Table 4. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials as to Product

Statement		MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
The teacher.....				
1.	provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.	3.54	0.50	Highly Observed
2.	sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.	3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
3.	creates tasks based on a real-world experiences /applications.	3.61	0.49	Highly Observed
4.	allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
5.	shows a sample of an output and explains how it was made	3.61	0.49	Highly Observed
6.	gives a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
7.	explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.	3.61	0.49	Highly Observed
8.	encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.	3.63	0.49	Highly Observed
9.	explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.	3.58	0.50	Highly Observed
10.	equips differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.	3.65	0.48	Highly Observed
	General Assessment	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
Legend:				
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree / Highly Observed	1.76 – 2.50		Disagree / Less Observed
2.51 – 3.25	Agree / Observed	1.00 – 1.75		Strongly Disagree / Not Observed at All

Table 4 presents the perceived use of differentiated instructional materials as to product. It can be concluded from the data that the statement that the teacher equips differentiated tasks that are challenging yet, can be finished within the given timeframe is the most highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.65, whereas the statement that the teacher sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs is the lowest highly observed indicator, with a mean of 3.51. Generally, it can be determined from the assessment that the respondents highly observed all indicators enumerated in Table 4, with an average mean of 3.59.

Teachers can differentiate the end product by requiring the read-and-write learners to make a book report, asking visual learners to create a graphic organizer of the story, requesting auditory and word learners to give an oral description, and instructing kinesthetic learners to build a diorama illustrating the story.

In a review by Lavoie and Pytash (2017), they suggested that the product component of differentiated instruction should include varieties of assessment options that align with the learning goals and objectives. They stressed the value of providing clear and specific criteria for each assessment option and ensuring that they are suitable for the learning purposes' level of challenge and complexity.

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Table 5. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials as to Affect/Environment

Statement		MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
The teacher.....				
1.	ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and well- ventilated.	3.46	0.50	Highly Observed
2.	makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.	3.46	0.50	Highly Observed
3.	promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environment for all learners.	3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
4.	sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest before the lesson starts.	3.53	0.50	Highly Observed
5.	shows sample of an output and explains how it was made.	3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
6.	requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during, and after the discussion of the lesson.	3.49	0.50	Highly Observed
7.	recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do-well in class.	3.48	0.50	Highly Observed
8.	allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.	3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
9.	encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.	3.53	0.50	Highly Observed
10.	gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs.	3.61	0.49	Highly Observed
General Assessment		3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
Legend:		3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree / Highly Observed	1.76 – 2.50 Disagree / Less Observed
		2.51 – 3.25	Agree / Observed	1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree / Not Observed at All

The table above exemplifies the perceived use of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment. It can be determined from Table 4 that the statement wherein the teacher gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs is the most highly observed indicator with a mean of 3.61. On the other hand, the statements that the teacher ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and always ventilated and makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts both ranked with the lowest highly observed indicator garnering a mean of 3.46. Overall, the respondents highly observed all indicators shown in Table 4 with an average mean of 3.51.

Teachers can differentiate the learning environment by changing the furniture arrangements as necessary, allowing students to read individually if preferred, creating some quiet spaces, and breaking some students into groups to discuss the task or assignment. In addition, changes in student groupings and the presentation of instructional materials may significantly impact their outputs (ULEAD, 2019).

Students' well-being, social inclusion, and academic self-concept are three critical student outcome factors thoroughly investigated in research and literature (DeVries et al., 2018; Venetz et al., 2019). These three student outcome variables have been observed for a long time now because of their relationship to students' academic learning and performance, including their overall satisfaction and development (Schwab et al., 2020). Furthermore, assessing students' subjective welfare, societal inclusion, and academic self-concept are variables that can reflect educational quality (Guillemot and Hessels, 2021).

The quantitative study by Alnahdi et al. (2021) revealed that the perception of students regarding their teachers' use of DI strongly predicted students perceived emotional and social inclusion as well as their academic self-concept. These findings showcase the correlation between the implementation of DI and the students' non-academic outcomes (Alnahdi et al., 2021). A more recent study by Kulakow (2020) that compared two learning environments showed that students following a competency-based DI learning approach reported higher levels of academic self-concept than students engaged with the traditional learning approach.

In North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany, children from 872 primary schools and 47 inclusive groups evaluated the frequency of usage of inclusive instructional strategies by their teachers. The results based on the data gathered showed high use of methods for meeting the needs of students with special educational needs (SEN) (K. T. Lindner, G. H. Alnahdi, S. Wahl, and S. Schwab, 2019).

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Table 6. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials as to the Four Key Elements of Differentiated Instruction: Content, Process, Product, and Affect/Environment

Key Elements of Differentiated Instruction	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Content	3.64	0.48	Highly Observed
Process	3.60	0.49	Highly Observed
Product	3.59	0.49	Highly Observed
Affect / Environment	3.51	0.50	Highly Observed
General Assessment	3.59	0.01	Highly Observed
Legend:	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree / Highly Observed	1.76 – 2.50 Disagree / Less Observed
	2.51 – 3.25	Agree / Observed	1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree / Not Observed at All

Table 6 illustrates the perceived use of differentiated instructional materials as to the four key elements of differentiated instruction: content, process, product, and affect/environment. Furthermore, the above data shows that among the aforesaid key elements, content is the most highly observed by the respondents with a mean of 3.64, whereas affect/environment is the lowest highly observed with a mean of 3.53. As a general assessment, the respondents highly observed all four key elements shown in Table 6 with an average mean of 3.59.

Holland (2017) stated that Differentiated Instruction is associated with increased student engagement and motivation; and identified specific classroom management strategies that supported the effective implementation of differentiated instruction, such as flexible grouping, clear expectations, and student choice.

McCarthy (2016) offered a comprehensive guide to implementing differentiated instruction in academically diverse classrooms, including classroom management strategies that support successful implementation. She also highlighted the importance of establishing a positive classroom culture, setting clear expectations, and developing practices and procedures that support student independence and accountability.

2. What are the Pre-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period before being exposed to the use of DIMs?

Table 7. Distribution of Respondents' Pre-test Scores in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter Period Before Being Exposed to the Use of DIMs

Score	Pre-test Scores in AP8		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	
21 – 25	-	-	Outstanding
16 – 20	6	3.75	Very Satisfactorily
11 – 15	63	39.38	Satisfactorily
6 – 10	75	46.87	Fairly Satisfactorily
0 – 5	16	10.00	Did not meet expectations
Total	160	100	

f - frequency % - Percent

Table 7 stipulates the pre-test scores of respondents in World History (AP 8) during the second quarter period before being exposed to the use of DIMs. The data indicates that almost half (46.87%) of the respondents have a fair comprehension of the subject, while 39.38% got satisfactory scores. Unfortunately, Table 6 also shows that there is a greater percentage of respondents who did not meet expectations (10%), than those who scored very satisfactorily (3.75%). It only strengthens the immediate need for a tool or intervention to effectively fill the gap and help the learners improve and maximize their academic success in World History.

Teachers struggle to motivate AP learners and must make information relevant to their experiences (Press Reader, 2017). There is a need to explore how teachers differentiate their instruction, particularly from large-scale studies on DI (Prast, van de Weijer-Bergsma, Kroesbergen, et al., 2018; Ritzema, Deunk, and Bosker, 2016). The systematization of the DI concept and the categorization of

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potential instructional strategies used to handle the wide range of student differences are necessary due to several intrinsic limitations on its efficient application. Pozas and Schneider (2019) offered a taxonomy of DI practices to close the gap between educational theory and common instructional practice. It is anchored within the current DI literature and research and built on existing works by giving teachers helpful and specific guidance on planning and differentiating their instruction to resolve classroom diversity.

Based on the study conducted by Suprayogi, M. N. et al., the primary factor considered in "Teaching and Teacher Education" was the growing diversity of student needs that require appropriate instructional strategies. It appears to be difficult not only on the part of the learners but more on the part of the teachers thus, they need to be further involved in complex teaching variables such as teachers' DI self-efficacy, teaching beliefs, teaching experience, professional development, teacher certification, and classroom size (Suprayogi, M. N., Valcke, M., & Godwin, R., 2017).

3. What are the Post-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period after being exposed to the use of DIMs?

Table 8. Distribution of Respondents' Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter Period After Being Exposed to the Use of DIMs

Score	Post-test f	Scores in AP8 %	Verbal Interpretation
21 – 25	66	41.25	Outstanding
16 – 20	62	38.75	Very Satisfactorily
11 – 15	32	20.00	Satisfactorily
6 – 10	-	-	Fairly Satisfactorily
0 – 5	-	-	Did not meet expectations
Total	160	100	
	<i>f</i> - frequency	% - Percent	

Table 7 signifies the post-test scores of respondents in World History (AP 8) during the second quarter period after being exposed to the use of DIMs. The information above reveals that 41.25% of the respondents have an outstanding understanding of the subject, 38.75% are very satisfactory, and 20% with satisfactory results. Most importantly, the data shows that all respondents met the expectations of AP 8. In conclusion, there is a huge improvement in the post-test scores of the respondents after being exposed to the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs).

Teachers use proven learning methods such as the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Approach and the Developed Twister Game or Gamification to address the challenges in teaching AP 8, particularly the lack of students' interest.

The CTL Approach can strengthen the links between the learning environment and the community. Localization links the learning content specified in the curriculum to the local information and materials available in the learners' community while indigenization enhances learning competencies with the biogeographical, historical, and sociocultural context of the learner's community (Nuqui, 2017). The fact is, many students learn better and recollect information longer when concepts are taught in context. It also makes learning in school relevant and enriching.

Gamification in teaching Araling Panlipunan 8 is a powerful tool to increase the level of attentiveness of students. Simulating the game instructions aids students to participate more and absorb the lesson with ease, primarily because they are learning while enjoying it.

The research study of Angela Mae S. Castro (2020) revealed that the developed twister games or gamification in teaching Araling Panlipunan is more effective than the traditional lecture method. On a similar note, Veny Rose Garcia- Acojido (2021) published a journal about the Merits and Demerits of AP Teachers in Using Instructional Resources.

An article by Oka Agus Kurniawan Shavab (2018) disclosed that gamification is a successful technique for educating learners in history classes. It emphasizes how gamification is used as a learning method to capture the students' interest. Furthermore, Potenciano Conte Jr. (2017) cited that using games as a learning tool is highly acceptable. It showed that developed twister games increase the vocabulary of students.

According to Rachma Hasibuan and Nur Ika Sari Rakhmawati (2017), developing new learning strategies like the twister game is essential to improve a child's learning ability. Miran Sakhatov (2019) also revealed that didactic games are duly endorsed learning strategies for history classes. Similarly, Polona Jančič (Faculty of Education, University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia) and Vlasta Hus (Faculty of Education, University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia) (2018) discovered that students are enthusiastic about game-based learning in AP.

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4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of Grade 8 respondents during the Second Quarter period before and after being exposed to the use of DIMs?

Table 9. Distribution of Respondents' Pre and Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter Period Before and After Being Exposed to the Use of DIMs

Score	Pre-test Scores in AP8		Post-test Scores in AP8		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	
21 – 25	-	-	66	41.25	Outstanding
16 – 20	6	3.75	62	38.75	Very Satisfactorily
11 – 15	63	39.38	32	20.00	Satisfactorily
6 – 10	75	46.87	-	-	Fairly Satisfactorily
0 – 5	16	10.00	-	-	Did not meet expectations
Total	160	100	160	100	

Legend: f - frequency % - Percent

Table 9 illustrates the pre-test and post-test scores in World History (AP 8) of the respondents during the second quarter period before and after the intervention of DIMs. The comparative data above clearly shows a huge difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents, indicating notable progress in their learning aptitude after being exposed to DIMs. It means that the highly encouraging improvement of the respondents' scores validates DIMs as effective learning instruments that motivate students and inspire active participation in classes resulting in enhanced learning and skills development.

Differentiated Instruction (DI) is a popular and practice-proven approach tailored to efficiently meet the diverse and distinctive needs of learners (Coubergs, Struyven, Vanthournout; et al., 2017). It also promotes inclusive education and aims to support academic learning and foster the social and emotional development of the students. This further means that students can learn and acquire content and competencies using varied resources and strategies, allowing them to demonstrate knowledge, values, and skills based on their unique needs and preferences. The effectiveness of DI is frequently linked to the best learning outcomes in terms of academic performance and achievement because it can be described as a collection of instructional strategies that enable teachers to ensure that all students, regardless of their characteristics, have positive and successful learning situations (Loreman, 2017).

Ho: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores in World History (AP 8) among Grade 8 respondents during the second quarter period.

Table 10. Test of Difference Between the Respondents' Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores in AP8 during the Second Quarter Period Before and After Being Exposed to the Use of DIMs

	<i>n</i>	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	<i>t</i>	Two-tailed (df =159, α = .05) Critical Value (CV)	p-value P(T<=t) two-tail
Pre-test	160	10.00	3.33	-68.11	+/- 1.97	0.00
Post-test	160	19.23	3.58			

The results from the pre-test ($M=10.00$, $SD=3.33$) and post-test ($M=19.23$, $SD=3.58$) scores in AP 8 before and after being exposed to the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) show a remarkable increase in the scores obtained by the respondents. This difference is significant because the null hypothesis is rejected, $t\text{-stats} (df=159) = -68.11 > t\text{-cv} = +/- 1.98$, and p-value ($0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, we conclude that the respondents' exposure to DIMs resulted in a considerable improvement in their post-test scores in World History (AP 8).

Deunk et al. (2018) conducted a meta-analysis to examine the effects of DI on the cognitive abilities of primary kids. The

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analysis of 21 studies revealed that DI generally has a beneficial impact on the pupils' academic achievements (Deunk et al., 2018). A parallel study by Nusser and Gehrer (2020) showed positive progress in the German reading competence of secondary students.

A previous research study by Kulakow (2020) showed that students following a competency-based DI learning method displayed higher levels of academic self-concept than students engaged with the traditional learning method. Similarly, M.S. Al-Shehri (2020) investigated the effect of DI on the critical thinking aptitude of grade six students, and evidence showed that an instructional program based on DI generated a much better performance of the students in terms of their critical thinking skills.

In 2018, Parsons et al. stated that adapting Differentiated Instruction is "the cornerstone of effective instruction" and "the gold standard teachers should strive for."

5. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 Learners in the Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product and Affect/Environment and their Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) for the Second Quarter Period?

Ho: That there is no significant relationship between the Perception of Grade 8 Learners in the Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product and Affect/Environment and their Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) for the Second Quarter Period.

Table 11. Perceived Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials and Its Relationship to the Four Key Elements of Differentiated Instruction: Content, Process, Product, and Affect/Environment

Key Elements of Differentiated Instruction	Pearson r	Degree of Correlation
Content	0.96	Very Strong Positive Correlation
Process	0.91	Very Strong Positive Correlation
Product	0.87	Very Strong Positive Correlation
Affect / Environment	0.92	Very Strong Positive Correlation
Over-all	0.96	Very Strong Positive Correlation

Legend:	$+/- 1.00$	Perfect Correlation	$0.20 \leq r < 0.4$	Weak Correlation
	$0.8 \leq r < 1.0$	Very Strong Correlation	$0.00 \leq r < 0.2$	Very Weak Correlation
	$0.6 \leq r < 0.8$	Strong Correlation	$0.00 = r $	No Correlation
	$0.4 \leq r < 0.6$	Moderately Strong Correlation		

Table 11 exhibits the relationship between the perception of Grade 8 learners in the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product, and Affect/Learning Environment, and their post-test scores in World History (AP 8) for the second quarter period. The relevant computation using Pearson r resulted in a *very strong positive correlation* between the perception of students and their corresponding post-test scores. In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 learners in the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) as to content, process, product, affect/environment and the obtained post-test scores. Therefore, the higher the level of perception, the higher the correlation.

"Perception is the process of organizing, identifying, and interpreting sensory data to represent and understand the information or environment presented" (Schacter, 2011). There are three stages of perception, according to Qiong (2017): selection, organization, and interpretation.

Students' well-being, social inclusion, and academic self-concept of self- perception are three critical student outcome factors thoroughly investigated in research and literature (DeVries et al., 2018; Venetz et al., 2019).

The quantitative study by Alnahdi et al. (2021) revealed that the perception of students regarding their teachers' use of DI strongly predicted students perceived emotional and social inclusion as well as their academic self-concept. These findings showcase the correlation between the implementation of DI and the students' non-academic outcomes (Alnahdi et al., 2021).

CHAPTER 4 DISCUSSION

Summary

The study focused on the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) of World History (AP 8) students in Grade 8 at Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School during the academic year 2022-2023.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions: 1) What is the perception of the Grade 8 respondents in the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) as to: Content, Process, Product, Affect / Environment 2) What are the Pre-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period before being exposed to the use of DIMs? 3) What are the Post-test Scores of the Grade 8 respondents in World History (AP 8) during the Second Quarter period after being exposed to the

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use of DIMs? 4) Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of Grade 8 respondents during the Second Quarter period before and after being exposed to the use of DIMs? 5) Is there a significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 Learners in the Use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product and Affect/Environment and their Post-test Scores in World History (AP 8) for the Second Quarter Period?

From the inferential problems stated, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

- There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents before and after being exposed to differentiated instructional materials through its four key elements Content, Process, Product, and Affect/Environment.
- There is no significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 Learners in the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) through its four key elements: Content, Process, Product, and Affect/Environment and their post- test scores in World History (AP 8) for the second quarter period.

This study utilized the pre-test/post-test group design involving the same group of respondents before and after being exposed to the use of DIMs. The respondents were composed of 160 students that have been taken from the Grade eight level. Validated pre-test and post-test scores were the main instruments in the study.

The following are the salient findings of the study:

1. During the pre-test when students were not exposed to DIMs, almost half (46.87%) of them obtained a fair verbal interpretation of the subject, while 39.38% got satisfactory scores. On the other hand, 3.75% scored very satisfactorily but 10% did not meet expectations. Unfortunately, no one (0%) obtained an outstanding score.
2. The post-test wherein students were exposed to DIMs showed that 41.25% obtained an outstanding verbal interpretation of World History (AP 8), 38.75% scored very satisfactory, and 20% with satisfactory results. Impressively, all respondents met the expectations of the subject at this point.
3. The comparative data between the pre-test and post-test, before and after students were exposed to DIMs showed that there is a significant difference in the obtained scores showing a remarkable improvement subsequently.
4. This difference is significant because the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, the use of DIMs resulted in a remarkable improvement in the scores of the respondents in World History (AP 8).
5. There is a very strong positive correlation between the four key elements and a significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 learners in the use of differentiated instructional materials (DIMs) as to content, process, product, and affect/learning environment vis-à-vis the obtained post-test scores.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The pre-test results obtained by the respondents required improvement since 10% did not meet expectations and the majority merely scored fairly. Proper intervention and assistance must be immediately extended to expand their verbal interpretation skills.
2. The post-test results showed remarkable progress as almost half of the respondents got an outstanding score while everyone met the expectations in World History (AP 8) hence, it can be assumed that the exposure of the students to the use of DIMs effectively resolved the deficiencies or learning gaps during the pre-test.
3. The significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results showing remarkable progress subsequently, implies the vital need for instructors to use DIMs in teaching World History (AP 8) to Grade 8 students during in-person classes.
4. The rejection of the null hypothesis underscores the key role of DIMs in helping students maximize their verbal interpretation and learning abilities.
5. The very strong positive correlation and significant relationship between the perception of Grade 8 students vis-à-vis the result of their post-test, signifies that the higher the level of perception, the higher the correlation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

- 1) Since it was found out that there was a significant difference between the pre- test and post-test scores of the respondents, the use of DIMs should be employed to the learners all-throughout the school year to continuously help improve the performance of their learners.
- 2) The study provides positive outcomes on the use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) through content, process, product, affect/environment in assisting and motivating Grade 8 students to learn World History (AP 8) effectively, teachers may strongly consider its use immediately.

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

- 3) Proper implementation and utilization of the established Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in World History (AP 8) for Grade 8 students at Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School during in-person classes as supplementary learning materials to the existing modules through the following steps:
Step 1: Establishment, endorsement, and approval of the materials;
Step 2: Progress tracking and evaluation of the result-based outcomes and assessment of its impact on the learners' verbal interpretation and learning skills improvement;
Step 3: Revisit, review, and revision of the learning material after three (3) years as necessary, to adapt to the dynamics and contemporary needs of the subject matter;
- 4) Integration of the materials and imposition of Continuing Quality Improvement (CQI) in the teaching-learning landscape through In-Service Training (INSET), seminar workshops, and other Continuing Development Programs (CDP) among teachers.
- 5) Parallel studies must be considered and conducted for the use of DIMs as supplementary learning material in teaching other subjects across all grade levels for in-person or face-to-face classes.

DEDICATION

This thesis manuscript is the fruit of countless and laborious sacrifices. I heartily and proudly dedicate this work to the people who served as an inspiration. From my Granny, Papa, Mama Susie in heaven, Ninang Rhidz, sisterets, brothers, nephews, nieces, to my classmates, circle of friends and colleagues and superiors especially my students who extended their help, guidance, and assistance, in any manner, in the midst of challenges while doing this project. I am truly thankful for having all of you in my life.

I also dedicate this study to my second home, Col. Lauro D. Dizon MIHS, and to my forever and beloved institution- Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo.

Above all, our God Almighty, who showered us with His blessings in our everyday lives, especially for the strength, courage, patience, wisdom, time, and guidance in the realization of this research study.

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Perseverance, inspiration, and motivation have always played a key role in the success of my endeavor. It was indeed a difficult journey, but I am so thankful, grateful, and blessed to have so many loving and supportive people rooting for my success.

I would like to express my heartfelt appreciation to everyone who helped in any manner, and shared effort, and knowledge for my thesis defense journey.

First, **my loving family** (my inspiration in pursuing my MA), for their moral encouragement, financial assistance, as well as their spiritual support in every path I take... To my ever-loving Inay (Granny), Papa, Ninong Odi, mga sisterets, brothers, nieces and nephews, and my dear Ninang Ridz and Tita Yeng.

My sincerest thanks go to **Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar**, my Thesis Adviser (and former PolSci Student in Research), for his unwavering support, patience, motivation, and immense knowledge.

I would like to give my genuine gratefulness to the panelist: PLSP President and my Thesis Adviser, **Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar**, my Subject Specialist- **Dr. Marc Lester F. Quintana**, my Language Specialist (and HT in AP) - **Dr. Elmer C. Escala**, my Statistician- **Prof. Vladimir P. Reyes**, and to our Graduate School Dean- **Dr. Preciosa D. Villacruel**. I salute your expertise, advice, comments, and suggestions which made my oral defense easier to present. Words are not enough to thank you all (especially for giving me an A+).

To my beloved professors (including my panel), **Dr. Janet N. Suaverdez**, **Dr. Donny Aries C. Malvar**, **Dr. Rommel D. Mallari**, and **Prof. Jay Anne V. Consignado** thank you all for sharing us your wisdom.

Special thanks also to our former and current School Heads - **Mam Editha**

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To **Mam Aleli C. Juliano**, **Mam Sarah S. Javilagon**, **Mam Marife B. Calanasan**, and **Mam Lyn L. Joaquin**, super big thanks for helping me validate my research instruments. Truly appreciate your time and expertise.

To my **Dizon High friends, colleagues**, and G8Chief Adviser, **Mam Rubelyn N. Enero**, my **AP Familia** headed by Doc Elmer, for their all-out support, love, care, and encouragement. Thank you for always believing in my potential. I super love you all. my PLSP friends, kapatid Mam Luz Bandian, Kumadre Mam Fepot, Mam Yena, and Sir AJ.

To **my dear students** – for being responsible and participative students. Special thanks also to my pre-service teachers: Sir Zeke and Mam Ckhrystel.

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To my stress relievers- my fur babies, Princess, Elie, Charlie, and Tommy
– plus Sendo, Bakbak and Lucky.

To my Dear **Mama Susie**, this is also for you, I miss you and love you with all my heart. Still wish that you were here.

Above all, **Jesus Christ**, our Lord, and Savior, for giving me the wisdom, strength, and ability in exploring things, the guidance in surpassing all the trials encountered, and for giving me the determination to pursue and complete this study. I give back all the honor and glory to You. *Ad Majorem Dei Gloriam*.

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Appendix A: Request Letter as Member of the Panel of Evaluators

7 September 2022

Dr. SIGFREDO C. ADAJAR
 PLSP University President
 Brgy. San Jose, San Pablo City

Dear **Dr. Adajar**:

Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of my second home, Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise to be my **Thesis Adviser** for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Please feel free to give our comments and suggestions for the improvement of my study. Your positive response is very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
 Researcher

Accepted and Approved by::

Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar
 PLSP University President

"Primed to Lead and Serve for Progress"

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7 September 2022

MARC LESTER F. QUINTANA, RN, MAN, EdD.
Adjunct Professor PLSP Graduate School
Brgy. San Jose, San Pablo City

Dear Dr. Quintana:

Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of my second home, Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise to be my **Subject Specialist** for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Please feel free to give our comments and suggestions for the improvement of my study. Your positive response is very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Approved by:

Dr. Sigfredo C. Anajar
Thesis Adviser

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

7 September 2022

ELMER C. ESCALA, EdD.PhD.
Head Teacher 1-AP Dept.
Col. Lauro D. Dizon MIHS, San Pablo City

Dear Dr. Escala:

Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of my second home, Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the **Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP)** with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise to be my **Language Specialist / Technical Editor** for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Please feel free to give our comments and suggestions for the improvement of my study. Your positive response is very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Approved by:

Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar
Thesis Adviser

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

7 September 2022

Prof. VLADIMIR P. REYES
Mater Teacher III-Math Department
San Pablo City Science Integrated High School, San Pablo City

Dear **Prof. Reyes**:

Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of my second home, Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the **Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP)** with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise to be my **Statistician** for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Please feel free to give our comments and suggestions for the improvement of my study. Your positive response is very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Approved by:

Dr. Sigfredo C. Adajar
Thesis Adviser

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Appendix B: Certificate of Content Validation

CERTIFICATE OF CONTENT VALIDATION

We hereby certify that the questionnaire prepared by **Jennifer A. Rayco** for her research entitled **"The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners** has been validated.

DR. SIGFREDO C. ADAJAR
Adviser

DR. MARC LESTER F. QUINTANA
Member

DR. ELMER C. ESCALA
Member

VLADIMIR P. REYES, MA
Member

PRECIOSA D. VILLACRUEL, PhD
DEAN

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix C: *Research Ethics Clearance Form*

**OFFICE OF THE VICE PRESIDENT FOR
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION**
Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo
Brgy. San Jose, San Pablo City

RESEARCH ETHICS CLEARANCE FORM		
Research Title: The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners		
Names of Student Researcher(s): Jennifer A. Rayco		
College/ Department: Graduate School		
Course/Program: Master of Arts in Education – Educational Management		
Expected Duration of the Project: from: September 2022 to: April 2023		
Ethical Principles observed/violated	OBSERVED	VIOLATED
1.Honesty	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.Objectivity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.Informed Consent/ Confidentiality	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.Competence	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.Fabrication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.Falsification	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.Plagiarism	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To the best of my knowledge, the ethical issues listed above have been addressed in the research.		
 DR. SIGFREDO C. ADAJAR Adviser		Date:
Noted by: DR. PRECIOSA D. VILLACRUEL Program Chairperson		Date:
Received by: PAUL ADRIAN S. AVECILLA Intellectual Property Rights Head		Date:

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix D: Letter to the School Principal

2 March 2023

DR. LINA M. LAGURAS
Principal IV-CLDDMIHS
San Pablo City

Dear **Dr. Laguras**:

Masayang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the **Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP)** with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am respectfully requesting approval from your good office to allow me to conduct and facilitate a survey from my selected students in Grade 8 as respondents for my research study entitled "*The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in Teaching World History for In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners*".

Rest assured that all survey-related data will be handled with the utmost confidentiality.

Thank you for your usual support.

More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

*approved by
Dr. J. 2/6/2023*

Appendix E: Request Letter as Research Instrument Validators

I. Survey Questionnaire and II. Pre/Post Tests

20 February 2023

Dr. ELMER C. ESCALA
 Head Teacher 1-AP Dept.
 CLDDMIHS, San Pablo City

Dear Dr. Escala:

Magandang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise in evaluating the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests as instruments to be used for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY FOR IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Your comments and suggestions are very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
 Researcher

Agreed and accepted by:

ELMER C. ESCALA, EdD, PhD.
 Research Expert/Validator
 Head Teacher 1-AP Dept.
 CLDDMIHS

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20 February 2023

Mrs. MARIFE B. CALANASAN
Master Teacher 1-AP Dept.
CLDDMIHS, San Pablo City

Dear Mam Calanasan:

Magandang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise in evaluating the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests as instruments to be used for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Your comments and suggestions are very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

Jenny
JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Agreed and accepted by:

M. Calanasan
MARIFE B. CALANASAN
Research Expert/Validator

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

20 February 2023

Mrs. LYN L. JOAQUIN
Master Teacher 1-AP Dept.
CLDDMIHS, San Pablo City

Dear Mam Joaquin:

Magandang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise in evaluating the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests as instruments to be used for my research study entitled "**THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY FOR IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS**".

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire and pre/posttests for your perusal. Your comments and suggestions are very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Agreed and accepted by:

LYN L. JOAQUIN
Research Expert/Validator
Master Teacher 1- AP Dept.
CLDDMIHS

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

 CITY OF SAN PABLO OFFICIAL SEAL		
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20 February 2023

MRS. ALELI C. JULIANO
Master Teacher 1-English Dept.
CLDDMIHS, San Pablo City

Dear **Mam Juliano**:

Magandang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the **Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP)** with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise in evaluating the survey questionnaire as one of the instruments to be used for my research study entitled **"THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY FOR IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS"**.

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire for your perusal. Your comments and suggestions are very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Agreed and accepted by:

ALELI C. JULIANO
Research Expert/Validator
Master Teacher 1- English Dept.
CLDDMIHS

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20 February 2023

MRS. SARA S. JAVILAGON
Coordinator-English Dept.
CLDDMIHS, San Pablo City

Dear Mam Javilagon:

Magandang buhay! Greetings of love and peace.

My primary goal as one of the faculty members of our beloved school is to become a more productive and competent individual in pursuit of better service to the school, students, and other stakeholders. Accordingly, I am currently working on my research paper for my Master's degree at the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo (PLSP) with a Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management to further my knowledge, skills, and potential.

Given the above, I am humbly requesting your expertise in evaluating the survey questionnaire as one of the instruments to be used for my research study entitled "**THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS**".

Attached is a copy of the survey questionnaire for your perusal. Your comments and suggestions are very much appreciated.

Thank you for your usual support. More power and God Bless!

Sincerely yours,

JENNIFER A. RAYCO
Researcher

Agreed and accepted by:

SARA S. JAVILAGON
Research Expert/Validator

"Primed to Lead and Serve for Progress"

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix F: Informed Consent Form

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Informed Consent Form

Dear Respondent:

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Please read the following information carefully and feel free to ask the researcher if anything is unclear or if you need more information or clarification about this research study. Furthermore, the researcher will use the collected data as groundwork for developing Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMS) in **Araling Panlipunan 8 -World History** to enhance the curriculum for "in-person" classes of Grade-8 learners.

You are chosen as an interviewee because the researcher is aware that you could bring substantial responses needed for the realization of this study.

During the conduct of this study, you will be asked to answer the questionnaire provided by the researcher. Your participation in this study is voluntary. If you decide to participate, you will be asked to sign this consent form. After signing this consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

Your response in this research will be anonymous and will be used solely for this research purpose. Only the researcher will have the access to your responses which will remain confidential.

Thank you for your cooperation.

Sincerely,

Jennifer A. Rayco, LPT
Researcher
jennifer_rayco@deped.gov.ph

Approved by:

DR. JOHN MATTHEW A. AQUINO, RDPO
University Data Privacy Officer

Reviewed by:

MR. PAUL ADRIAN S. AVECILLA, RPM
Intellectual Property Rights Head/OVPRI

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

CONSENT

I have read the provided information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I understand that I will be given a copy of this form, and the researcher will keep another copy on file. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____
Signature of Participant: _____
Date: _____

Print Name of Researcher: **Jennifer A. Rayco**
Signature of Researcher: _____
Date: February 1, 2023

Print Name of Impartial Witness: _____
Signature of Impartial Witness: _____
Date: _____

[If the participant is illiterate]

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Print Name of Witness: _____
Signature of Witness: _____
Date: _____

A literate witness must sign (if possible, this person should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the research team.

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix G: Research Instrument – Survey Questionnaire

INSTRUMENT 1: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent:

Good day!

This questionnaire attempts to investigate the **“The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) in Teaching World History for In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners”**.

The study intends to determine the perception of the respondents about the effectiveness of the use of **Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs)** in teaching World History. Furthermore, the researcher will use the collected data as groundwork for developing **Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs)** in **Araling Panlipunan 8-World History** to enhance the curriculum for “in-person” classes of Grade-8 learners.

Kindly fill up the answer sheet honestly or check the box corresponding to your answer. Once finished, please return the answer sheet and the questionnaire to the researcher. Rest assured that all information will be handled with the utmost confidentiality.

Thank you very much for your cooperation. God bless!

Sincerely yours,

Jennifer A. Rayco

Researcher

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

INSTRUCTION: Below are statements pertaining to the *Four Key Elements of Differentiated Instructions*. Kindly read each statement carefully and answer them honestly. Please rate the extent of your **agreement / disagreement** using the scale below. Put a checkmark (✓) on the item that applies to your stand or position.

Rate	Description
Scale: 4	- I Strongly Agree
3	- I Agree
2	- I Disagree
1	- I Strongly Disagree

A. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO CONTENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to **content**?

Content pertains to the specific readings, research, or materials, the learners will study.

Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.				
2. enhances visual presentations to add appeal to the lecture notes by means of <i>pictures, tables, diagrams, graphic organizers, and the like</i> .				
3. uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.				
4. presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .				
5. utilizes <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson				
6. designs the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.				
7. explains words that are not familiar to the learners.				
8. applies enrichment activities with varying difficulties.				
9. gives various resources, materials, and worksheets the learners can utilize.				
10. sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

B. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PROCESS

How do you perceive the teacher’s utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to process?

Process is how the lesson is designed for the learners.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	<i>I Strongly Agree</i>	<i>I Agree</i>	<i>I Disagree</i>	<i>I Strongly Disagree</i>
1.	presents each lesson in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners.				
2.	uses visual materials such as pictures, maps, tarpapel, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.				
3.	makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.				
4.	gives various examples about the lesson.				
5.	encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.				
6.	designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well with the lesson.				
7.	gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.				
8.	provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners’ unique talents and skills.				
9.	allows the learners to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.				
10.	encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.				

C. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PRODUCT

How do you perceive the teacher’s utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to product?

Product includes the kinds of work products the learners will be asked to complete.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	<i>I Strongly Agree</i>	<i>I Agree</i>	<i>I Disagree</i>	<i>I Strongly Disagree</i>
1.	provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.				
2.	sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.				
3.	creates tasks based on a real-world experiences/applications.				
4.	allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.				
5.	shows sample of an output and explains how it was made.				
6.	gives a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

7. explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.				
8. encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.				
9. explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.				
10. equips differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.				

D. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT

How do you perceive the teacher’s utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment?

Affect/environment refers to the rules, procedures, and routines to ensure that students are actively involved in learning.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
1.	ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and well-ventilated.				
2.	makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.				
3.	promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environment for all learners.				
4.	sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest before the lesson starts.				
5.	requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during, and after the discussion of the lesson.				
6.	motivates all learners to participate in the discussion and accomplishment of various tasks.				
7.	recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do-well in class.				
8.	allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.				
9.	encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.				
10.	gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group’s performance tasks/outputs.				

Thank you for sharing your time in answering this survey questionnaire honestly!

Appendix H: Research Instrument – Pre/Post Tests

Talaan ng Espesipikasyon sa Araling Panlipunan 8

**INSTRUMENT 2: Pre-Test / Post-Test
IKALAWANG MARKAHAN**

MGA KASANAYAN SA PAGKAKATUTO MELCs (Most Essential Learning Competencies)	BLG. NG ARAW NG PAGTUTURO	KINALALAGYAN NG AYTEM	BLG. NG AYTEM	BAHAGDAN
***Nasusuri ang kabihasnang Minoan, Mycenaean at kabihasnang klasikong Greece.	6	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	6	24
***Naipapaliwanag ang kontribusyon ng kabihasnang Romano.	3	7, 8	2	8
***Nasusuri ang pag-usbong at pag-unlad ng mga klasikong kabihasnang sa: Africa – Songhai, Mali, atbp; America – Aztec, Maya, Olmec, Inca, atbp; Mga Pulo sa Pacific – Nazca, Polynesia, Micronesia, Melanesia.	6	9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16	8	32
***Nasusuri ang mga pagbabagong naganap sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon: Politika (Pyudalismo, Holy Roman Empire), Ekonomiya (Manoryalismo), Sosyo-kultural (Paglakas ng Simbahang Katoliko, Krusada).	6	17, 18, 19, 20, 21	5	20
***Natataya ang impuwensya ng mga kaisipang lumaganap sa Gitnang Panahon.	3	22, 23, 24, 25	4	16
KABUUAN	24		25	100%

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Note: All the questions in this Pre-Test/Post Test are taken from the Alternative Delivery Mode of Department of Education SDO-Pasig Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 which are all based on the MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies) for the Second Grading Period. These standardized questions were validated by SDO Pasig.

INSTRUMENT 2: PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

IKALAWANG MARKAHAN

ARALING PANLIPUNAN 8-KASAYSAYAN NG DAIGDIG

Pangalan: _____

Marka: _____

Baitang at Seksyon: _____

Petsa: _____

Panuto: Basahing mabuti ang mga sumusunod na pahayag. Piliin ang **TITIK** ng pinakaangkop na sagot mula sa mga pagpipilian at isulat sa inyong sagutang papel.

1. Ayon sa alamat ng sibilisasyong Minoan, siya ang anak ng diyos na si Zeus at Europa at hari ng naturang sibilisasyon.
A. Agamemnon B. Minos C. Daedalus D. Theseus
2. Mga larawang mabilisan subalit bihasang ipininta sa mga dinding na basa ng plaster upang kumapit nang husto sa pader ang mga pigment ng metal at mineral oxide.
A. Mask B. Palayok C. Fresco D. Corbel
3. Isang English na arkeologong nakadiskubre sa kabihasnang Minoan nang mahukay ang Knossos noong 1899.
A. Arthur Evans B. Michael Ventris C. Henrich Schliemann D. John Chadwick
4. Ito ang politikal na ideolohiya na ipinanukala ng Athens na siyang nangangahulugang pamahalaan ng nakararami.
A. aristokrasya B. monarkiya C. oligarkiya D. demokrasya
5. Ito ang maliit na yunit ng komunidad na bumubuo sa kabihasnang Greece. Ito ang nagsisilbing lungsod-estado sa Gresya na siyang sentro ng kalakalan at pamayanan.
A. agora B. polis C. acropolis D. metropolis
6. Pamublikong gusali na nagsilbing libingan ng mga emperador sa Roma. Itinayo ito bilang templo sa Roma noong 126 C.E. at nananatili pa rin ang istruktura hanggang ngayon.
A. Colosseum B. Aqueduct C. Pantheon D. Appian Way
7. Ito ay isang bukas na teatro o **amphitheater** ay naging sentro ng labanan ng mga gladiator. Nagsilbi ito bilang isang malaking dulaan na may 50,000 upuan. Ipinagawa ni Emperador Vespasian noong 69-79 C.E.
A. Aqueduct B. Colosseum C. Appian Way D. Pantheon
8. Batas ang pinakadakilang ambag ng mga Romano sa sibilisasyong kanluran. Ano ang tawag sa kauna-unahang nasusulat na batas sa Rome at nagsilbing ugat ng **Batas Romano**. Dahil dito, umunlad ang kalagayan ng mga plebeian, pinahintulutan na silang humawak ng kapangyarihan sa pamahalaan at makapag-asawa ng patrician.
A. Law of the Twelve Tables B. Code of Hammurabi C. Canon Law D. Vedas

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

9. Saan bahagi ng Africa nakilala ang tatlong imperyo imperyo ng *Ghana, Mali, at Songhai* na siyang naging makapangyarihan dulot rin ng pakikipagkalakalan sa mga mamamayan sa labas ng Africa?
- A. Hilaga B. Timog C. Silangan D. Kanluran
10. Sila ay tinaguriang mahuhusay na inhenyero at tagapagtayo ng mga estruktura sa Amerika tulad ng mga kanal o *aqueduct*, mga dam, gayundin ng sistema ng irigasyon, liwasan, at mga pamilihan.
- A. Inca B. Olmec C. Aztec D. Maya
11. Ang pinakamahalagang diyos ng araw ng mga Aztec dahil sila ay mga magsasaka na taimtim na umaasa sa mga puwersa ng kalikasan at sinasamba ang mga ito bilang mga diyos. Mahalaga ang sikat ng araw sa pananim ng mga magsasaka kaya sinusuyo at hinahandugan nila ang naturang diyos.
- A. Tlaloc B. Huitzilopochtli C. Quetzalcoatl D. Pachakuti
12. Ito ang tawag sa sentro ng pamayanan sa Polynesia na kadalasang nasa gilid ng mga bundok. Ito ay tanghalan ng mga ritwal at pagpupulong kung saan nakapaligid dito ang tirahan ng mga pari at mga banal na estruktura.
- A. Tohua B. Tenochtitlan C. Chinampas D. Texcoco
13. Bakit tinawag na *Trans-Sahara* ang kalakalan sa Hilagang Africa? Dahil _____?
- A. dito nagsimula ang sistema ng kalakalan sa buong mundo.
B. dinarayo ito ng mga turista upang masilayan ang Sahara Desert.
C. tinatawid ng mga nomadikong mangangalakal ang disyertong ito sakay ng caravan.
D. maraming ginto ang makikita dito kaya marami ang nangahas na sakupin ito ng mga karatig-lugar.
14. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang magandang katangian ng mga kabihasnang sa America ang dapat tularan ng kasalukuyang panahon?
- A. May sariling batas na sinusunod ang bawat mamamayan.
B. Naging sarado ang kanilang mga pamayanan sa mga dayuhan.
C. Nagtalaga sila ng mga matatalino at mayayamang pinuno sa bawat pamayanan.
D. Nakapagtatag ng mahusay na pamayanan sa kabila ng hamon ng kapaligiran.
15. Bakit mahalaga ang *inhenyerang haydrolik* sa kabihasnang Inca? Dahil ito ay _____?
- A. Nakakatulong ito sa pagdaloy ng tubig patungong disyertong bundok.
B. Nagsisilbi itong tagapamagitan sa kalakalan ng iba't ibang produkto sa Africa
C. Nagsisilbing natural na proteksiyon ng kabihasnang sa pagpasok ng mga dayuhan.
D. Nakakatulong ito sa pagkakaroon ng maayos na transportasyon at komunikasyon.
16. Alin sa mga *Pulo sa Pacific* ang artistiko pagdating sa mga maskara, pigura, at kagamitang panseremonya na gawa sa kahoy, talukab ng pagong at kabibe napininturahan ng itim, pula o puti.
- A. Polynesia B. Melanesia C. Micronesia D. Nazca
17. Ano ang pinakamahalagang anyo ng kayamanan noong Panahon ng *Piyudalismo*?
- A. Alahas B. Ginto C. Lupa D. Mineral
18. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang **HINDI** totoo sa *Sistemang Piyudalismo*?
- A. Piyudalismo ang sistemang politikal sa Panahong Medieval.
B. Ang hari at panginoon ang tanging nagmamay-ari ng mga lupain.
C. Kasunduan sa pagitan ng panginoon at basalyo.
D. Ang mga alipin ay may karapatang mag may-ari ng lupa.

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19. Katapat ito ng pyudalismo. Ito ay sistemang pang-ekonomiya na gumagabay sa paraan ng pagsasaka sa buhay ng magbubukid at ugnayan sa lord ng manor. Ang mga magbubukid ay nagigigay serbisyo sa isang pyudal na hari o nagmamay-ari ng lupa kapalit ng kanilang proteksyon.

- A. Manoryalismo B. Imperyalismo C. Kolonyalismo D. Neokolonyalismo

20. Tawag sa mga *nobles* o dugong bughaw na nakatanggap ng lupa ay mula sa hari. Bilang kapalit ng lupa, sila ay susumpa ng katapatan sa hari at magbibigay ng serbisyong militar. Sa panahon na kailanganin ng hari ang tulong militar gaya ng panahon ng digmaan, inaasahang sila ay handang tumulong.

- A. Slave B. Peasant C. Clergy D. Vassal

21. Bakit kinilala si *Charlemagne* bilang unang *Holy Roman Emperor at Protector of the Church*?

- A. Naging masunurin siya sa mga naisin ng Simbahan.
B. Nakuha nya ang mga teritoryo ng Banal na Lupain.
C. Napasuko niya ang mga Lombards na kalaban ng Simbahan at nawakasan ang pag-aalsa laban sa Santo Papa.
D. Ipinalaganap ang Kristiyanismo hanggang Asya.

22. Ito ay tumutukoy sa mayayamang mangangalakal na naging makapangyarihang uri sa Medieval France.

- A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft guild C. Merchant guild D. Reformist

23. Nang lumaki ang mga bayan, ang mga artisan ay nagtatag ng sariling guild. Halimbawa ay ang mga karpintero, sastre, panadero, at iba pang hanapbuhay na may sariling angking kakayanan.

- A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft guild C. Merchant guild D. Reformist

24. Siya ay isang Pransiskanong monghe sa Oxford. Tinawag siyang "*tagapanguna ng makabagong agham*", dahil sa kanyang ambag sa kemistri at sipnayan (matimatika).

- A. Rodrigo Vivar B. Francis Bacon C. Geoffrey Chaucer D. Dante Alighieri ng England

25. Ito ang nangangalaga sa mga suliraning namamagitan sa mga manggagawa at namumuhunan.

- A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Reformist C. Knight D. Guild

SUSI SA PAGWAWASTO:

- | | | | | |
|------|-------|-------|-------|-------|
| 1. B | 6. C | 11. B | 16. B | 21. C |
| 2. C | 7. B | 12. A | 17. C | 22. A |
| 3. A | 8. A | 13. C | 18. D | 23. B |
| 4. D | 9. D | 14. D | 19. A | 24. B |
| 5. B | 10. C | 15. A | 20. D | 25. D |

"Ating balikan, mga lihim ng nakaraan,
Bakas ng lumipas, marapat pakaingatn,
Anino ng kahapon, bigyang-kulay at saysay sa kasalukuyan
Ратана ng Kasaysayan, kumukubog sa ating kinabukasan". - Мам Јенму А. Рауко

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FOR SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMS) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS

Direction: Good day! Please take time to review and validate this instrument to ensure the validity and correctness of the content and examples. This will help the researcher to measure and determine if the indicators per parameter are appropriate and properly structured. Please respond to each item by putting a checkmark on the corresponding column. Thank you and God bless!

INSTRUCTION	<p>INSTRUCTION: Below are statements pertaining to the <i>Four Key Elements of Differentiated Instructions</i>. Kindly read each statement carefully and answer them honestly. Please rate the extent of your agreement / disagreement using the scale below. Put a checkmark (✓) on the item that applies to your stand or position.</p>		
	<p>Rate Scale:4 - 3 - 2 - 1 -</p>	<p>Description 1 Strongly Agree I Agree I Disagree I Strongly Disagree</p>	
Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks

A. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO CONTENT

*How do you perceive the teacher’s utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to **content**?*

Content pertains to the specific readings, research, or materials, the learners will study.

Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<i>The teacher...</i>				
1. provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.				
2. enhances visual presentations to add appeal to the lecture notes by means of <i>pictures, tables, diagrams, graphic organizers, and the like</i> .				
3. uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.				
4. presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .				
5. utilizes <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson				

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6. designs the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.				
7. explains words that are not familiar to the learners.				
8. applies enrichment activities with varying difficulties.				
9. gives various resources, materials, and worksheets the learners can utilize.				
10. sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.				

B. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PROCESS

How do you perceive the teacher’s utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to process?

Process is how the lesson is designed for the learners.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	presents each lesson in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners.				
2.	uses visual materials such as pictures, maps, tarpapel, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.				
3.	makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.				
4.	gives various examples about the lesson.				
5.	encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.				
6.	designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well to the lesson.				
7.	gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.				
8.	provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners’ unique talents and skills.				
9.	allows the learners to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.				
10.	encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.				

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C. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PRODUCT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to product?

Product includes the kinds of work products the learners will be asked to complete.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.				
2.	sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.				
3.	creates tasks based on a real-world experiences/applications.				
4.	allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.				
5.	shows sample of an output and explains how it was made.				
6.	gives a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.				
7.	explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.				
8.	encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.				
9.	explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.				
10.	equips differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.				

D. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment?

Affect/environment refers to the rules, procedures, and routines to ensure that students are actively involved in learning.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and well-ventilated.				
2.	makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.				
3.	promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environment for all learners.				
4.	sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest before the lesson starts.				
5.	requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during and after the discussion of the lesson.				
6.	motivates all learners to participate in the discussion and accomplishment of various tasks.				
7.	recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do-well in class.				
8.	allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.				
9.	encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.				
10.	gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs.				

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Appendix J: *Instrument Validation for Pre/Post Tests*

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FOR PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS

Direction: Good day! Please take time to review and validate this instrument to ensure the validity and correctness of the content and the alignment of every item to the learning competency including the plausibility of distractors. This will help the researcher to measure and determine if the questions included are appropriate and properly structured. Please respond to each item by putting a checkmark on the corresponding column. Thank you and God bless!

Note: All the questions in this Pre-Test/Post Test are taken from the Alternative Delivery Mode of Department of Education SDO-Pasig Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 which are all based on the MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies) for the Second Grading Period. These standardized questions were validated by SDO Pasig.

INSTRUMENT 2: PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

IKALAWANG MARKAHAN

ARALING PANLIPUNAN 8-KASAYSAYAN NG DAIGDIG

Pangalan: _____

Marka: _____

Baitang at Seksyon: _____

Petsa: _____

Panuto: Basahing mabuti ang mga sumusunod na pahayag. Piliin ang **TITIK** ng pinakaangkop na sagot mula sa mga pagpipilian at isulat sa inyong sagutang papel.

MELC #1 - ***Nasusuri ang kabihasnang Minoan, Mycenaean at kabihasnang klasiko ng Greece.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1. Ayon sa alamat ng sibilisasyong Minoan, siya ang anak ng diyos na si Zeus at Europa at hari ng naturang sibilisasyon. A. Agamemnon B. Minos C. Daedalus D. Theseus				
2. Mga larawang mabilisan subalit bihasang ipininta sa mga dinding na basa ng plaster upang kumapit nang husto sa pader ang mga pigment ng metal at mineral oxide. A. Mask B. Palayok C. Fresco D. Corbel				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>3. Isang English na arkeologong nakadiskubre sa kabihasnang Minoan nang mahukay ang Knossos noong 1899.</p> <p>A. Arthur Evans B. Michael Ventris C. Henrich Schleiman D. John Chadwick</p>				
<p>4. Ito ang politikal na ideolohiya na ipinanukala ng Athens na siyang nangangahulugang pamahalaan ng nakararami.</p> <p>A. aristokrasya B. monarkiya C. oligarkiya D. demokrasya</p>				
<p>5. Ito ang maliit na yunit ng komunidad na bumubuo sa kabihasnang Greece. Ito ang nagsisilbing lungsod-estado sa Gresya na siyang sentro ng kalakalan at pamayanan.</p> <p>A. agora B. polis C. acropolis D. metropolis</p>				
<p>6. Pamublikong gusali na nagsilbing libingan ng mga emperador sa Roma. Itinayo ito bilang templo sa Roma noong 126 C.E. at nananatili pa rin ang istruktura hanggang ngayon.</p> <p>A. Colosseum B. Aqueduct C. Pantheon D. Appian Way</p>				

MELC #2 - ***Naipapaliwanag ang kontribusyon ng Kabihasnang Romano.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>7. Ito ang maliit na yunit ng komunidad na bumubuo sa kabihasnang Greece. Ito ang nagsisilbing lungsod-estado sa Gresya na siyang sentro ng kalakalan at pamayanan.</p>				

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<p>A. agora B. polis C. acropolis D. metropolis</p>				
<p>8. Pamublikong gusali na nagsilbing libingan ng mga emperador sa Roma. Itinayo ito bilang templo sa Roma noong 126 C.E. at nananatili pa rin ang istruktura hanggang ngayon. A. Colosseum B. Aqueduct C. Pantheon D. Appian Way</p>				

MELC #3 - *Nasusuri ang pag-usbong at pag-unlad ng mga klasikong kabihasnan sa: Africa – Songhai, Mali, atbp; America – Aztec, Maya, Olmec, Inca, atbp; Mga Pulo sa Pacific – Nazca, Polynesia, Micronesia, Melanesia.**

Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>9. Saan bahagi ng Africa nakilala ang tatlong imperyo imperyo ng Ghana, Mali, at Songhai na siyang naging makapangyarihan dulot rin ng pakikipagkalakalan sa mga mamamayan sa labas ng Africa? A. Hilaga B. Timog C. Silangan D. Kanluran</p>				
<p>10. Sila ay tinaguriang mahuhusay na inhenyero at tagapagtayo ng mga estruktura sa Amerika tulad ng mga kanal o aqueduct, mga dam, gayundin ng sistema ng irigasyon, liwasan, at mga pamilihan. A. Inca B. Olmec C. Aztec D. Maya</p>				
<p>11. Ang pinakamahalagang diyos ng araw ng mga Aztec dahil sila ay mga magsasaka</p>				

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<p>na taimtim na umaasa sa mga puwersa ng kalikasan at sinasamba ang mga ito bilang mga diyos. Mahalaga ang sikat ng araw sa pananim ng mga magsasaka kaya sinusuyo at hinahandugan nila ang naturang diyos.</p> <p>A. Tlaloc B. Huitzilopochtli C. Quetzalcoatl D. Pachakuti</p>				
<p>12. Ito ang tawag sa sentro ng pamayanan sa Polynesia na kadalasang nasa gilid ng mga bundok. Ito ay tanghalan ng mga ritwal at pagpupulong kung saan nakapaligid dito ang tirahan ng mga pari at mga banal na estruktura.</p> <p>A. Tohua B. Tenochtitlan C. Chinampas D. Texcoco</p>				
<p>13. Bakit tinawag na Trans-Sahara ang kalakalan sa Hilagang Africa? Dahil _____?</p> <p>A. dito nagsimula ang sistema ng kalakalan sa buong mundo. B. dinarayo ito ng mga turista upang masilayan ang Sahara Desert. C. tinatawid ng mga nomadikong mangangalakal ang disyertong ito sakay ng caravan. D. maraming ginto ang makikita dito kaya marami ang nangahas na sakupin ito ng mga karatig-lugar.</p>				
<p>14. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang magandang katangian ng mga kabihasnang sa America ang dapat tularan ng kasalukuyang panahon?</p>				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>A. May sariling batas na sinusunod ang bawat mamamayan.</p> <p>B. Naging sarado ang kanilang mga pamayanan sa mga dayuhan.</p> <p>C. Nagtalaga sila ng mga matatalino at mayayamang pinuno sa bawat pamayanan.</p> <p>D. Nakapagtatag ng mahusay na pamayanan sa kabila ng hamon ng kapaligiran.</p>				
<p>15. Bakit mahalaga ang inhenyerang haydrolik sa kabihasnang Inca? Dahil ito ay _____?</p> <p>A. Nakakatulong ito sa pagdaloy ng tubig patungong disyertong bundok.</p> <p>B. Nagsisilbi itong tagapamagitan sa kalakalan ng iba't ibang produkto sa Africa.</p> <p>C. Nagsisilbing natural na proteksiyon ng kabihasan sa pagpasok ng mga dayuhan.</p> <p>D. Nakakatulong ito sa pagkakaroon ng maayos na transportasyon at komunikasyon.</p>				
<p>16. Alin sa mga Pulo sa Pacific ang artistiko pagdating sa mga maskara, pigura, at kagamitang panseremonya na gawa sa kahoy, talukab ng pagong at kabibe napininturahan ng itim, pula o puti.</p> <p>A. Polynesia</p> <p>B. Micronesia</p> <p>C. Melanesia</p> <p>D. Nazca</p>				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

MELC #4 - ***Nasusuri ang mga pagbabagong naganap sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon: Politika (Pyudalismo, Holy Roman Empire), Ekonomiya (Manoryalismo), Sosyo-kultural (Paglakas ng Simbahang Katoliko, Krusada).				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
17. Ano ang pinakamahalagang anyo ng kayamanan noong Panahon ng <i>Piyudalismo</i> ? A. Alahas B. Ginto C. Lupa D. Mineral				
18. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang HINDI totoo sa <i>Sistemang Piyudalismo</i> ? A. Piyudalismo ang sistemang politikal sa Panahong Medieval. B. Ang hari at panginoon ang tanging nagmamay-ari ng mga lupain. C. Kasunduan sa pagitan ng panginoon at basalyo. D. Ang mga alipin ay may karapatang mag may-ari ng lupa.				
19. Katapat ito ng pyudalismo. Ito ay sistemang pang-ekonomiya na gumagabay sa paraan ng pagsasaka sa buhay ng magbubukid at ugnayan sa lord ng manor. Ang mga magbubukid ay nagigigay serbisyo sa isang pyudal na hari o nagmamay-ari ng lupa kapalit ng kanilang proteksyon. A. Manoryalismo B. Imperyalismo C. Kolonyalismo D. Neo-kolonyalismo				
20. Tawag sa mga <i>nobles</i> o dugong bughaw na nakatanggap ng lupa ay mula sa hari. Bilang kapalit ng lupa, sila ay susumpa ng katapatan sa hari at magbibigay ng serbisyong militar. Sa panahon na				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>kailanganin ng hari ang tulong militar gaya ng panahon ng digmaan, inaasahang sila ay handang tumulong.</p> <p>A. Slave B. Peasant C. Clergy D. Vassal</p>				
<p>21. Bakit kinilala si <i>Charlemagne</i> bilang unang <i>Holy Roman Emperor at Protector of the Church</i>?</p> <p>A. Naging masunurin siya sa mga naisin ng Simbahan. B. Nakuha nya ang mga teritoryo ng Banal na Lupain. C. Napasuko niya ang mga Lombards na kalaban ng Simbahan at nawakasan ang pag-aalsa laban sa Santo Papa. D. Ipinalaganap ang Kristiyanismo hanggang Asya.</p>				

MELC # 5 - ***Natataya ang impuwensya ng mga kaisipang lumaganap sa Gitnang Panahon.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>22. Ito ay tumutukoy sa mayayamang mangangalakal na naging makapangyarihang uri sa Medieval France.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft Guild C. Merchant Guild D. Reformist</p>				
<p>23. Nang lumaki ang mga bayan, ang mga artisan ay nagtatag ng sariling guild. Halimbawa ay ang mga karpintero, sastre, panadero, at iba pang hanapbuhay na may sariling angking kakayanan.</p>				

<p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft Guild C. Merchant Guild D. Reformist</p>				
<p>24. Siya ay isang Fransiskanong monghe sa Oxford. Tinawag siyang "tagapanguna ng makabagong agham", dahil sa kanyang ambag sa kemistri at sipnayan (matimatika).</p> <p>A. Rodrigo Vivar B. Francis Bacon C. Geoffrey Chaucer ng England D. Dante Alighieri</p>				
<p>25. Ito ang nangangalaga sa mga suliraning namamagitan sa mga manggagawa at namumuhunan.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Reformist C. Knight D. Guild</p>				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix K: Validators' Instrument Checklist

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FOR SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMS) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS

Direction: Good day! Please take time to review and validate this instrument to ensure the validity and correctness of the content and examples. This will help the study to measure and determine if the indicators per parameter are appropriate and properly structured. Please respond to each item by putting a checkmark on the corresponding column. Thank you and God bless!

DIRECTION	DIRECTION: Please read the statements carefully and answer them honestly. Read each item below and kindly put a checkmark (✓) on the answer sheet that will be provided to you which will correspond to your answer. Use the scale below that applies to your responses.		
	Rate Scale:4 3 2 1	- - - -	Description I Strongly Agree I Agree I Disagree I Strongly Disagree
Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks

A. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO CONTENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to **content**?

Content pertains to the specific readings, research, or materials, the learners will study.

Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.	✓			
2. adds visual presentations and appeal to the lecture notes by means of <i>pictures, tables, diagrams, graphic organizers, and the like</i> .	✓			
3. uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.	✓			
4. presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .	✓			
5. <u>uses</u> <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson	✓			

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6. presents the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.	/			
7. explains words that are not familiar to the learners.	/			
8. uses enrichment activities with varying difficulties.	/			
9. gives various resources, materials, and worksheets the learners can utilize.	/			
10. sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.	/			

B. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PROCESS

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to process?

Process is how the lesson is designed for the learners.

Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. presents the lessons in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners.	/			
2. uses visual materials such as <i>flashcard, table, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.	/			
3. makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.	/			
4. gives various examples about the lesson.	/			
5. encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.	/			
6. designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well to the lesson.	/			
7. gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.	/			
8. provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners' unique talents and skills.	/			
9. allows the class to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.	/			
10. encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

C. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PRODUCT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to product?

Product includes the kinds of work products the learners will be asked to complete.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
	1. provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.	/			
	2. sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.	/			
	3. creates tasks based on a real-world experiences/applications.	/			
	4. allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.	/			
	5. shows a sample of an output and explains how it was made.	/			
gives	6. provides a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.				
	7. explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.	/			
	8. encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.	/			
	9. explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.	/			
equip	10. provides differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.	/			

D. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment?

Affect/environment refers to the rules, procedures, and routines to ensure that students are actively involved in learning.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
	1. ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and always ventilated.	/			
	2. makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.	/			
	3. promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environments for all learners.	/			
	4. sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest the lesson starts.	/			
	5. requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during and after the discussion of the lesson.	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

boosts / motivates

6. encourages all learners to participate in the discussion and accomplishment of various tasks.	/			
7. recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do-well in the class.	/			
8. allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.	/			
9. encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.	/			
10. gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs.	/			

Evaluated by:

Lyn L. Joaquin

Master Teacher I, Araling Panlipunan

Talaan ng Espesipikasyon sa Araling Panlipunan 8

IKALAWANG MARKAHAN

MGA KASANAYAN SA PAGKAKATUTO MELCs (Most Essential Learning Competencies)	BLG. NG AYTEM	ABILITY TO DIFFEREN- TIATE	ABILITY TO ORGANIZE	ABILITY TO ATTRIBUTE
***Nasusuri ang kabihasnang Minoan, Mycenaean at kabihasnang klasiko ng Greece.	6	1, 2, 3, 4		5, 6
***Naipapaliwanag ang kontribusyon ng kabihasnang Romano.	2			7, 8
***Nasusuri ang pag-usbong at pag-unlad ng mga klasikong kabihasnang sa: Africa – Songhai, Mali, atbp; America – Aztec, Maya, Olmec, Inca, atbp; Mga Pulo sa Pacific – Nazca, Polynesia, Micronesia, Melanesia.	8	9, 16	11, 12, 13	10, 14, 15
***Nasusuri ang mga pagbabagong naganap sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon: Politika (Pyudalismo, Holy Roman Empire), Ekonomiya (Manoryalismo), Sosyo-kultural (Paglakas ng Simbahang Katoliko, Krusada).	5		18, 19, 20	17, 21
***Natataya ang impuwensya ng mga kaisipang lumaganap sa Gitnang Panahon.	4	22, 23		24, 25
KABUUAN	30 25	8 10 —	6 10 —	11 10 —

Suggestions

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FOR PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMS) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS

Direction: Good day! Please take time to review and validate this instrument to ensure the validity and correctness of the content and the alignment of every item to the learning competency including the plausibility of distractors. This will help the researcher to measure and determine if the questions included are appropriate and properly structured. Please respond to each item by putting a checkmark on the corresponding column. Thank you and God bless!

Note: All the questions in this Pre-Test/Post Test are taken from the Alternative Delivery Mode of Department of Education SDO-Pasig Module in Araling Panlipunan 8 which are all based on the MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies) for the Second Grading Period. These standardized questions were validated by SDO Pasig.

INSTRUMENT 2: PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST

IKALAWANG MARKAHAN

ARALING PANLIPUNAN 8-KASAYSAYAN NG DAIGDIG

Pangalan: _____

Marka: _____

Baitang at Seksyon: _____

Petsa: _____

Panuto: Basahing mabuti ang mga sumusunod na pahayag. Piliin ang **TITIK** ng pinakaangkop na sagot mula sa mga pagpipilian at isulat sa inyong sagutang papel.

MELC #1 - **Nasusuri ang kabihasnang Minoan, Mycenaean at kabihasnang klasiko ng Greece.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>1. Ayon sa alamat ng sibilisasyong Minoan, siya ang anak ng diyos na si Zeus at Europa at hari ng naturang sibilisasyon.</p> <p>A. Agamemnon B. Minos C. Daedalus D. Theseus</p>	/			
<p>2. Mga larawang mabilisan subalit bihasang ipininta sa mga dinding na basa ng plaster upang kumapit nang husto sa pader ang mga pigment ng metal at mineral oxide.</p> <p>A. Mask B. Palayok C. Fresco D. Corbel</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>3. Isang English na arkeologong nakadiskubre sa kabihasnang Minoan nang mahukay ang Knossos noong 1899.</p> <p>A. Arthur Evans B. Michael Ventris C. Henrich Schleiman D. John Chadwick</p>	/			
<p>4. Ito ang politikal na ideolohiya na ipinankala ng Athens na siyang nangangahulugang <i>pamahalaan ng nakararami</i>.</p> <p>A. aristokrasya B. monarkiya C. oligarkiya D. demokrasya</p>	/			
<p>5. Ito ang maliit na yunit ng komunidad na bumubuo sa kabihasnang Greece. Ito ang nagsisilbing <i>lungsod-estado</i> sa Gresya na siyang sentro ng kalakalan at pamayanan.</p> <p>A. agora B. polis C. acropolis D. metropolis</p>	/			
<p>6. Pampublikong gusali na nagsilbing libingan ng mga emperador sa Roma. Itinayo ito bilang templo sa Roma noong 126 C.E. at nananatili pa rin ang istruktura hanggang ngayon.</p> <p>A. Colosseum B. Aqueduct C. Pantheon D. Appian Way</p>	/			

MELC #2 - ***Naipapaliwanag ang kontribusyon ng Kabihasnang Romano.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>7. Ito ang maliit na yunit ng komunidad na bumubuo sa kabihasnang Greece. Ito ang nagsisilbing <i>lungsod-estado</i> sa Gresya na siyang sentro ng kalakalan at pamayanan.</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>A. agora B. polis C. acropolis D. metropolis</p>				
<p>8. Pampublikong gusali na nagsilbing libingan ng mga emperador sa Roma. Itinayo ito bilang templo sa Roma noong 126 C.E. at nananatili pa rin ang istruktura hanggang ngayon. A. Colosseum B. Aqueduct C. Pantheon D. Appian Way</p>	/			

MELC #3 - ***Nasusuri ang pag-usbong at pag-unlad ng mga klasikong kabihasan sa: Africa – Songhai, Mali, atbp; America – Aztec, Maya, Olmec, Inca, atbp; Mga Pulo sa Pacific – Nazca, Polynesia, Micronesia, Melanesia.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>9. Saan bahagi ng Africa nakilala ang tatlong imperyo imperyo ng Ghana, Mali, at Songhai na siyang naging makapangyarihan dulot rin ng pakikipagkalakalan sa mga mamamayan sa labas ng Africa? A. Hilaga B. Timog C. Silangan D. Kanluran</p>	/			
<p>10. Sila ay tinaguriang mahuhusay na inhenyero at tagapagtayo ng mga estruktura sa Amerika tulad ng mga kanal o <i>aqueduct</i>, mga dam, gayundin ng sistema ng irigasyon, liwasan, at mga pamilihan. A. Inca B. Olmec C. Aztec D. Maya</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>11. Ang pinakamahalagang diyos ng araw ng mga Aztec dahil sila ay mga magsasaka na taimtim na umaasa sa mga puwersa ng kalikasan at sinasamba ang mga ito bilang mga diyos. Mahalaga ang sikat ng araw sa pananim ng mga magsasaka kaya sinusuyo at hinahandugan nila ang naturang diyos.</p> <p>A. Tlaloc B. Huitzilopochtli C. Quetzalcoatl D. Pachakuti</p>	/			
<p>12. Ito ang tawag sa sentro ng pamayanan sa Polynesia na kadalasang nasa gilid ng mga bundok. Ito ay tanghalan ng mga ritwal at pagpupulong kung saan nakapaligid dito ang tirahan ng mga pari at mga banal na estruktura.</p> <p>A. Tohua B. Tenochtitlan C. Chinampas D. Texcoco</p>	/			
<p>13. Bakit tinawag na Trans-Sahara ang kalakalan sa Hilagang Africa? Dahil _____?</p> <p>A. dito nagsimula ang sistema ng kalakalan sa buong mundo. B. dinarayo ito ng mga turista upang masilayan ang Sahara Desert. C. tinatawid ng mga nomadikong mangangalakal ang disyertong ito sakay ng caravan. D. maraming ginto ang makikita dito kaya marami ang nangahas na sakupin ito ng mga karatig-lugar.</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>14. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang magandang katangian ng mga kabihasnang sa America ang dapat tularan ng kasalukuyang panahon?</p> <p>A. May sariling batas na sinusunod ang bawat mamamayan.</p> <p>B. Naging sarado ang kanilang mga pamayanan sa mga dayuhan.</p> <p>C. Nagtalaga sila ng mga matatalino at mayayamang pinuno sa bawat pamayanan.</p> <p>D. Nakapagtatag ng mahusay na pamayanan sa kabila ng hamon ng kapaligiran.</p>	/			
<p>15. Bakit mahalaga ang inhenyerang haydrolik sa kabihasnang Inca? Dahil ito ay _____?</p> <p>A. Nakakatulong ito sa pagdaloy ng tubig patungong disyertong bundok.</p> <p>B. Nagsisilbi itong tagapamagitan sa kalakalan ng iba't ibang produkto sa Africa.</p> <p>C. Nagsisilbing natural na proteksiyon ng kabihasnang sa pagpasok ng mga dayuhan.</p> <p>D. Nakakatulong ito sa pagkakaroon ng maayos na transportasyon at komunikasyon.</p>	/			
<p>16. Alin sa mga Pulo sa Pacific ang artistiko pagdating sa mga maskara, pigura, at kagamitang panseremonya na gawa sa kahoy, talukab ng pagong at kabibe napininturahan ng itim, pula o puti.</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

A. Polynesia B. Micronesia C. Melanesia D. Nazca				
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MELC #4 - ***Nasusuri ang mga pagbabagong naganap sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon: Politika (Pyudalismo, Holy Roman Empire), Ekonomiya (Manoryalismo), Sosyo-kultural (Paglakas ng Simbahang Katoliko, Krusada).				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
17. Ano ang pinakamahalagang anyo ng kayamanan noong Panahon ng <i>Piyudalismo</i> ? A. Alahas B. Ginto C. Lupa D. Mineral	/			
18. Alin sa mga sumusunod ang HINDI totoo sa <i>Sistemang Piyudalismo</i> ? A. Piyudalismo ang sistemang politikal sa Panahong Medieval. B. Ang hari at panginoon ang tanging nagmamay-ari ng mga lupain. C. Kasunduan sa pagitan ng panginoon at basalyo. D. Ang mga alipin ay may karapatang mag may-ari ng lupa.	/			
19. Katapat ito ng pyudalismo. Ito ay sistemang pang-ekonomiya na gumagabay sa paraan ng pagsasaka sa buhay ng magbubukid at ugnayan sa lord ng manor. Ang mga magbubukid ay nagigigay serbisyo sa isang pyudal na hari o nagmamay-ari ng lupa kapalit ng kanilang proteksyon. A. Manoryalismo B. Imperyalismo C. Kolonyalismo D. Neo-kolonyalismo	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>20. Tawag sa mga <i>nobles</i> o dugong bughaw na nakatanggap ng lupa ay mula sa hari. Bilang kapalit ng lupa, sila ay susumpa ng katapatan sa hari at magbibigay ng serbisyong militar. Sa panahon na kailanganin ng hari ang tulong militar gaya ng panahon ng digmaan, inaasahang sila ay handang tumulong.</p> <p>A. Slave B. Peasant C. Clergy D. Vassal</p>	/			
<p>21. Bakit kinilala si <i>Charlemagne</i> bilang unang <i>Holy Roman Emperor at Protector of the Church</i>?</p> <p>A. Naging masunurin siya sa mga naisin ng Simbahan. B. Nakuha nya ang mga teritoryo ng Banal na Lupain. C. Napasuko niya ang mga Lombards na kalaban ng Simbahan at nawakasan ang pag-aalsa laban sa Santo Papa. D. Ipinalaganap ang Kristiyanismo hanggang Asya.</p>	/			

MELC # 5 - ***Natataya ang impuwensya ng mga kaisipang lumaganap sa Gitnang Panahon.				
Test Question	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<p>22. Ito ay tumutukoy sa mayayamang mangangalakal na naging makapangyarihang uri sa Medieval France.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft Guild C. Merchant Guild D. Reformist</p>	/			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>23. Nang lumaki ang mga bayan, ang mga artisan ay nagtatag ng sariling guild. Halimbawa ay ang mga karpintero, sastre, panadero, at iba pang hanapbuhay na may sariling angking kakayanan.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft Guild C. Merchant Guild D. Reformist</p>	/			
<p>24. Siya ay isang Pransiskanong monghe sa Oxford. Tinawag siyang "tagapanguna ng makabagong agham", dahil sa kanyang ambag sa kemistri at sipnayan (matimatika).</p> <p>A. Rodrigo Vivar B. Francis Bacon C. Geoffrey Chaucer ng England D. Dante Alighieri</p>	/			
<p>25. Ito ang nangangalaga sa mga suliraning namamagitan sa mga manggagawa at namumuhunan.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Reformist C. Knight D. Guild</p>	/			

Evaluated by:

Lyn L. Joaquin

Master Teacher I, Araling Panlipunan

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>23. Nang lumaki ang mga bayan, ang mga artisan ay nagtatag ng sariling guild. Halimbawa ay ang mga karpintero, sastre, panadero, at iba pang hanapbuhay na may sariling angking kakayanan.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Craft Guild C. Merchant Guild D. Reformist</p>	/			
<p>24. Siya ay isang Pransiskanong monghe sa Oxford. Tinawag siyang "tagapanguna ng makabagong agham", dahil sa kanyang ambag sa kemistri at sipnayan (matimatika).</p> <p>A. Rodrigo Vivar B. Francis Bacon C. Geffrey Chaucer ng England D. Dante Alighieri</p>	/			
<p>25. Ito ang nangangalaga sa mga suliraning namamagitan sa mga manggagawa at namumuhunan.</p> <p>A. Bourgeoisie o Burgis B. Reformist C. Knight D. Guild</p>	/			

Evaluated by:

mbalanasan

Marife B. Calanasan

Master Teacher I, Araling Panlipunan

INSTRUMENT VALIDATION FOR SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMS) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN-PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE 8 LEARNERS

Direction: Good day! Please take time to review and validate this instrument to ensure the validity and correctness of the content and examples. This will help the study to measure and determine if the indicators per parameter are appropriate and properly structured. Please respond to each item by putting a checkmark on the corresponding column. Thank you and God bless!

DIRECTION	DIRECTION: Please read the statements carefully and answer them honestly. Read each item below and kindly put a checkmark (✓) on the answer sheet that will be provided to you which will correspond to your answer. Use the scale below that applies to your responses.		
	Rate Scale:4 3 2 1	- - - -	Description I Strongly Agree I Agree I Disagree I Strongly Disagree
Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks

A. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO CONTENT

*How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to **content**?*

***Content** pertains to the specific readings, research, or materials, the learners will study.*

Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.	✓			
2. adds visual presentations to add appeal to the lecture notes by means of <i>pictures, tables, diagrams, graphic organizers, and the like</i> .	✓			
3. uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.	✓			
4. presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .	✓			
5. uses <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson	✓			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

6. presents the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.	✓			
7. explains words that are not familiar to the learners.	✓			
8. uses enrichment activities with varying difficulties.	✓			
9. gives various resources, materials, and worksheets the learners can utilize.	✓			
10. sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.	✓			

B. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PROCESS

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to process?

Process is how the lesson is designed for the learners.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	presents the lessons in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners.	✓			
2.	uses visual materials such as <i>tarpapel, table, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.	✓			
3.	makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.	✓			
4.	gives various examples about the lesson.	✓			
5.	encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.	✓			
6.	designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well to the lesson.	✓			
7.	gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.	✓			
8.	provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners' unique talents and skills.	✓			
9.	allows the class to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.	✓			
10.	encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.	✓			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

C. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PRODUCT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to product?

Product includes the kinds of work products the learners will be asked to complete.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.	✓			
2.	sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.	✓			
3.	creates tasks based on a real-world experiences/applications.	✓			
4.	allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.	✓			
5.	shows a sample of an output and explains how it was made.	✓			
6.	provides a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.	✓			
7.	explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.	✓			
8.	encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.	✓			
9.	explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.	✓			
10.	provides differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.	✓			

D. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment?

Affect/environment refers to the rules, procedures, and routines to ensure that students are actively involved in learning.

<i>The teacher...</i>	Statement	Retain (Acceptable)	Revise (Requires improvement)	Reject (Unacceptable/ Eliminate)	Remarks
1.	ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and always ventilated.	✓			
2.	makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.	✓			
3.	promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environments for all learners.	✓			
4.	sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest the lesson starts.	✓			
5.	requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during and after the discussion of the lesson.	✓			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

6. encourages all learners to participate in the discussion and accomplishment of various tasks.	✓			
7. recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do-well in the class.	✓			
8. allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.	✓			
9. encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.	✓			
10. gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs.	✓			

Evaluated by:

Aleli C. Juliano
Master Teacher I, English Department

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Mu'amana,

My congratulations to you!

Your study "The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials in Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners" allows our learners greater engagement, social and academic inclusivity. This also encourages teachers to understand each student's unique gifts and challenges that connect different learning styles.

Thank you very much for sharing your knowledge and expertise as an educator. God bless you more Mu'amana.

Etan,
Perli

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

INSTRUCTION: Please read the statements carefully and answer them honestly. Read each item below and kindly put a checkmark (✓) on the item corresponding to your answer. Use the scale below that applies to your response.

Rate	-	Verbal Interpretation
Scale: 4	-	I Strongly Agree
3	-	I Agree
2	-	I Disagree
1	-	I Strongly Disagree

A. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO CONTENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to **content**?

Content pertains to the specific readings, research, or materials, the learners will study.

Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. provides lecture notes (<i>hard and soft copy</i>) as reading materials for the class to use.				
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3. uses simple and common words in crafting the lecture notes.				
4. presents the teaching-learning materials in differentiated forms: <i>lecture notes, tarpapel, video and PowerPoint presentations</i> .				
5. uses <i>maps, pictures, diagrams, timeline, word bank and graphic organizers</i> in presenting the lesson.				
6. presents the teaching-learning materials in such a manner that they can be easily understood by the class.				
7. explains words that are not familiar to the learners.				
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10. sets the <i>time-frame</i> in which a specific task or activity must be accomplished.				

B. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PROCESS

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to process?

Process is how the lesson is designed for the learners.

The teacher...	Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
	1. presents the lessons in such a way that it can be easily understood by all learners. <i>yes</i>	<i>or present each lesson in such a way that it can be</i>			
	2. uses visual materials such as tarpapel, table, diagram, graphic organizer, video and PowerPoint presentations to make the lesson more interesting and appealing to the class.				
	3. makes sure that the visual materials presented are simple and easy to understand.				
	4. gives various examples about the lesson.				
	5. encourages the learners to actively participate in the class discussion.				
	6. designs activities to assist learners who are struggling and not coping-well to the lesson. <i>Disagree</i>				
	7. gives tasks/activities that are challenging yet engaging to all learners.				
	8. provides differentiated activities/tasks to enhance the learners' unique talents and skills.				
	9. allows the class to create their own group where members can actively collaborate.				
	10. encourages the learners to write their reflections and share their takeaways or significant learnings about the lesson.				

C. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO PRODUCT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to product?

Product includes the kinds of work products the learners will be asked to complete.

The teacher...	Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
	1. provides the list of all possible outputs that can be made by the learners.				
	2. sets various options on how the learners can make their outputs.				
	3. creates tasks based on a real-world experiences/applications.				
	4. allows the learners to work alone or in a group collaboratively in making their outputs.				
	5. shows a sample of an output and explains how it was made. <i>Disagree</i>				
	6. provides a clear direction on how the output can be accomplished.				

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

7. explains the significance or value of accomplishing the task/output.				
8. encourages learners to design or decorate their own output or portfolio.				
9. explains the rubrics as basis for grading the outputs of the learners.				
10. provides differentiated tasks which are challenging yet can be finished within the given timeframe.				

D. PERCEPTION OF DIFFERENTIATION AS TO AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT

How do you perceive the teacher's utilization of differentiated instructional materials as to affect/environment?

Affect/environment refers to the rules, procedures, and routines to ensure that students are actively involved in learning.

Statement	I Strongly Agree	I Agree	I Disagree	I Strongly Disagree
<i>The teacher...</i> 1. ensures that the classroom is well-lighted and always ventilated. <i>well-ventilated</i>				
2. makes sure that the classroom is clean before the discussion starts.				
3. promotes friendly and non-threatening learning environments for all learners.				
4. sees to it that the learners pay full-attention and interest the lesson starts.				
5. requires the learners to observe proper decorum before, during and after the discussion of the lesson.				
6. encourages all learners to participate in the discussion and accomplishment of various tasks.				
7. recognizes the learners who actively participate and praises those who do well in the class.				
8. allows the learners to choose their own groupmates based on their unique skills and talents.				
9. encourages the learners to work collaboratively to finish the task on a specified timeframe.				
10. gives ample time to exchange ideas in planning, preparing, and presenting their group's performance tasks/outputs.				

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix L: *Similarity Report Certificate*

This is to certify that the study entitled **THE USE OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (DIMs) IN TEACHING WORLD HISTORY IN IN- PERSON CLASSES OF GRADE-8 LEARNERS** by **RAYCO, JENNIFER A.** has a similarity index of **15%** based on the Turnitin Originality Report (quoted material and bibliography excluded).

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***Differentiated
Instructional
Materials
(DIMs)
in World History
-AP 8-***

ARALIN 1: ANG SINAUNANG KABIHASNAN NG GRESYA

PAKSA I: Ang mga Minoan at Mycenaean

MELC: Nasusuri ang Kabihasnang Minoan at Mycenaean

LAYUNIN: Sa katapusan ng aralin, ang mga mag aaral ay inaasahang:

1. Nakakapahayag ng maliwanag sa naging simula at katapusan ng kabihasnang Minoan at Mycenaean;
2. Nakakagawa ng malikhaing garwain ng mga pamanana ng Minoan at Mycenaean; at
3. Napapahalagahan ang naging ambag ng dalawang kabihasnang sa kasaysayan at sa mundo.

Ang Klasikal na Gresya

Ang Gresya ang tinuturing na "Sinilangan ng Kanluraning Sibilisasyon" dahil sa kakaibang kulturang nalinang sa naging batayan ng mga taga-Kanluranin. Sa gitna ng masalimuot na kasaysayan dulot ng pananakop ng mga dayuhan, napanatili ng lugar ang kanilang tradisyon. Nananatili hanggang sa kasalukuyang panahon ang impluwensya ng Greece sa larangan ng politika at sining.

Fig 1 & 2. Mapa ng Gresya

Heograpiya

- Ang Gresya ay isang peninsula
- Bulubundukin ang buong lupain
- Napapaligiran ng mga dagat. Sa kanluran ng bansa ay ang Dagat Ionian, sa timog ay Dagat Mediterranean, at sa silangan ay ang Dagat Aegean.
- Ang kapatagan ay matatagpuan sa Thessaly (sa Atica), Boconia (sa gitnang Gresya), at Messenra (sa Peloponnesus) na nasa timog tangway ng bansa.

Pamunuhay

- Marami sa mga Griyego ay mga magsasaka, mangingisda, marino at mangangalakal.
- Ang katamtamang klima ay mainam taniman ng wheat, barley, olives, at ubas.
- Ang bulubundukin ang heograpiya ng Gresya ay nagdulot ng pagkakahati ng mga lungsod at pamayanan. Dito umusbong ang mga polis or city-state.

Ang Kabihasnang sa Crete

➤ Ang Kabihasnang Minoan

- Sumibol ang unang kabihasnang ng Gresya sa pinakamalaking pulo, ang Crete

- Ang kabihasnang Minoan ay hango sa pangalan ni Haring Minos na pinaniniwalaang nagtatag ng kahirapan sa Crete.
- Nasa estratehikong lokasyon ang isla ng Crete na naging dahilan kung bakit masigla ang naging kalakalan sa lugar na ito.
- Sila ay nakikipagkalakal sa Cyprus, Ehipto, Anatolia, Asia Minor, at Mesopotamia.
- Bukod sa pangangalakal, ang pagtatanim at pag aalaga ng hayop ay kanila ding hanapbuhay.
- Ang mga Minoan ay mahusay na arkitekto, nakapagpagawa ng mga palasyo gaya ng Knossos Palace.
- Ang mga Minoan ay may kahusayan din sa paghahabi, paggawa ng alahas, paggawa ng palayok, mga kagamitang yari sa tanso, paggawa ng mga sandata na yari sa tanso at bronse, at paggawa ng sining.
- Tinatayang noong 2500 BCE, ang mga Minoan ay may nasusukat ng alpabeto.
- Pagkaraan ng ilang taon, sumalakay mula sa Peloponnesus ang Mycenaean at nawasak ang kabihasnang Minoan.

Fig 3 & 4. Knossos Palace

✦ Ang Kabihasnang Mycenaean

- Ang mga sumalakay na Mycenaean ay galing sa kapatagan ng Eurasia at naninirahan sa Peloponnesus
- Tinatawag silang Mycenaean na hango sa pangalan ng kanilang lungsod, ang Mycenae.
- Binubuo ng ibat ibang lungsod estado ang organisasyong politikal ng Mycenae pinamumunuan ng isang mandirigmang hari na nakatira sa citadel.
- Si Haring Agamemnon ang pinuno ng lungsod at siyang itinuturing pinakamayaman at pinakamakapangyarihan sa hari sa sinaunang Gresya.
- Batay sa mga labing nahukay, ang mga Mycenaean ay nagsusuot ng mga alahas, gumagamit ng sandatang tanso, at iba pang kasangkapang yari sa ginto, pilak, at tanso.
- Naging kabuhayan ng mga Mycenaean ang pagtatanim, pagpapastol ng hayop, at pakikipagkalakal.
- Ang mga Mycenaean Kilala din sa paggawa ng mga alahas, pagpapanday, paghahabi ng tela, paglikha ng palayok, at paggawa ng frescoes.
- Bumagsak ang kabihasnang Mycenaean ng magkaroon ng digmaan sa pagitan ng mga Dorian na nanirahan sa Peloponnesus.
- Ang pagbagsak ng kabihasnang Mycenaean ay humantong ang tinatawag na Dark Ages na nagsimula noong 1100 at tumagal ng hanggang 800 BCE.

Fig 5. Frescoes

PAKSA 2 Kabihasnang Klasikal ng Gresya

MELC: Nasusuri ang Kabihasnang Klasiko ng Greece

LAYUNIN: Sa katapusan ng aralin, ang mga mag aaral ay inaasahang:

1. Nakakapagsuri ng mabuti sa mga importanteng pangyayari sa kabihasnang klasiko ng Greece;
2. Nakakagawa ng malikhaing gawain ng dakilang pamana ng Greece; at
3. Napapahalagahan ang mga ambag ng klasikong kabihasnang ng Greece sa kasaysayan at ng kasalukuyang panahon.

Ang Polis

- Pagsapit ng 800 BCE, isang yunit pampolitikal ang nabuo sa Gresya na tinatawag na lungsod-estado o polis.
- Ang polis ay binubuo ng tatlong bahagi: Una ay ang acropolis. Makikita rito ang templo at pampublikong gusali. Karaniwang itong matatagpuan sa mataas na lugar gaya ng burol or gilid ng bundok na napapalibutan ng pader. Pangalawa, ang agora o pamilihan na matatagpuan sa ibaba ng acropolis. Ang ikatlo ay ang polis na binubuo ng mga nakapaligid na kanayunan.
- Ang sukat ng isang polis ay nasa 500 hanggang 500 milya kuwadrado at tinitirhan ng mahigpit na 20,000 mamayan.
- Ang uri ng gobyerno sa bawat polis ay ibat iba. May nasa ilalim ng monarkiya, ang iba ay aristokrasya, tiraniya o demokrasya.

Fig. 6 Mapa ng Polis

Ang Athens

- Sa baybayin ng kapatagan ng Attica, sa may timog-silangang bahagi ng Gresya umusbong ang Athens.
- Nakilala ang Athens sa pagtatag ng pamahalaang demokrasya. Hinubog ito ng mga unang lider ng Athens na sina Draco, Solon, Pisistratus, at Cleisthenes.

Mga Dakilang Lider ng Athens	Mga Nagawa
1. Draco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Isang archon (opisyal ng pamahalaan) • Ginawa ang Draconian Code, isang batas na hinahatulan ng kamatayan ang mga magkakasala. • Ipinaglaban ang mga karapatan ng mga magsasaka sa tamang paghahati ng lupa
2. Solon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inayos ang kalagayan ng mga magsasaka

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Itinatag niya ang Konseho ng Apat na Raan (Council of the Four Hundreds), isang konseho na binubuo ng mga piling mayamang may-ari ng lupa
3. Pisistratus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kinuha ang mga lupa ng mga mayayaman at ibinihagi sa mga magsasakang walang lupa. • Pinaganda niya ang Athens sa pamimigatan ng pagtatayo ng mga templo
4. Cleisthenes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inayos ni Cleisthenes ang demokrasyang pamahalaan sa Greece • Itinatag niya ang asemblea na isang sangay ng pamahalaan na humahalal sa opisyal ng pamahalaan. • Ang Konseho ng Matanda ay binubuo ng dalawang hari at walong miyembro na pawang nasa edad animnapu na nagpapanukala ng batas sa Asemblea ng Mamayan. • Pinalawak ni Cleisthenes ang Konseho at ginawang Konseho ng Limandaan • Ang Asemblea ng Mamayan ay may kapangyarihan sa pamahalaan at ang Konseho ay ang nagpapanukala ng batas sa asemblea.

Ang Sparta

- Ang lungsod estado ng Sparta ay matatagpuan sa katimugang bahagi ng Peloponnesus.
- Hinati sa tatlong lipunan ang Sparta, ang una ay ang Spartiate. Mga nagmamay-ari ng lupa at opisyal ng pamahalaan. Ang Perioeci, ay hindi mamayan ng Sparta ngunit sila ay malayang tao. Ang mga Helot, ay mga katutubong sinakop ng mga Spartan. Sila ang nasa pinakamababang antas ng lipunan.
- Ang pamahalaan ay binubuo ng Asemblea at Konseho ng Matanda. Ang ephors o opisyal ay ang nagpapatupad ng batas at may kontrol sa edukasyon at paglilitis ng mga kaso.
- Layunin ng Spartan na magkaroon ng mahusay na militar. Sa eded na pitong taon ay nagsasanay na ang isang batang lalaki para maging isang mahusay na mandirigmang Spartan. Bumabalik lang sila sa tahanan sa edad na dalawampung isa.
- Bukod sa pagiging may bahay ng isang asawang babae, nagsasanay din sila palakasan, pagtakbo, at pagbuno.

Mga Tagumpay at Kabiguan sa Kabihasnang Gresya

✦ Ang Digmaang Persia

- Noong 546 BCE, sinakop ni Haring Cyrus, ang dakilang lider ng mga Persiano ang Asia Minor at iba pang lungsod-estado ng Gresya.
- Noong umupo sa trono si Haring Darius noong 521 BCE, sinumulan niyang sakupin ang iba pang lungsod-estado gaya ng Ionia. Nagpadala ng tulong ang Athens sa Ionia para pakikipagdigma sa mga Persiano pero natalo ang pwersang Griyego
- Ito ay nakatala sa "History of Persian Wars" ni Herodotus na siyang Ama ng Kasaysayan.

✦ Digmaang Marathon

- Noong 491 BCE, nagpadala ng embahador si Haring Darius sa mga lungsod-estado sa Gresya na mapasailalim ng imperyong Persia. May lungsod-estado na tumalima pero may mga hindi sumunod gaya ng Athens at Sparta.

- Sa kapatagan ng Marathon naglaban ang pwersa ng Athens at Persia. Matagumpay na nanalo ang Athens sa pamumuno ni Miltiades.
- Gumamit sila ng estilong phalanx.

✦ Digmaang Thermopylae

- Pagkaraan ng sampung taon matapos ang Digmaang Marathon, sa pamumuno ni Haring Xerxes tinawid ng hukbong Persia ang Hellespoint or Dardanelles sa kasalukuyang panahon upang sakupin ang Athens.
- Hinarangan sila ng 300 kawal ng Sparta sa pamumuno ni Haring Leonidas sa masikip na kipot.
- Natalo ang mga Spartans dahil sa isang taksil na nagbunyag ng lihim na daan.

✦ Digmaang Salamis

- Nagsanib pwersa ang Athens at Sparta upang kalabanin ang Persia. Sa huli ang mga Athenians ang nagpapanalo sa laban.
- Dahil sa pangambang sakupin muli ng Persia. Bumuo ng isang alyansa ang 140 na polis at tinawag itong Liga ng Delian sa pamumuno ng Athens. Hindi kasama sa alyansa ang Sparta.

✦ Digmaang Peloponnesian

- Dahil sa pagsikat ng Athens, pinakialaman nito ang mga interes ng Sparta na nagdulot ng digmaan sa pagitan ng dalawa.
- Nagdeklara ng digmaan ang Sparta laban sa Athens noong 431 BCE, na siyang ikinatalo ng Athens.

Kulturang Griyego

✦ Sining at Arkitektura

Fig 8. Parthenon

Fig 9. Types of Columns

🌟 Agham at Pilosopiya

1. Thales	-sinuri niya ang likas na sanhi ng lindol at ayon sa kanya, ang daigdig ay nakalutang sa tubig at minsan ay naaalog ng malaking alon.
2. Pythagoras	- isang pilosopo at mathematician -lumikha ng Pythagorean theorem
3. Democritus	-sa kanya nagsimula ang atomic theory -na ang buong kalikasan ay binubuo ng atomic particle
4. Hippocrates	- "Ama ng Medisina" -gumamit ng siyensya sa pagtuklas ng pinagmumulan ng sakit
5. Sophist	- ay isang guro sa sinaunang Greece noong ikalima at ikaapat na siglo BC. -itinuro nila ang arete - "kabutihan" o "kahusayan" - pangunahin sa mga batang estadista at maharlika.
6. Socrates	-nagtatag ng "Socratic Method" -nakilala siya sa katagang na "Know Thyself"
7. Plato	-ang may akda ng "The Republic"
8. Aristotle	-nagsulat ng librong "Rhetoric" -nagsulat ng librong "Politics"

🌟 Pananampalataya

Diyos at Diyosa ng Mitolohiyang Griyego

1. Zeus - diyos ng langit, kidlat, kulog, batas, kaayusan at hustisya.	7. Artemis - Diyosa ng pangangaso, ilang, birhen, Buwan, archery, panganganak, proteksyon at salot
2. Hera - Reyna ng mga diyos at diyosa ng kasal, kababaihan, panganganak at pamilya.	8. Ares - Diyos ng digmaan, karahasan, pagdanak ng dugo at mga kabutihang panlalaki.
3. Poseidon - Diyos ng mga dagat, tubig, bagyo, bagyo, lindol at kabayo.	9. Aphrodite - Diyosa ng pag-ibig, kasiyahan, pagsinta, pag-aanak, pagkamayabong, kagandahan at pagnanasa.
4. Demeter - Diyosa ng ani, pagkamayabong, agrikultura, kalikasan at mga panahon. Pinamunuan niya ang mga butil at ang pagkamayabong ng lupa	10. Hephaestus - Dalubhasang panday at manggagawa ng mga diyos; diyos ng forge, craftsmanship, imbensyon, apoy at bulkan.
5. Athena - Diyosa ng karunungan, gawaing kamay, at pakikidigma	11. Hermes - Mensahero ng mga diyos; diyos ng paglalakbay, komersyo, komunikasyon, hangganan, mahusay na pagsasalita, diplomasya, magnanakaw, at mga laro. Siya rin ang naging gabay ng mga patay na kaluluwa.
6. Apollo - Diyos ng liwanag, Araw, propesiya, pilosopiya, archery, katotohanan, inspirasyon, tula, musika, sining, kagandahan ng lalaki, gamot, pagpapagaling, at salot	12. Hades - kapatid ni Zeus, diyos ng impyerno at ng mga patay

Panahong Hellenistiko

Philip of Macedonia

- o Noong 359 BCE, naging hari siya ng Macedonia.
- o Sinumulan niyang palakasin at sanayin ang kanyang hukbo
- o Sinakop niya ang buong Gresya
- o Pataksil na pinatay noong 336 BCE

Alexander the Great

- o Anak ni Philip
- o Isa syang mahusay na lider kagaya ng kanyang ama
- o Naging guro niya si Aristotle at madalas magsanay sa gymnastics
- o Nilusob ang Asya Minor at nilupig ang mga Persiano. Sinunod niyang sinakop ang Syria, Egypt, Babylonia, at ang buong Imperyo ng Persia.
- o Sa pagitan ng 334 BCE hanggang 323 BCE, naitatag niya ang pinakamalaking imperyo na umabot hanggang silangan ng Ilog Indus.
- o Namatay siya noong 332 BCE at pinghatian ng kanyang tatlong heneral ang buong imperyo. Si Ptolemy ay pinamunuan ang Egypt, si Antigonos ay namuno sa Macedonia, at si Seleucus ay namuno sa Asya.

Fig 14. Empire of Alexander the Great

Kabihasnang Hellenistiko

- o Sa pamumuno ni Alexander the Great, lumaganap ang kulturang Griyego mula sa Egypt hanggang Asya.
- o Yumabong ang panahong Hellenistiko sa pagitan noong 133 BCE hanggang 30 BCE.
- o Nakilala ang Alexandria bilang isang tanyag na port-city at dahil sa Library of Alexandria.
- o Lumutang ang pilosopiyang Stoicismo na itinatag ni Zeno na tumatalakay sa pagtanggap kung anong meron tayo, paggamit ng katuwiran, at pag ayon sa batas ng kalikasan. Umusbong din ang pilosopiyang Epicureanismo ni Epicurus na itinuturo ang pagpapakasaya sa buhay sapagkat hindi natin alam ang ating kinabukasan.

Sanggunian:

Soriano, et.al. (2015). *Kayamanan: Kasaysayan ng Daigdig*. Rex Book Store. pp 92-107

ARALIN 2: ANG SINAUNANG ROMA

PAKSA 1: Ang Pagkakabuo ng Roma

MELC: Naipapaliwanag ang mahahalagang pangyayari sa kabihasnang klasiko ng Rome

Heograpiya

- Ang Italya ang isang tangway na nahahangganan mula sa timog na bahagi ng Europa patungo sa Dagat Mediterranean.
- May hugis itong bota na hinango ang pangalang Italya na mula sa salitang "italus."
- Maburool at bulubundukin ang Italya. Sa halaga nito ay ang Bundok ng Alps naghihiwalay sa bansa sa iba pang bansa sa Europa.

Fig 1 & 2. Map of Italy

Unang Pamayanan sa Roma

- Unang nanirahan sa matabang kapatagan ng Latium sa timog Tiber ang mga Indo-European noong 2000 BCE. Dala nila ang kanilang mga sandatang gawa sa bronse at wikang Latin.
- May ilang pangkat ng mga tao na naninirahan sa halaga at timog ng Roma. Sila ang mga Etruscan.
- Ang mga Etruscan na mula sa Etruria ay sinakop ang Roma at ang karatig pook. Pinamunuan ng mga Etruscan ang Roma sa loob ng mahigpit isang daan taon.

Fig 3. Etruscan People

Roma sa Ilalim ng Republika

- Ang republika ay isang gobyerno na kung saan ang mga mamayan ay may karapatang Bumuo at maghalal ng mga opisyal.
- Noong 509 BCE, itinaboy ng mga Romano ang kanilang haring Etruscan at kanilang tinatag ang isang republika o isang pamahalaan na walang hari.
- Mga patrician o may mga may ari ng lupa ang naging pinuno ng republika. May dalawang konsul na nangangasiwa sa pang araw araw na gawain ng pamahalaan at kasundaluhan.
- Mayroon Senado na binubuo ng 300 na tao na mula sa patrician. Sila ay may kapangyarihan tungkol sa ugnayan panlabas ng republika at mag desisyon sa mga importanteng isyu.
- Ang asembleya ay binubuo ng mga plebeian o ordinaryong mamayan ng Roma.
- Noong 494 BCE, nagsimulang humingi ng karapatan ang mga plebeian. Nagbanta silang gagawa ng bagong lungsod at hindi magbabayad ng buwis. Dahil dito, ang asemblea ay pinayagang maggawa ng batas at maghalal ng tribune na mangangalaga sa karapatan ng mga plebeian.
- Isinulat ng mga plebeian ang kanilang batas noong 451 BCE sa isang lapidang tanso na tinatawag na Law of the Twelve Tables o Lex Duodecim Tabularum.
- Umunlad ang estado ng mga plebeian at nagkaroon sila ng pagkakataon maging miyembro ng senado at maging konsul.

- Unti unting nasakop ng Roma ang kabuuan ng Italya sa timog ng ilog Rubicon.
- Lalong lumawak ang teritoryo ng Roma at naging isang makapangyarihan na bansa.

Ang Labanan ng Roma at Carthage (Digmaang Punic)

- Sa paglawak ng teritoryo ng mga Romano ay nakipagtunggalian sila sa isang estado sa ibayo ng Mediterranean, ang Carthage.
- Ang Carthage ay isang lungsod-estado sa Hilagang Aprika na itinatag ng mga Phoenician.
- Ang Carthage ay walang kolonya sa peninsula ng Italya ngunit may mga panirahan ito sa mga karatig na Sicily, Sardinia, at Corsica.
- Magaling na manlalayag at mangangalakal ang mga taga-Carthage na may taglay maraming barko at mahusay na hukbong pandagat.
- Nang masakop ng Roma ang Timog ng Italya, nagkaroon ng takot ang mga taga-Carthage na maagaw ng Roma ang kanilang pamilihan sa Sicily. Nagkaroon din ng pangamba ang mga taga-Roma na isara ng Carthage ang daanan sa Dagat Adriatiko at Kipot ng Messina.
- Ang mga pangambang ito ay nagdulot ng digmaan o ang Punic Wars. Ang punic ay nanggaling sa salitang Latin na punicus o Phoenician.

Fig 4. Carthage Empire Map

Unang Digmaang Punic

- Naganap sa dagat ang unang digmaang Punic. Sa kawalan na maayos na barko ang Roma ay nahirapan silang makipagdigma sa Carthage.
- Nang may masirang isang barko ang Carthage, agad itong kinuha ng Roma at ginawang modelo sa paggawa ng sarili nilang barko.
- Nanalo ang Roma sa labanan at nasakop nila ang Sardinia at Corsica noong 238 BCE.

Fig 5. Carthage Warship

✦ Ikalawang Digmaang Punic

- Ang Ikalawang digmaan ay naganap sa lupa na tangkain ng dakilang heneral ng Carthage na si Hannibal na tawirin ang bundok ng Alps at salakayin ang Roma.
- Nahirapan si Hannibal kasama ang kanyang hukbo na nakasakay sa mga elepante na tawarin ang mga makakapal na yelo.
- Nakarating sa Lambak Po ang hukbo ni Hannibal at namalagi ng labinlimang taon.
- Pinagwagian niya ang bawat labanan ngunit hindi nasakop ang Roma dahil kulang sa tauuhan.
- Sinalakay ng heneral na si Scipio ng Roma ang mga Carthaginian sa Espana upang hindi makatulong kay Hannibal sa Italya.
- Napilitang umuwi si Hannibal sa Carthage noong 240 BCE upang ipagtanggol ang lungsod-estado sa pagsalakay ng Roma.
- Noong 220 BCE, natalo ni Scipio si Hannibal sa Zama sa Numudia o Algeria ngayong panahon

Fig 6. Hannibal

✦ Ikatlong Digmaang Punic

- Pinag alab ni Cato na isang tagapagsalita sa Senado ang salitang *Delanda est Carthago* o wasakin ang Carthage.
- Noong 149 BCE, lubusang nawasak ang Carthage at napasakamay ng Roma.

Epekto ng Digmaan

- Sa pagtatapos ng digmaan, nagputuloy sa pananakop ang Roma at napasakamay ang ilang bahagi ng Macedonia, Gresya, at Anatolia.
- Naging isang makapangyarihan na imperyo ang Roma.

Ang Pag-angat ni Julius Caesar

Fig 7. Julius Caesar

- Noong 60 BCE, may tatlong ambisasyong heneral na kinilalang pinuno ng Roma sa pagkamatay ni Sulla. Sila ay sina Crassus, Pompey, at Caesar.
- Nagsanib pwersa ang tatlo at tinawag na Unang Triumbirata o alayansa ng tatlong katao. Pinaghatian nila ang buong imperyo. Napunta ang silangang parte kay Crassus, sa kanluran si Caesar at sa gitna at timog na bahagi si Pompey.
- Tagumpay na nasakop ni Pompey ang Armeni at si Crassus ay namatay sa Parthia. Matagumpay ang pakikipaglaban ni Caesar laban sa mga Gaul sa Pransya. Patuloy na pinalawak ni Caesar ang sakop ng imperyo.
- Sa pagiging Matagumpay ni Caesar ay nainggit si Pompey. Sa kanyang impluwensya sa Senado, ipanag utos na buwagin ang kanyang kawal at bumalik agad sa Roma.
- Hindi sumunod si Caesar at tumawid sa Ilog Rubicon at winikang "The die is cast."
- Natakot si Pompey at tumakas sa Gresya. Naglaban ang hukbo ni Caesar at Pompey sa Pharsalus, Thessaly noong 48 BCE. Tumakas si Pompey patungong Egypt at siya at napatay.

- Mula sa Ehipto ay sinakop ni Caesar ang Asya Minor at inulat sa Roma ang mga salitang “Veni, Vedi, Vici” o I came, I saw, I conquer.
- Naging dakila si Caesar at ginawad ng Senado ang titulong master ng daigdigang Romano at diktador ng panghabangbuhay.
- Naging mahusay na pinuno si Caesar. Tinanggap niya ang mga plebian sa Senado at Pinalawak ang miyembro hanggang 900. Tinanggal niya ang mga utang sa mga mahuhirap at binago ang sistema ng pagbubuwis.
- Napalapit siya sa puso ng mga tao pero kinamumuhian siya ng Senado sa kadahilanang baka magtatag ng monarkiya si Caesar.
- Kaya noong Marso 14, 44 BCE ay pinatay si Caesar habang nasa loob ng Senado na tinawag na Ides of March.

Ang Pagtatapos ng Republika

- Sa pagkamatay ni Julius Caesar ay nabuo ang Ikalawang Triumvirate na binubuo ni Octavian, malayang pamangkin sa pinsan ni Caesar, Mark Antony na pinagkakatiwalaang tinuyente ni Caesar at Marcus Lepidus na dating heneral ni Caesar.
- Hinawakan ni Octavian ang Roma at kanlurang bahagi, habang ang silangan si Mark Antony. Hinikayat ni Octavian na magretiro na sa politika si Marcus Lepidus.
- Sa paglipas ng taon, nahikayat ni Octavian na magdeklara ng gyera laban kay Mark Antony at Cleopatra.
- Sa labanan sa Actium noong 31 BCE, ay napatay si Mark Antony.
- Iginawad ang titulong “unchallenged leader” kay Octavian.

Fig 8. Roman Empire Flag

Paksa 2: Ang Pagkakabuo ng Imperyong Romano at ang Pagbasak

Ang Pamamahala ni Octavius

- Iginawad kay Octavian ang titulong princeps o unang mamayan ng Roma at Augustus o “kanyang kamahalan o emperador.”
- Kinilala siya bilang Augustus Caesar.
- Kinontrol niya ang hukbong militar at Pinalawak ang sakop ng imperyo.
- Nagpasa siya ng batas na nagpatatag sa pamilyang Romano.
- Nagpagawa rin siya ng mga daan, irigasyon at mga proyekto na nagpaunlad sa kalagayan ng tao at nagbigay hanapbuhay.
- Namuno si Augustus sa loob ng 40 na taon at tinawag itong Pax Romana o Roman Peace.
- Umabot hanggang sa British Isles hanggang sa timog kanlurang Asya ang imperyo ng Roma sa pagkamatay ni Augustus.

Fig 9. Roman Empire Map

Ang Limang Mabubuting Emperador

1. Nerva

Upang maiwasan ang agawan sa kapangyarihan, ipinatupad niya ang adoption system, na kung saan pinapangalanan na ang susunod na emperador.

2. <i>Trajan</i>	<i>Pinalawak niya ang sakop ng imperyo hanggang silangan ng Euphrates at ang Dacia sa halaga ng Danube.</i>
3. <i>Hadrian</i>	<i>Isang emperador na tagapagtangkilik ng sining at isang mapagtimping tao. Ipinatayo niya ang Hadrian Wall sa England.</i>
4. <i>Antoninus Pius</i>	<i>Ipinagawa niya ang Anonine Wall bilang proteksyon laban sa mga pagala galang tribu.</i>
5. <i>Marcus Aurelius</i>	<i>Ipinatupad niya ang sistemang merit na syang basihan ng pag angat ng ranggo sa militar at opisyal ng gobyerno.</i>

Ang Paghina at Pagbagsak ng Imperyong Romano

1. <i>Ang Pagtaas ng Buwis</i>	➤ <i>Ang mga mahihirap ay nagbabayad ng mabigat na buwis samantala ang mga mayayaman ay nakakaiwas magbayad.</i>
2. <i>Pagpili ng Emperador</i>	➤ <i>Nagkakaroon ng assassination ng mga emperador at ang tagapagmana ng trono. Kung minsan ang militar ang nagluluklok ng emperador na nagsisilbing isang puppet.</i>
3. <i>Ang Paghina ng Ekonomiya ng mga Lungsod</i>	➤ <i>Nang ilipat ni Emperador Constantine ang kapital ng imperyo mula Roma patungong Byzantium o Constantinople ay nanghina ang mga Kanluraning lungsod.</i> ➤ <i>Napabayaang ang mga lungsod na syang pinagkukunan ng mga buwis.</i>
4. <i>Ang Pagbaba ng Populasyon</i>	➤ <i>Hindi makayanan ang gastos at mabigat na buwis na naging dahilan ng pag unti ng anak sa bawat pamilya. Marami din ang namatay dahil sa sakit.</i>
5. <i>Ang Pagsalakay ng mga Barbaro</i>	➤ <i>Sa huling bahagi ng 300 CE, sinakop ng mga barbarong Aleman ang malaking bahagi ng imperyo, sila ang mga Ostrogoths, Visigoths, Vandals, Franks at Angles. Ang mga Hun na nagsimula sa Sentral Asya sa pamumuno ni Attila ay lumusob sa silangan at nagtuloy sa hilagang bahagi ng Gaul.</i>

Ang Kabihasnang Greko-Romano

Fig 10. Aqueduct

Fig 11. Dome

Fig 12. Arch and Vault

Fig 13 & 14. The Colosseum

Fig 15. Virgil

Fig 16. Latin Languages

Fig 17. Roman Catholic

Ang Imperyong Byzantine

Fig 18. Byzantine Empire Map
ang Kodigo ni Justinian.

- Sa pampang ng Kipot ng Bosphorus Palestina, at Ehipto.
- Ang pamamahala sa Imperyong Byzantine ay katulad ng dating imperyong Romano.
- May kapangyarihan din ito sa Simbahan. Siya ang pumipili ng Patriarch ng Constantinople.
- Nang maging emperador si Emperador Justinian noong 527 CE, nakamtan ng imperyo ang pinakamataas na tagumpay.
- Nabawi din ng imperyo nang sumunod na taon ang kabuuan ng Italya at bahagi ng Espana mula sa kamay ng mga Ostrogoth.
- Binuo ni Emperador Justinian ang kodigo mula sa mga ng mga pangkat ng dalubhasa. Tinawag itong Corpus Juris Civilis o

✚ Kalagayang Panrelihiyon

	Simbahan sa Kanluran	Simbahan sa Imperyong Byzantine
Pinuno	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Santo Papa ang pinuno ng lahat ng Simbahan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emperador ang pinuno ng Simbahan at humirang sa Patriarch

Paggamit ng Icon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pinahihintulutan ang paggamit ng icon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ipinagbawal ang paggamit ng icon
Wika sa Misa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latin ang gamit sa misa 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wikang Griyego ang gamit sa misa
Deborsyo/Pari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ipinagbabawal ang deborsyo/ Ipinagbabawal ang pag-aasawa ng mga pari. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pinahintulutan ang deborsyo/ Pinapayagan ang pagpapakasal ng mga pari

✦ **Ang Pagbagsak ng Imperyo**

- Gumamit ng pamamaraang diplomasya, pagpapakasal na may pampolitikang layunin, pagbibigay ng suhol, at paggamit ng dahas.
- Ngunit sa patuloy na pagsalakay ng mga kalaban ay humina ang imperyo. Napadalas din ang pagsalakay ng mga Avar, Slav at Bulgar mula sa Rehiyon ng Balkan.
- Pagsapit ng ika-15 siglo, lumawak ang kapangyarihan ng mga Ottoman sa Anatolia at Balkan sa pangunguna ni Sultan Muhammad II. Sinalakay at tuluyang sinakop ng mga Ottoman ang Constantinople noong Mayo 1453 at tuluyang bumagsak ang imperyo.

✦ **Ang Pamana sa Kabihasanan ng Byzantine**

Fig 19. Mosaic

Fig 20. Hagia Sophia

Fig 21. Cyrillic Letter

Sanggunian:

Soriano, et.al. (2015). *Kayamanan: Kasaysayan ng Daigdig*. Rex Book Store. pp 108-124

Aralin 3: Ang Kabihasang Klasikal ng Amerika at Aprika at sa mga Pulo sa Pasipiko

MELC: Nasusuri ang pag-usbong at pag-unlad ng mga klasikong kabihasan sa: Africa – Songhai, Mali, atbp; America – Aztec, Maya, Olmec, Inca, atbp; Mga Pulo sa Pacific – Nazca

Paksa 1: Sinaunang Aprika

Heograpiya

Ang Aprika ay pangalawang pinakamalaking kontinente sa daigdig. Ang malaking bahagi ng kontinente ay binubuo ng disyerto – sa timog ay matatagpuan ang Kalahari Desert at sa hilagang bahagi naman ay ang Sahara Desert. Sa disyerto matatagpuan ang oasis na kung saan ay may tubig at mga puno. Ang ibang mga pamayanan ay naninirahan sa oasis. Sa gitna ng kontinente ay isang tropical rainforest na kadalasan ay umuulan mula lima hanggang walong pulgada sa isang taon. Sa pagitan ng gubat at malawak na disyerto ay ang savanna. Ang savanna ay kapatagan na kung saan maraming talahib at damo na tumutubo.

Figure 1 Map of Africa

Mga Sinaunang Sibilisasyon sa Aprika

Ang mga Kush

- o Matatagpuan ang Kush sa kahabaan ng Nile sa timog Aprika. Sumasaklaw ito hanggang sa 800 kilometro pahilaga at patimog.
- o Ang Kush ay nasa sangangdaan ng maraming sibilisasyon sa sinaunang daigdig. Nasa hilaga nito ang Rehiyon ng Mediterranean. Doon nagsimula ang mga sibilisasyong Ehipto, Griyego, at Romano. Nasa silangan naman nito ang mga sibilisasyon ng Babylonia, Sumeria Assyria, at Persia. Sa timog at kanluran, nagsimula ang sibilisasyon ng Ghana at Mali.
- o Noong 1500 BCE, sinakop ng Egypt ang Kush at naging kolonya sa loob ng 500 taon. Dulot nito, naimpluwensyahan ang kulturang Kush ng mga ideyang Ehipto tulad ng wika, relihiyon, arkitektura, sining, at relihiyon. Nang bumagsak ang Ehipto, itinaboy nila ang mga Ehipsyo.
- o Inilipat ng mga Kushite ang kanilang kabisera sa timog ng Meroe sa Egypt.
- o Aktibo sa pagsasaka at kalakalan ang mga Kushite. Nagtatanim sila ng trigo, barley, millet at bulak. Nag aalaga sila ng tupa at kambing.

Figure 2 Kush Empire

Figure 3 Meroe Pyramids

- Kilala ang mga Kushite sa kanilang kagamitang bakal, gaya ng espada, gunting, palakol, piko, pala at sipot. May malaking deposito ng iron at ore ang lupain ng Sudan na noon ay sinilangan ng sibilisasyong Kush.
- Nagsimulang humina ang kabihasnang ng Kush nang magapi sila ng mga Romano noong 23 BCE.

★ Ang Ghana

- Ang mga tao sa Ghana ay tinatawag na Soninke.
- Saklaw ng kanilang teritoryo ang rutang daanan ng kalakalan ng mga ginto mula sa Mali, at asin naman mula sa hilagang disyerto.
- Ang pangunahing lungsod ng Ghana ay binubuo ng Djenne, Timbuktu, at Kumbi. Ang Timbuktu ay sentro para sa mga caravan na tumatawid sa disyerto. Ito rin ang sentro ng edukasyon at kalakalan. Ang Djenne ay sentro ng koleksyon ng ginto at aliping nagmula sa kagubatan. Ang Kumbi naman ay kabiserang lungsod ng Ghana. Sa lugar na ito matatagpuan ang palasyo ng hari, maliit na gusaling Napapaligiran ng mataas na pader o bakod, mga pamilihan, at tirahan ng mga negosyanteng Muslim, maharlika, at manggagawa.
- Ang mga taga-Ghana ay magagaling na negosyante at mahusay na panday. Ang mga paninda nila ay asin, ginto, at bakal na ipinapalit nila sa garing (ivory) at alipin.
- Ang mga taga-Ghana ay nahikayat sa Islam. Malaya ang

Figure 5 Sankore Mosque

Figure 4 Ghana Empire

mga iskolar na Muslim na mangaral ng mga ideya mula sa Q'uran at magtayo ng mga paaralan sa mga lungsod ng imperyo.

- Noong 1055 CE, isang pangkat ng mga Berber, ang mga Almoravid, ang sumakop sa Ghana. Ngunit inabot ng 21 taon ang mga Almoravid bago nila nasakop ang lungsod ng Kumbi. Nag aklas ang mga tao naitaboy palabas ng kaharian ang mga Almoravid.

- Pagkalaya ng mga taga-Ghana ay sumigla muli ang kalakalan sa kaharian ngunit ibat ibang pinuno ng mga tribo ang namahala sa matandang imperyo, at noong 1420 CE, ang Ghana ay naging bahagi ng Imperyong Mali.

✦ Ang Imperyo ng Mali

- Napasailalim sa kontrol ng mga pinuno ng Mali ang mga ruta ng caravan at mga lungsod sa Ghana. Nagtatag sila ng Ikalawang pinakamalaking imperyo sa daigdig nang panahong iyon.
- Si Sundiata, isang itim na Muslim ang unang mansa o emperador ng Mali. Nasakop niya ang kaharian ng Ghana sa pamamagitan ng digmaan. Muli niyang pinasigla ni Sundiata ang kalakalan ng asin at ginto sa Niani, ang kabisera ng imperyo. Ginawa rin niya itong sentro ng pag aaral.
- Si Mansa Musa ay isa ring dakilang lider ng Mali. Kaniyang Hinati sa mga Lalawigan ang imperyo at humirang ng mga mahusay na gobernador na namamahala sa bawat Lalawigan. Nagpatayo rin siya ng mga moske at mga lungsod-kalakalan tulad ng Timbuktu na siya ring sentro ng kaalamang Muslim.
- Noong 1324, naglakbay si Mansa Musa patungong Mecca upang ganapin ang hajj. Bumagsak ang Mali nang siya ay namatay noong 1337 CE.

Figure 6 Mansa Musa

✦ Ang Songhai

- Isang pangkat ang humiwalay sa mga Mali pagsapit ng ika-14 na siglo. Sila ang mga Songhai na bumubuo ng isang hukbo, nagpalawak ng teritoryo at namahala sa rutang pangkalakalan. Nasakop nila ang lupain ng mga Sarkos. Ang bayan ng Ghana ay naging kabisera nila. Naging pinuno noon ng Songhai ang ilang maharlikang Dia.
- Noong 1464 CE, naging pinuno ng Songhai si Sunni Ali na kilala rin sa tawag na Ali Ber o Ali the Great. Siya magaling na pinuno at may mahusay na hukbo, sundalong kabayuhan at mga barkong pandigma. Sinakop niya ang Timbuktu, Gao, at Djenne. Naghari siya sa loob tatlumpung taon at pinaunlad Timbuktu bilang sentro ng kalakalan at kulturang Muslim sa Aprika.
- Naninirahan sa ang mga taga-Songhai sa mga bahay na yari sa luwad na ang bubong ay mga damo. Ang Songhai ay marunong gumamit ng bakal, tanso, at bronse sa paggawa ng mga kasangkapan, sandata, banga, at palamuti. Mga kamelyo, kabayo, at asno ang kanilang pangunahing transportasyon.
- Wikang Arabic ang kanilang ginagamit sa pakikipagtalastasan.
- Naging kahalili ni Ali Ber ang kanyang anak noong 1492 CE ngunit siya pinatalsik ni Askia Muhammad na may higit na Kasanayan sa pamamahala.
- Noong 1591, sumalakay ang mga Moroccan na may taglay na mga makabagong armas gaya ng kanyon. Bumagsak ang imperyong Songhai dahil sa kawalan ng makabagong armas.

Figure 7 Songhai Empire

Figure 8 Songhai Art

Paksa 2: Ang Sinaunang Amerika

- Ang kontinente ng Hilagang Amerika at Timog Amerika ay nasa pagitan ng dalawang malalawak na karagatan: ang Karagatang Pasipiko at Atlantiko. Nagmistulang hadlang ang mga karagatang ito upang makipag-ugnayan ang mga kabihasnang sa Amerika sa ibang kabihasnang sa Asya, Aprika, at Europa.
- Noong ika-13 siglo BCE, umunlad ang kauna-unahang kabihasnang sa Amerika. Ito ay ang mga Olmec at Toltec sa lupain na ngayon na tinatawag na Mexico. Pinaniniwalaan na sa Panahon ng Yelo (Ice Age) may isang tulay na nagdurugtong sa Asya at Amerika nagsilbing daan upang makapaglakbay ang mga sinaunang tao sa dalawang kontinente.

Figure 9 Map of North and South America

Olmec

Figure 10 Olmec Civilization Map

Figure 11 Olmec Art

- Tinatawag na Olmec o mga taong goma ang pamayanang naninirahan sa baybayin ng Golpo ng Mehiko noong 1200 BCE
- Nakasentro sa relihiyon ang buhay ng mga Olmec. Sila ay mga templo na hugis pyramid at sa tuktok ginaganap ang mga seremonyang panrelihiyon. Isang paraan ng pagsamba ng mga Olmec sa mga diyos ay sa pamamagitan ng paglalaro ng bolang goma.
- Ang sistemang pamilyang ng mga Olmec ay binubuo ng tatlo. Ang dot ay katumbas ng 1, ang bar ay katumbas ng lima, at 0. Ginamit ng mga Olmec ang sistema ng pagbilang sa pagtatala ng eclipse at paggalaw ng planeta. Lumikha rin sila ng dalawang kalendaryo gamit sa pang araw araw na gawain at sa seremonyang panrelihiyon.
- Naniniwala rin ang mga Olmec na ang ilang mga hayop ay may espesyal na kakayahan tulad ng isang jaguar.
- Gumagamit ng mga alahas ang mga Olmec bilang palamuti sa katawan na mula sa feathers at beads.
- Ginagamit nila ang slash and burn para sa sistema ng agrikultura.

Toltec

- Pagkaraang bumagsak ng Teotihuacan, nagtungo ang mga Toltec sa Sentral Mehiko mula sa hilaga at nagtatag doon ng isang estado.

<p>Maya</p> <p>Heograpiya</p>	<p>-Nakatira sa rehiyon na ngayon ay bahagi ng silangan at timog Mehiko, Guatemala, Belize, El Salvador, at Kanlurang Honduras.</p>	
<p>Lipunan at Pamahalaan</p>	<p>-Nakatira sila sa mga sa bahay na ang bubong ay yari sa kogon. -Nahahati sa apat na antas ang lipunang Mayan.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Halach uinic (tunay tao) – mga maharlika o Ah Kin Mai (The Highest One of the Sun) – mga pari na nagsasagawa ng mga seremonya o Mga magsasaka - nagtatanim ng mais, kalabasa, at mga bulak. -nagbabayad sila ng buwis para sa pagsasaayos ng mga templo o Mga alipin -mga manggagawa ng kaharian 	
<p>Sining</p>	<p>-Nagtatayo sila ng malaki at matibay na piramideng bato at templo. -Nakilala ang mga Maya sa larangan ng matematika at astronimiya. -Nalinang ng mga Maya ang komplikadong sistema ng hiroglipiko na kanilang ginamit sa pagtala ng obserbasyon at kalkulasyon sa astronomiya.</p>	

<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p>-Gumagamit sila ng pinatulis na patpat sa pagtatanim ng mga pananim gaya ng mais, sitaw, kalabasa, abokado, sili, pinya, papaya, at cacao.</p> <p>-Pangingisda ay isa rin sa ikinabubuhay nila.</p> <p>-Gumagawa sila ng mga kasangkapan na yari sa bato, luwad, jade, mga panali, basket, at banig.</p> <p>-Ang kababaihan ay gumagawa ng poncho, bahag, at palda na mula sa bulak o sa mga dahoon ng maguey.</p>	
<p>Relihiyon</p>	<p>-Poleistiko ang relihiyon ng mga Maya.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Hunab Ku (tagagawa ng daigdig) o Itzama (diyos ng langit at patron ng mga taong may dugong maharlika) o Ix Chel (diyos ng bahaghari, pagbibigay lunas panganganak at paghahabi) <p>-Tuwing may bagong taon, panahon ng kagipitan, epidemya o tagtuyot ay nagsasagawa ng seremonya at ritwal ang mga Maya upang pakiusapan ang mga diyos at diyosa.</p>	
<p>Aztec</p>		
<p>Heograpiya</p>	<p>-Nagmula sa hilagang Mexico ang mga Aztec.</p> <p>-Noong 1200, nagsilbi ang mga Aztec bilang mga sundalo sa maliliit na lungsod-estado. Naitatag ang kabisera ng Aztec sa Tenochtitlan at unti unti nilang nasakop ang kanilang mga kalapit na kaharian. Pagsapit ng ika-15 siglo ang kabuuan ng gitna Mexico ay napasailalim ng Imperyong Aztec.</p>	
<p>Lipunan at Pamahalaan</p>	<p>-Ang pangunahing batayan ng lipunan ng mga Aztec ay tinatawag na calpulli na kadalasan ay binubuo ng mga pamilya.</p> <p>-Ang mga calpulli ang nagpapatakbo ng paaralan na kung saan ang kalalakihan ay Tinuturuan ng pagkamamamayan, pakikidigma, kasaysayan, sining, at relihiyon.</p> <p>Nahahati sa tatlong antas ng lipunan Aztec</p>	

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Maharlika</i> – kinabibilangan ng pamilya ng hari, kaparian, at mga pinuno ng hukbo. ○ <i>Ordinaryong mamayan</i> – magsasaka, mangangalakal, sundalo, at artisan. ○ <i>Alipin</i> ○ <i>Pochteca</i> – isang pangkat na pinapahalgahan ng mga Aztec. Ito ay mga pangkat ng mga mangangalakal na nagtutungo sa iba’t ibang bahagi ng imperyo. Nagsisilbi rin silang espiya ng kaharian 	
<p>Sining</p>	<p>-Sila ay magaling na manlililok na Nakagawa ng templong piramide, at ang kanilang kalendaryong bato na may bigat na 22 metric ton. Ang kalendaryong bato ay nagpakilala sa daigdig sa mga Aztec.</p>	
<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p>-Pagsasaka ang batayan ng kabuhayan -Sila ay Nagtatanim ng mais, kalabasa, mga gulay, at bulaklak. -Gumawa sila ng irigasyon, naglagay ng hagdang hagdang palayan, at gumamit ng patabang lupa. Gumawa rin sila ng chimampa o isang artipisyal na latian o floating gardens. -Ang mga yaring produkto tulad ng palayok, alahas, pigurin, basket, tela, at mga mamahaling produkto gaya ng asin at palamuting yari sa ginto. -Walang uri ng salapi ang mga Aztec at barter ang ginagawa nila upang makabili ng iba’t ibang produkto.</p>	
<p>Relihiyon</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Huitzilopochtli</i> – diyos ng araw at digmaan ○ <i>Tlaloc</i> – diyos ng ulan ○ <i>Quetzalcoatl</i> – diyos ng hangin at karanungan 	

	<p>-Sila ay nagsasagawa ng mga sakripisyo. Ang mga bihag sa digmaan o mga nagboluntaryo ay inaalay sa mga diyos. Higit na kalugod lugod sa mga diyos ang mga bata bilang sakripisyo.</p>	
<p>Inca</p>		
<p>Heograpiya</p>	<p>-Sa Timog Amerika, Sumibol ang imperyo ng Inca na sumakop sa malaking bahagi ng Bulubunduking Andes. Sakop ng kanilang teritoryo ang Peru, Bolivia, Ecuador, at mga bahagi ng Chile at Argentina.</p>	
<p>Lipunan at Pamahalaan</p>	<p>-Hinati sa mga rehiyong kilala sa daigdig bilang "Apat na Suyus" na Cuzco ang nasa sentro.</p> <p>-Tinatawag na mga Inca ang kanilang imperyo na Tahuantinsuyu o "Land of the Four Quarters"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Antisuyu - nakahimlay sa silangan ng Cuzco hanggang sa kagabutan ng Amazon. o Cuntisuyu - binubuo ng lahat ng lupain sa kanluran, kabilang ang Rehiyon sa kostal ng Peru. o Collasuyu - ang pinakamalaking suyu na sakop ang timog na bahagi ng imperyo. Saklaw nito ang Lake Titicaca, mga rehiyon sa Bolivia, Chile, at Argentina. o Chincasuyu - ang hilagang parte ng imperyo. Saklaw nito ang lupain ng Ecuador at hilagang Peru. <p>-Ang lipunang Inca ay organisado - mula sa emperador at sa mga maharlika pababa sa mga magsasaka.</p> <p>-Ang lipunang Inca ay nakabatay sa ayllu. Ito ay binubuo ng mga pamilyang sama-samang naninirahan at gumagamit ng bukid, hayop, at ani.</p> <p>-Ang emperador ay nakatira sa palasyo na napalilibutan ng mga kagamitang yari sa ginto at pilak.</p> <p>-Ang mga lalaki ay nagsusuot ng brsscloth (walang manggas na tunic at poncho). Ang kababaihan naman ay may mahabang damit at kappa na isinasara sa pamamagitan ng</p>	

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

	<p><i>aspiling yari sa tanso, pilak o ginto. Inaayos ng lalaki ang kanilang buhok ayon sa kinabibilangang ayllu.</i></p>	
<p>Sining</p>	<p><i>-Ang talaan ng mga kasulatan ay nakatala sa quipu o isang hilerang binuhol na tali na nakasabit mula sa mahabang panali.</i> <i>-Mayaman sa musika ang mga Inca. Nakagawa sila ng mga instrumentong musikal na kinabibilangan ng wind instruments tulad ng horns, flutes, at percussion.</i></p>	
<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p><i>-Ang mga kababaihan ay gumagawa ng chicha o isang alak na gawa sa mais, at ang patatas at mais ay ginawa nilang harina. Gumagawa rin sila ng mga tela sa pamamagitan ng pag-ikid at paghahabi ng bulak o lana.</i> <i>-Sila ay nagtatanim ng mga mais, patatas, kalabasa, sitaw, sili, mani, at cassava.</i></p>	
<p>Relihiyon</p>	<p><i>-Naniniwala sa maraming diyos ang mga Inca at naniniwala rin sila na maaring mabuhay pagkaraang mamatay ang isang tao, kung kayat sinasamba nila ang kaluluwa ng kanilang mga ninuno.</i> <i>-Ang bawat pamilya ay may huaca.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Viracocha - tagalikha ng mundo o Inti - diyos ng araw at pinagmulan ng maharlikang pamilya. 	

Paksa 3: Ang Kabihasnang Pasipiko

Sa karagatang Pasipiko ay matatagpuan ang mga Rehiyon ng Oceania. Kabilang dito ang mga Rehiyon ng Polynesia, Micronesia, at Melanesia. Ito ay binubuo ng libong-libong pulo na tinitirhan ng mga mamayan na sanay sa kulturang pangkaragatan.

Polynesia

Heograpiya at Kasaysayan

-Ang Polynesia ay binubuo ng mahigpit sanlibong pulo mula sa Gitnang Pasipiko hanggang sa New Zealand. Ang salitang Polynesia ay hango sa wikang Griyego na "polus" na ang ibig sabihin ay "marami" at "nesos" na nangangahulugang "pulo."

-Ito ay hugis triyngulo mula sa Hawaii sa hilagang-silangan patungong Easter Island sa timog-silangan at sa New Zealand sa kanluran. Sakop nito ang mga pulo na tulad ng Fiji, Samoa, Tonga, Tuvalu.

-Pinaniniwalaan na ang mga ninuno ay nanggaling sa Timog Tsina at Formosa noong 5000 hanggang 3000 BCE. Naglakbay sila patungong timog at dumaan sa Pilipinas at iba pang bahagi ng Timog-silangang Asya bago lumayag patungong sa Pasipiko.

-Ang pagkakatulad ng kanilang mga itsura sa Pilipinas, Malaysia, at Indonesia ay ang ebidensya at paliwanag ng mga historyan ng migrasyon.

Kultura

-Mga bihasang manlalayag

-Nagtatag ng mga pamayanan na pinamumunuan ng mga maharlika.

-Ang pwesto ay namamana ngunit sa Samoa ang katungkulan ay nababatay sa pagkilala ng komunidad sa kakayahang mamuno.

-Ang bahay ay yari sa kahoy, kawayan, at mga dahoon ng puno ng niyog.

-Hiwa-hiwalay ang pamayanan ng mg Polynesia na madalas ay may pader na yari sa kahoy o bato.

-Mahilig sa palamuti gaya ng pagtatato bilang tanda ng katapangan at kagandahan.

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<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p>-Nabubuhay sa pamamagitan ng pangingsida at pagtatanim ng breadfruit, taro, saging, at niyog.</p> <p>-Mahusay sa paggawa ng bangka na kanilang ginagamit sa pangangalakal at sa paghahanap ng makakain sa ibang pulo. Naitbento nila ang catamaran, isang uri ng bangka na may dalawang hull o katawan na mas mabilis kaysa sa pangkaraniwang bangka.</p>	
<p>Mga Ambag</p>	<p>-Ang mga hardin sa mga hamlet ay nagbibigay ng mga produktong agrikultural tulad ng kamote, taro, rimas, saging, tubo, at niyog.</p> <p>-Ang kava ay isang inuming hindi alkohol na gawa sa ugat ng halamang paminta na paboritong inumin ng matatanda at kadalasan ginagamit sa mga seremonya.</p> <p>-Ang kahoy mula sa puno ng rimas ay ginagamit sa paggawa ng mga canoe at ang mga hibla nito ay ginagawang tela na tinatawag na tapa.</p> <p>-Ang larangan ng sining at arkitektura ay kanilang napaunlad. Nakagawa sila ng mga higanteng mukha inukit sa malalaking bato sa pulo Easter Island.</p>	
<p>Micronesia</p>		
<p>Heograpiya at Kasaysayan</p>	<p>-Sa kanlurang bahagi ng Pasipiko matatagpuan ang Micronesia. Nagmula rin sa salitang Griyego "mikros" na nangangahulugang maliit at nesos na ibig sabihin ay mga pulo.</p> <p>-Ang Micronesia ay nasa bahagi pa rin ng Oceania na matatagpuan sa silangan ng Pilipinas, Indonesia, Papua New Guinea, at Melanesia. Ang Guam, Northern Mariana Islands, Kiribati, Palau, Federated States of Micronesia, Marshall Islands, Nauru, at Wake Island ang bumubuo sa Micronesia.</p>	

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>Kultura</p>	<p>-Mahusay na manlalayag sa karagatan na gumagamit ng araw, buwan, at mga bituin bilang gabay sa paglalakbay. -Gumagamit ng mga pahiwatig ng mga ibon, isda, at mga agos ng dagat upang malaman ang kanilang kinaroroonan. -Mahusay sa paggawa ng bangka tulad ng ut ang mga Carolinian at mga parao ng mga katutubo ng Marianas na tinawag na Chamoro. -Ngumunguya sila ng nganga at buyo bilang libangan. -Naniniwala sila sa espiritu ng kalikasan at ng kanilang mga ninuno.</p>	
<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p>-Pangingisda at pagsasaka ang pangunahing hanapbuhay. -Sa Marianas at Caroline's, ang mga katutubo ay Nagtatanim ng palay sa pamamagitan ng rice terraces. -Ang kanilang pananim ay gabi at ube.</p>	
<p>Mga Ambag</p>	<p>-Magagaling silang gumawa ng canoe. Ang layag ng kanilang bangka ay triyanggulo at nalilipat sa magkaibang dulo.</p>	

Melanesia

Heograpiya at Kasaysayan

-Nagmula sa salitang Griyego na "melas" na nangangahulugang maitim at "nesos" na nangangahulugang mga pulo.
 -Sa Kanlurang Pasipiko matatagpuan ang Melanesia.
 -Ang mga pulo na bumubuo ay ang New Guinea, New Caledonia, Solomon Islands, Bismarck Islands, Norfolk Islands, Flores Islands, Nauru, Sumba at ang pulo ng Timor.

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

<p>Kultura</p>	<p>-Ang wikang gamit nila ay nagmula sa grupo ng mga wika na tinatawag na Papuan. -Ang kanilang pinuno ay napipili at hindi namamana. Ang pagpili ng pinuno ay nababatay sa taglay na katangian tulad talion sa pakikipaglaban at paghimok ng katapatan sa nakakarami. -Ang mga katutubo ay naninirahan sa mga kagubatan. -Ang tahanan ay yari sa kahoy, kawayan, at dahoon ng niyog.</p>	
<p>Kabuhayan</p>	<p>-Gumagawa ng bangka na kanilang ginagamit sa paglalakbay sa mga ilog o sa mga pulo. -Nabubuhay sa pamamagitan ng pangangaso, pagtatanim, at pangingsida.</p>	
<p>Mga Ambag</p>	<p>-Ginamit nila ang swidden horticulture na kung saan hinayaang nakatiwangwang ang lupa ng ilang panahon bago muling taniman. -Gumamit sila ng sistemang kaingin sa paggagawa ng bagong taniman. -Mayroon silang sistema ng palitan na kung saan ang labis na nilutong baboy o halamang ugat ay ipinapalit ng mahalagang bagay buhat sa seremonya o ritual tulad ng kabibe o ngipin ng aso.</p>	

Sanggunian:
 Soriano, et.al. (2015). *Kayamanan: Kasaysayan ng Daigdig*. Rex Book Store. pp 130-145

Aralin 4: Ang Daigdig sa Panahon ng Transisyon

MELC: Nasusuri ang mga pagbabagong naganap sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon; Politika (Pyudalismo, Holy Roman Empire), Ekonomiya (Manoryalismo) at Sosyo-kultural (Paglakas ng Simbahang Katoliko, Krusada).

Paksa 1: Ang Pag-usbong ng Europa

Ang pagbagsak ng kapangyarihan ng mga Romano ang nagbigay-daan sa bagong pamumuhay. Ito ang naghudyat sa pagsisimula ng Gitnang Panahon mula 500-1500 CE. Nagdatingan sa imperyo ng Roma ang mga mananakop na barbaro buhat sa hilaga ng Europa. Tuluyang nasakop ng mga barbaro ang Roma at ang mga lalawigan nito sa kanlurang Europa noong 467 CE. Ang mga pangkat-etnikong Aleman ay bumuo ng maliliit na kaharian at sila ang namayani sa pook mula ika-5 siglo hanggang sa simula ng ika-7 siglo.

Ang mga Franks

- Isa sa mga naitatag na kaharian ay ang kaharian ng mga Frank na matatagpuan sa Gaul na ngayon ay bansang France. Naging hari ng mga Frank si Clovis noong 481 CE. Naglunsad siya ng digmaan upang pagisahin ang lahat ng kahariang Aleman.
- Sa pagkapanalo sa isang digmaan noong 496 CE, tinanggap niya ang Kristyanismo na ikinalugod ng Simbahang Katolika.
- Noong 511 CE, napag-isa ni Haring Clovis ang buong Gaul at kinilalang tagapagtatag ng dinastiyang Merovingian.
- Nang namatay si Clovis nagkaroon ng digmaan sa kaharian dahil sa pag-aagawan ng mga kaanak sa trono.

Figure 12 Clovis

✦ Pepin the Short

- Minana ni Pepin ang trono mula sa kanyang ama na si Charles Martel at dito nagsimula ang Carolingian Dynasty.
- Naging tagapagtanggol ng Simbahang Katolika si Pepin. Isinalin ni Pepin sa Papa ang bahagi ng teritoryong kontrolado ng mga Lombards at naging parte ng Estado ng Papa.
- Noong 751 CE, pinatalsik ni Pepin ang huling haring Merovingian at tinanghal siyang hari ng mga Frank.
- Minana ni Charles, anak ni Pepin ang trono noong 771 CE at tinanghal na Charlemagne o Charles the Great.

✦ Charlemagne

- Tulad din ng mga naunang haring Frank prinotektahan ni Charlemagne ang kapakanan ng Papa.
- Ang buong France at ang malaking bahagi ng Alemanya at Italya ay napasakamay ni Charlemagne.
- Bilang emperador, nagpatupad si Charlemagne ng mga pagbabago sa pamamahala. Kanyang hinati ang imperyo sa duchies at counties na pinamumunuan ng isang konde o duke.
- Ang palasyo ni Charlemagne ay nasa Aix-la-Chapelle sa Kanlurang Germany.

Figure 13 Charlemagne

- Pinaunlad ni Charlemagne ang karunungan sa kanyang imperyo. Naghanap siya ng mga guro at iskolar. Inutusan din niya ang mga monghe na magbukas ng mga paaralan at paramihin ang kanilang aklatan.
- Noong 814 CE, namatay si Charlemagne at napunta ang trono sa kanyang anak na si Louis the Pious.

Ang Banal na Imperyong Romano

- Nagkaroon ng digmaan sa pagitan ng mga anak ni Louis the Pious kung sino ang magmamana ng trono.
- Hinati sa tatlong bahagi ang imperyo sa kanyang tatlong anak na nabuo sa Kasuduan sa Verdun noong 843 CE.
- Ang gitnang bahagi ay napunta kay Lothair. Sakop nito ang Lorraine, Alsace, Burgundy, Provence, at ang mga Low Countries. Napunta kay Charles the Bald ang Pransya at ang Alemanya ay napunta kay Louis the German.
- Noong 870 CE, ang buong kaharian ni Lothair ay muling nahati sa pamamagitan ng Kasunduan ng Mersen. Napasakamay ng West France ang Lotharingia. Ang paghahatian ay nagbigay pundasyon sa makabagong estado ng Alemanya at France.
- Noong 936 CE, umupo sa trono si Oto I. Nakipagkasundo si Oto I sa Santo Papa sa Diploma Ottonium na nagsasaad na magiging tagapagtanggol ng mga lupain ng Santo Papa ang emperador.
- Nagkaroon ng pagbabagong politikal sa Imperyo sa panahon ni Oto I. Ang pamumuno ng mga duchies ay sinubukang ipagkaloob sa mga Obispo at abbot.
- Sa pangunguna ni Oto I at ang kanyang mga hakbang ay naitatag ang banal na Imperyong Romano.

Figure 14 Map of the Holy Roman Empire

Ang Paglakas ng Simbahan

Nagkaroon ng malaking impluwensya ang Simbahan sa Gitnang Panahon. Ito ang pangunahing institusyon sa Europa na nagbigkis sa mga tao at bansa pagkatapos mawasak ng Imperyong Romano.

Mga Daan sa Paglakas ng Kapangyarihan ng Kapapahan

➤ Ang Pagbagsak ng Imperyong Roma

- Nang pumasok ang mga barbaro sa Imperyong Roma, ang tanging institusyon lamang na hindi kinalaban ay ang Simbahan. Sa panahong ito ang simbahan ang nangalaga sa mga pangangailangan ng mga tao.
- Maging ang mga barbaro ay nahikayat magpabinyag bilang isang Kristyano at maging tapat na kaalyado ng mga pari.

Ang Organisasyon ng Simbahan

- Anyong tatsulok ang organisasyon ng simbahan. Nasa tuktok ang Santo Papa na nagsisilbing pangkalahatang pinuno ng simbahan. Ang obispo ay naman ang nasa ikalawang antas na katuwang ng Santo Papa sa pamamahala. Tungkulin ng obispo lutasin ang mga sigalot na may kaugnayan sa mga aral ng simbahan at gabayan ang mga pari. Katulong niya ang isang Curia, na binubuo ng mga Kardinal na pinili mula sa pangkat ng mga Arsobispo. Kapag namatay ang Santo Papa, ang mga Kardinal ang pipili ng kapalit. Ang mga pari nasa ikatlong antas na gumaganap sa mga banal na sakramento ng simbahan at nagpapalaganap ng Kristyanismo.
- Ang simbahan ay bumuo ng Canon Law o kalipunan ng mga batas tungkol sa mga aral ng Kristyanismo, kaasalan at moralidad ng mga pari. Ang sinumang sumuway sa batas ay pinaparusahan ng simbahan. Ang pinakamabigat na parusa ay ang excommunication at interdict. Ang excommunication ay isang parusa na nag aalis ng karapatan at pribilehiyo bilang kasapi ng simbahan. Ang interdict ay pagpapatigil ng simbahan sa pagganap ng sakramento sa isang kaharian kapag hindi sumusunod ang isang hari sa kagustuhan ng simbahan.

Figure 15 Church Hierarchy during the Middle Ages

Ang Pamumuno ng mga Monghe

Figure 16 Monastery

- Ang mga monghe ay binubuo ng mga pangkat ng mga pari na tumalikod sa makamundong pamumuhay at nanirahan sa mga monasteryo. Namumuhay sila sa panalangin at sariling disiplina.
- Ang mga monghe ay marunong magsaka, mag alaga ng hayop at magsulat ng mga libro.
- Ang gawaing makasining tulad ng mga manuskripto at pintura ay napreserba ng mga monghe sa pamamagitan ng matiyagang pagkopya. Sila ay gumagawa ng mga libro na kalimitan ay biblia na sulat kamay. Naging sentro ng sining at karunungan ang mga monasteryo.
- Ang mga monghe kumalinga sa mga maysakit, mahihirap at manlalakbay.
- Dahil dito, mas napalapit ang mga tao sa simbahan at lumawak ang Kristyanismo sa Europa.

Ang Krusada

Ang Krusada ay serye ng labanan ng mga Kristyano mula sa Kanlurang Europa upang mabawi muli ang Banal na Lupain mula sa kamay ng mga Muslim. Ang krusada ay unang ginawa noong 1096, at nagwakas sa huling bahagi ng ika-13 siglo. Ang salitang krusada ay pagsasalarawan ng pagsisikap ng mga Europeo na mabawi ang banal na lungsod ng Jerusalem mula sa mga Muslim.

Pinagmulan ng Krusada

- Pagkaraan ng kamatayan ni Charlemagne at pagkaraang bumagsak ang kanyang imperyo, ang Kristyanong Europeo ay napasailalim ng pag atake. Nilooban ng mga Magyars mula Asya ang Silangan at Gitnang bahagi ng Europa. Ginulo ng mga Vikings pamumuhay sa hilagang bahagi ng Europa at maging ang mga lungsod sa Mediterranean. Pagsapit ng ika-8 siglo, nakontrol ng mga pwersang Muslim ang Hilagang Aprika, hanggang silangan baybayin ng Mediterranean at kalakhan bahagi ng Espanya.
- Ang mga Europeong Kristyano ay gumaganap ng pilgrimage upang bisitahin ang Jerusalem. Bagamat nasa ilalim ng pamumuno ng mga Muslim ang lungsod, sila ay pinapayagan pumasok sa kondisyon na magbabayad ng buwis at susunod sa mga batas.
- Noong ika-11 na siglo naging makapangyarihan ang mga Seljuk Turks at unti unting nasakop ang Byzantine Empire. Sa pangambang tuluyang masakop ang buong imperyo, humingi ng tulong si Emperador Alexius I kay Pope Urban II na magpdala ng hukbo. Tumugon ang Santo Papa at sa Konseho ng Clermont at hinimok ang lahat ng mga Kristyano na magkaisa at bawiin ang banal na lupain at paalsin ang mga Muslim.

Figure 17 Crusades

Figure 18 Crusades Map

Mga Krusada	Taong Nanguna	Mga Kaganapan
Unang Krusada 1096-1099	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robert, Duke of Normandy • Raymond, Count of Toulouse • Godfrey, Duke of Lorraine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Narating ng pangkat ang Constantinople ngunit nagapi sila ng mga Turko sa may talampas ng Asya Minor. ➤ Nabawi ang Jerusalem noong 1099

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Nanatili sa kamay nila ang Jerusalem hanggang 1187 ngunit naagaw ng mga Muslim
Ikalawang Krusada 1147-1149	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • King Louis of France • Conrad III, Emperor of the Holy Roman Empire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Tinungo ng hukbo ang Asya Minor, subalit hindi pa nila nararating ang Edessa nang matalo sila ng mga Turko.
Ikatlong Krusada 1189-1192	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • King Richard I of Great Britain • King Philip Augustus of France • Emperor Fredrick Barbossa of the Holy Roman Empire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Nakuha nila ang lupain ng Cyprus at ang lungsod ng Acre ➤ Sa isang kasunduan napayagan ang mga Kristiyano na dumalaw sa Jerusalem.
Ikaapat na Krusada 1202-1204		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Naagaw ang Zara, ang lungsod sa baybayin ng Adriatiko ➤ Inatake ang Constantinople noong 1204 at nagtatag ng maliliit na kahariang pyudal para sa pansariling pangkabuhayan.
Ikalimang Krusada 1271-1221	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leopold VI of Austria • Andrew II of Hungary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Napunta ang Jerusalem sa kamay ng mga krusador sa pamamagitan ng diplomasya at kasunduan.
Ikaanim na Krusada 1228-1229	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • King Fredrick II of the Holy Roman Empire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Napakiusapan ang mga Muslim na isuko ang Jerusalem sa mga Kristiyano

Mga Bunga ng Krusada

- Natutuhan ang paggamit ng pana at kalapati sa paghahatid ng mensahe sa larangan ng digmaan. Mula naman sa mga Muslim, natutuhan ng mga Kristiyano ang paggamit ng pulbura, kaalaman sa astronomiya at algebra.
- Nabawasan naman ang katanyagan ng simbahan dahil sa pandarambong ng mga ilang sumama sa krusada.
- Pinalakas ng krusada ang monarkiya ng Pransya at Inglatera at pinahina naman nito ang kapangyarihang pyudal.
- Nakilala ang mga produktong nagmula sa silangan tulad ng rekado, seda, pabango, at gamot. Umunlad ang kalakalan at pagbabangko. Ang salik na ito ay nakatulong upang ang Espanya at Portugal ay maghanap ng alternatibong ruta patungong India at China.

Paksa 2: Ang Buhay sa Europa noong Gitnang Panahon

Ang Piyudalismo

- Ang piyudalismo (feudalism) ay isang sistemang politikal at militar sa kanlurang Europa noong Gitnang Panahon. Ito ay isang ugnayan ng mga aristokrata (aristocrat) o ng panginoon (lord) at kanyang basalyo (vassal).
- Pinagkalooban ng mga panginoon ang kanilang basalyo ng lupa kapalit ng serbisyong militar at iba pang paglilingkod.
- Ang panginoon at basalyo ay kailangang maging tapat at makatugon sa kanilang mga obligasyon at tungkulin sa bawat isa.
- Nabuo ang sistemang piyudal dahil sa ugnayan sa mga mandirigmang Aleman. Sila ay sumumpang maglilingkod sa kanilang panginoon at bilang kapalit binigyan sila ng mga lupa o fief.

Ang Lipunan sa Sistemang Piyudal

- Nahahati sa tatlong pangkat ang lipunang piyudal: ang noble, klerigo at mga pesante. Sa pangkat ng mga noble kabilang ang hari, kanilang basalyo at mga nakakababang panginoon.
- Karamihan sa mga hari ay walang kapangyarihan. Ang mga panginoong may lupa ay syang may kontrol sa politikal, hudisyal at militar ng kanilang lupain.
- Ang titulo ng mga panginoong may lupa ay prinsipe, baron, duke o konde.
- Tungkulin ng mga panginoon na pamahalaan ang kanilang lupain, mangolekta ng buwis at magpanatili ng mga hukbo ng kabalyero.
- Ang mga klerigo ay nahahati sa dalawang pangkat. Ang mga obispo ay may mataas na katungkulan at kapangyarihan ay syang naninirahan sa katedral. Ang mga pari ay nasa nayon katabi ang kanilang simbahan ay namumuhay ng mahirap. Sila ay kalimitan nagbibigay payo sa mga magsasaka at nagsasaayos ng sigalot sa nayon.
- Ang mga pesante o magsasaka nasa pinakamababang antas. Sila ay may trabahong paglilingkuran ang kanilang panginoon. Sila ay mahihirap at bumubuo sa malaking bahagdan ng populasyon ng manor.

Figure 19 Feudal System

Ang Manoryalismo

- Sa Kanlurang Europa noong Gitnang Panahon ang ekonomiya ay nakasentro sa sistemang manoryal.
- Ito ay sistemang agrikultural na nakasentro sa mga nagsasariling estado na kung tawagin ay manor.
- Ang manor ay lupain sakop ng isang panginoong maylupa na binubuo ng kanyang kastilyo, simbahan, at pamayanan na may 15 hanggang 30 pamilya.

- Kabilang sa mga nasasakupan ay ang bukirin, pastulan, at gubat na nakapalibot sa manor. Halos lahat ng produkto at serbisyo ay ginagawa sa loob ng manor na pinapatakbo ng panginoong maylupa.

Figure 20 Manorial System

- Tungkulin ng panginoon maylupa na bigyan ng pabahay, lupang sakahan at proteksyon ang mga naninirahan sa manor. Kapalit nito ang paglilingkod ng mga tao sa pangangailangan ng kanilang panginoong maylupa.

Ang Paghina ng Piyudalismo

- Sa pagsapit ng ika-13 na siglo, ang sistemang piyudal ay humina. Una marami sa mga panginoong maylupa ay sumama sa krusada at hindi na nakabalik. Ang iba sa kanila ay pinagbenta ang mga lupa upang makasama sa Krusada.
- Pangalawa, lumakas ang kapangyarihan ng hari at binuwag ang sistemang piyudal.
- Pangatlo, sumigla ang kalakalan at lumago ang mga bayan o lungsod bilang sentro ng komersyo. Nilisan ng mga magsasaka ang lupain at nanirahan sa mga lungsod.
- Panghuli, tumama sa buong Europa ang black death o isang nakakahawang sakit na kumutil sa milyong tao sa buong kontinente. Umunti ang populasyon sa bawat manor.

Figure 21 Black Death

Ang Pagsilang ng mga Bayan at Lungsod

- Sa pagbagsak ng sistemang piyudal, unti unting umusbong ang mga bayan at lungsod bilang sentro ng komersyo, industriya at kalakalan.
- Muling nabuhay ang komersyo sa Italya. Ang mga lungsod-estado ng Venice, Genoa at Pisa nagkaroon ng karapatang pangkalakalan sa Constantinople, Syria, Palestina at Hilagang Aprika.

Ang mga Rutang Pangkalakalan

- Ang mga produkto sa silangan ay dinadala pakanluran ng mga mangangalakal na Tsino at Muslim sa pamamagitan ng tatlong ruta:
 1. Mula sa daungan sa Black Sea ay nagtungo sila Constantinople sakay ng mga barkong pangkalakal
 2. Mula sa Indian Ocean at Red Sea hanggang marating ang daungan sa Ehipto.
 3. Mula sa Persian Gulf naglakbay ang mga mangangalakal hanggang marating ang mga daungan sa Silangan ng Mediterranean.
- Ang mga Italyano ang naging tagapamagitan ng mga mangangalakal galing Asya at ng mga mangangalakal buhat sa Gitna at Hilagang Europa.
- Sumigla rin ang komersyo at kalakalan sa Hilagang Europa. Ang ruta sa Dagat Baltic at Dagat Norte ay syang naging daan upang makipagkalakal sila sa mga Flanders na nasa Belgium at Hilagang Pransya at patungong Dagat Mediterranean at Italya.

Figure 22 Medieval Trade Routes

Epekto at Kontribusyon Dulot ng mga Bayan at Lungsod

1. Ang mga bayan at lungsod ang sentro ng kalakalan at industriya. Ang Hilagang Italya at Flanders ay mga bayan naging pangunahing sentro ng paglago ng kalakalan.
2. Tumaas ang populasyon ng mga bayan at lungsod na naging sanhi ng paglaganap ng nakakahawang sakit. Sa parte ng lungsod na kung saan nakatira ang mga mahihirap ang mga bahay dikit dikit at walang maayos na kanal at palikuran.
3. Umunlad ang sistemang guild. Binubuo ito ng mga mangangalakal upang pigilin ang pagpasok ng mga tagalabas sa pagbebenta ng kanilang produkto na hindi nagbabayad ng buwis.

Figure 23 Medieval Town

4. Nagkaroon din ng samahan ng mga may epesyalisasyon, ang crafts guild na binubuo ng mga sapatero, platero, samahan ng mga gumagawa ng baril at iba pa. Ang samahan na ito ang kumokontrol sa kalidad at presyo ng mga produktong ibinebenta sa mga pamilihan, pangalagaan ang kanilang epesyalisasyon, at proteksyunan ang karapatan at buhay ng bawat miyembro.
5. Naging sentro rin ng kultura ang mga bayan at lungsod tulad ng pagpipinta, eskultura, at arkitektura.

Ang Hanseatic League

- Ang mga mahahalagang komersyal na lungsod sa baybayin ng North Sea at Baltic Sea tulad ng Hamburg, Lubeck, at Bremen ay bumuo ng liga na tinawag na Hansa.
- Ang organisasyon ay nabuo upang mabigyan-proteksyon sa mga gawain pangkomersyo.
- Binubuo ito ng humigit 70 na miyembrong lungsod. Ang mga lungsod na kasapi ng liga ay may permanenteng himpilan ng kalakalan sa Flanders, Scandinavia, Inglatera, at Rusya.
- Kapag ang isang kasapi ay lumabas sa anumang kasunduan ay inaalisan ng mga pribilehiyong pangkalakan na kanilang tinamasa.

Figure 24 Hanseatic League Trade Route

Ang Kapitalismo at Pagbabangko

- Ang kapitalismo at pagbabangko ay dalawang bunga ng muling pagsigla ng kalakalan sa Europa.
- Ang kapitalismo ay isang sistema pang-ekonomiya kung saan ang mga pribadong indibidwal ay ginamit ang kanilang kayamanan para sa kapital.
- Sa paglago ng komersyo at pagdami ng pera ng mga mangangalakal. Nabuo ang bangko upang may paglagakan ng mga pera ng mga tao at upang tumubo sila.
- Ang kapitalismo ay nagbigay daan sa pagusbong ng malalaking industriya.

Arkitektura at Sining sa Gitnang Panahon

Figure 25 Medieval Castle

Figure 15 Christ of Mercy between the Prophets David and Jeremiah (between c. 1495 and c. 1500) by Diego de la Cruz

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lolpE3AgS8c&list=PL0eaffF0bkY6fiQNFcDT6AyoEKnHmC_AZ

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Alg_afRdaPc&list=PL0eaffF0bkY6fiQNFcDT6AyoEKnHmC_AZ&index=2&t=14s

Pag-usbong at Pag-unlad ng mga Klasikal na Lipunan sa Europe:

Klasikong Kabihasan sa Africa, America at mga Pulo ng Pacific

Sir Edgar Ariela

AP8 Q2
MELC Based

Klasikong Kabihasan sa Africa, America at mga Pulo ng Pacific

This thumbnail features a green chalkboard with white text. On the desk in front of the board are a globe, a coffee cup, and books. A cartoon character of a man with glasses and a white shirt is on the right side, looking towards the board.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zh36rRy9s70&list=PL0eaffF0bkY6flQNFcDT6AyoEKnHmC_AZ&index=3

Pag-usbong at Pag-unlad ng mga Klasikal na Lipunan sa Europe:

Mga Kontribusyon ng Klasikong Kabihasan

Sir Edgar Ariela

AP8 Q2
MELC Based

Mga Kontribusyon ng Klasikong Kabihasan

This thumbnail is similar to the one above, but the cartoon character is pointing towards the text on the board.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VcHtSxMBbSI&list=PL0eaffF0bkY6flQNFcDT6AyoEKnHmC_AZ&index=4

**Pagbabagong
Pampolitika sa Europa
sa Gitnang Panahon
(Panahong Medieval)**

**AP8 Q2
MELC Based**

Sir Edgar Ariela

Pagbabagong Pampolitika sa Europa sa Gitnang Panahon

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kt7ydim57sU&list=PL0eaffF0bkY6fIQNFcDT6AyoEKnHmC_AZ&index=5&t=7s

**Impluwensiya ng
mga Kaisipang
Lumaganap sa
Gitnang Panahon**

**AP8 Q2
MELC Based**

Sir Edgar Ariela

Impluwensiya ng mga Kaisipang Lumaganap sa Gitnang Panahon

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

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The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Layunin: Naipaliliwanag ang mga katangian ng Kabihasnang Minoan at Mycenaean.

A. Fill in the Blanks.

Panuto: Punan ang patlang ng tamang kasagutan na nakapaloob sa kahon.

Dagat Mediterranean	Mabato	Kultura
Greece	Bulubundukin	Kaisipan
Pamayanan	Komunikasyon	katangian

Ang Kabihasnang *Minoan at Mycenaean* ay kilala sa mga naunang kabihasan na sumibol sa 1. _____. Naging sentro ng sinaunang Greece ang Balkan at karagatan ng Aegean samantalang ang 2. _____ ang naging tagapag-ugnay ng Greece sa iba pang panig ng mundo. Ang mga 3. _____ dito ay nasa dakong baybay dagat. Ang pagiging 4. _____ at 5. _____ ang pangunahing sagabal sa mabilis na daloy ng 6. _____ sa Greece. Mabagal ang paglago ng 7. _____ at teknolohiya subalit ito rin ang naging dahilan upang ang bawat lungsod estado ay magkaroon ng natatanging 8. _____ na nagpayaman ng kanilang 9. _____, gaya ng daungan na nagbigay-daan sa maunlad na kabuhayan, kaugnayan sa iba't ibang uri ng tao na nakatulong upang mapayaman ang kanilang kultura.

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Isulat ang titik ng tamang sagot.

- Saan nagmula ang kaunaunahang sibilisasyong Aegean?
a. Crete c. Kabihasan
b. Peninsula d. Knossos
- Haring nagtatag ng kabihasnang Minoan?
a. Haring Minotor c. Haring Mino
b. Haring Minos d. Haring Minoan

3. Karagatan na naging sentro ng kabihasnang Mycenaean?

- a.** Karatagatang Mycenaean **c.** Karatagatang Pasipiko
b. Karatagatang Aegean **d.** Karatagatang Athens

4. Pangkat na ginupo ang mga Mycenaean?

- a.** Dorian **c.** Athens
b. Spartan **d.** Griyego

5. Apat na pangkat sa pamayanan ng kabihasnang Minoan?

- a.** Maharlika, Mangangalakal, Magsasaka, at ang mga Alipin
b. Maharlika, Negosyate, Mandirigma, at ang mga Alipin
c. Mayaman, May kayamanan, Mangangalakal at ang mga, Alipin
d. Maharlika, Magsasaka, Mangangalakal at mga Alipin

6. Makapangyarihang lungsod ng kabihasnang Minoan?

- a.** Crete **c.** Knossos
b. Lungsod estdao **d.** Aegean

7. Dahilan ng pagwakas ng Kabihasnang Minoan?

- a.** Naging palasak ang digmaan ng mga iba't ibang kaharian
b. Isang pangkat ng tao mula sa hilaga ang pumasok sa Greece at iginupo ang mga Minoan
c. Sinalakay at sinakop ng mga Mycenaean ang crete
d. Nagkawatakwatak at hindi pagkaunawaan ng mga Pinuno at mamamayan

8. Pangunahing kabuhayan sa kabihasnang Minoan ?

- a.** Pangingisda **c.** Pangangaso
b. Pagsasaka **d.** Pangangalakal

9. Sanhi ng Dark Age sa kabihasnang Mycenaean ?

- a.** Naging palasak ang digmaan ng mga iba't ibang kaharian
b. Nahinto ang kalakalan, pagsasaka at ibang kabuhayan
c. Nahinto ang paglago ng sining at pagsulat nang unti-unti ay naudlot
d. Lahat ng nabanggit

10. Toro ni Minos?

- a.** Minotor **b.** Poseidon **c.** Zeus **d.** Apollo

Module 1: Worksheet #2

Layunin: Naipapaliwanag kung bakit lumaganap ang kabihasnang Greek sa halos lahat ng bahagi ng daigdig.

Check list

Panuto: Lagyan ng check (✓) ang pangungusap na naglalahad ng katotohanan patungkol sa kabihasnang Griyego.

- 1. Isa sa mga pinakatangi at pinakamaunlad na sibilisasyon sa daigdig
- 2. Ang mga Griyego ay may pinaniniwalaang Diyos at Diyosa.
- 3. Hindi tanyag ang mga Griyego sa pakikipaglaban at pananakop.
- 4. Nakasulat sa kasaysayan ang mga tula, drama, at epiko bilang mahalagang anyo ng panitikang Griyego.
- 5. Partikular lamang sa Agham at Pilosopiya na lumaganap sa daigdig ay nagmula sa kabihasnang Greek.

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Isulat ang **TAMA** kung ang pangungusap ay nagsasaad ng katoohan at **MALI** naman kung isinassad ng pangungusap hindi tama.

- _____ 1. Ang salitang Pilosopiya ay “ pag-aaral ng batayang katotohanan” ito ay mula sa salita Griyego na nangunguhulugang “pagmamahal sa kaalaman”.
- _____ 2. Sa mga Griyego, ang mga diyos ay katulad din ng mga tao na nakakaranasng ligaya at lungkot.
- _____ 3. May dalawang uri ng dula sa sinaunang Griyego: Lungkot at Pighati.
- _____ 4. Sappho ay isa sa mga tanyag na makatang Griyego na may paksang pagkakaibigan at pag-ibig na tema ng tula.
- _____ 5. Si Socrates ay kinilalaang “Ama ng kasaysayan” dahil sa Ang kanyang malinaw na paglalahad ng digmaang Persian ay naggging pamantayan ng mga manunulat ng kasaysayan.
- _____ 6. Ang Istrakturang may disenyong madahon at mabulaklak na disenyo ng haligi ay tinatawag na Ionic.
- _____ 7. Pynthagorean Theorem ang tawag sa nagpapaliwanag ng relasyon sa pagitan ng mga sulok ng right Triangle.
- _____ 8. Sa pamamaraan ng pagtatanong at pagsasagot (Question and Answer) o ang tinatwag na Socratic Method ay malalaman kung ano ang nalalaman ng isang tao.
- _____ 9. Si Plato ay Isang manggagamot. Itinuro niya na hanapin ang sanhi ng sakit kaysa sisihin ang diyos.
- _____ 10. Isang malaking pagakakamali ng mga Griyego na sila ay makilala at naging tanyag sa buong daigdig.

Module 1: Worksheet #3

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga dakilang ambag ng mga sinaunang Greek sa kasalukuyan.

Chart Matrix . Panuto: Tukuyin kung saan kabilang ang mga konsepto, pangalan o salita na nasa loob ng kahon. Isulat ang sagot sa talahanayan.

Pathenon	Poseidon	Demokrasya	Xenophon	Zeus
Demosthenes	Iliad at Odyssey	Aristokrasya	Pericles	Ionic
Hades	Socrates	Herodotus	Plato	Aristotle
Athena	Doric	Monarkiya	Thucydides	Homer

LARANGAN	KATAWAGAN O PANGALAN
1. Pilosopiya	
2. Tula	
3. Talumpati	
4. Pamahalaan	
5. Relihiyon	
6. Arkitektura	
7. Kasaysayan	

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Isulat ang titik ng tamang sagot.

- Ama ng Kasaysayan**
 - A. Thucydides
 - B. Herodotus
 - C. Xenophon
 - D. Pericles
- Kahanga-hangang marmol na temple sa acropolis**
 - A. Parthenon
 - B. Temple of Mausolus
 - C. Column of Trajan
 - D. Colosseum
- Kalipunan ng mga kwento ni Socrates mula sa aklat ni Xenophon**
 - A. Memorabilia
 - B. Socratic Method
 - C. Anabasis
 - D. Apology of Socrates to the Jury
- Ama ng Biyolohiya**
 - A. Thales
 - B. Plato
 - C. Aristotle
 - D. Socrates
- Pangkat ng mga guro na sumikat sa Athens**
 - A. Scholars
 - B. Humanista
 - C. Scribes
 - D. Sophists
- Pinakabantog na paligsahan sa palara sa buong daigdig**
 - A. Olympic Games
 - B. Marathon
 - C. Olympic Sports
 - D. Marathonian
- Pinakamataas na diyos ng mga diyos at diyosa**
 - A. Poseidon
 - B. Hades
 - C. Zeus
 - D. Hera
- Pinaniniwalaang tirahan ng mga diyos ng sinaunang Griyego**
 - A. Mt. Lycabettus
 - B. Mt. Pelion
 - C. Zas Mountain
 - D. Mt. Olympus
- Lungsod Estado ng demokrasya**
 - A. Sparta
 - B. Thessaly
 - C. Athens
 - D. Thebes
- Dakilang obra ni Homer**
 - A. Iliad and Odyssey
 - B. Antigone
 - C. Prometheus Bound
 - D. History of Persian Wa

Module 2: Worksheet #4

Layunin: Naisa- isa ang mga kontribusyon/ pamana ng Kabihasnang Romano.

Panuto: Punan ng tamang kasagutan

1. Ang kauna- unahang batas ng mga Romano ay _____.
2. Isinasagawa sa _____ ang mga labanan ng gladiator noong 80 C. E .
3. Marami sa mga daan na ginawa ng mga sinaunang Romano ay ginagamit pa hanggang ngayon at isang halimbawa ay ang _____ na nag-uugnay sa Rome at timog Italy.
4. Sinulat ni Livy ang _____ na nagsasalaysay ng kasaysayan ng Roma.
5. Si _____ ng Roma ay isang manunulat at orador na nagpahalaga sa batas.

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Piliin ang tamang sagot. **Titik** lamang ang isulat sa patlang.

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---|
| _____ 1. <i>Pantheon</i> | a. libingan ng mga emperador
b. malaking dulaan
c. paliguan |
| _____ 2. <i>Twelve Tables</i> | a. unang batas ng Carthage
b. batas ng pamalaang sentral
c. unang batas Romano |
| _____ 3. <i>Appian Way</i> | a. rutang pangkalakalan
b. daanang nag-uugnay sa Roma at Capua, Italya
c. daanan para sa digmaan |
| _____ 4. <i>Latin</i> | a. wika ng mga Cartaginian
b. wika ng mga Hebreo
c. wika ng mga Romano |
| _____ 5. <i>Aenid</i> | a. epiko ni Homer
b. epiko ni Vergil
c. epiko ni Gilgamesh |
| _____ 6. <i>Colosseum</i> | a. malaking dulaan na ipinagawa ni Vespasian
b. malaking dulaan sa panahon ni Titus
c. malaking dulaan na ipinagawa ni Caesar |
| _____ 7. <i>Cicero</i> | a. Prinsipe ng Manunulang Romano
b. Prinsipe ng Kasaysayan sa Roma
c. Prinsipe ng Mananalumpating Romano |
| _____ 8. <i>Basilica</i> | a. nagsisilbing simbahan ng mga Romano
b. nagsisilbing korte ng mga Romano
c. nagsisilbing pamilihang Romano |
| _____ 9. <i>Forum</i> | a. plasa at pamilihang Romano
b. pinagpupulungan ng Asembleya
c. bulwagan o korte |
| _____ 10. <i>Ptolemy</i> | a. Teoryang Geocentric
b. Teoryang Heliocentric
c. Teoryang Bigbang |

Module 2: Worksheet #5

Layunin: Naipapaliwanag kung paano pinayaman ng kabihasnang Rome ang kultura ng daigdig.

Panuto: Punan ng tamang kasagutan

Fact o Bluff. Suriin ang mga pahayag at isulat ang **Bluff** kung ang pahayag ay opinyon lamang at **Fact** kung ang pahayag ay isang katotohanan.

- ___ 1. Nakaka apekto ng husto sa mundo ang mga kulturang Romano.
- ___ 2. Ang unang batas ng mga Romano ay napakahalaga sa mga plebeians.
- ___ 3. Ang mga eksperto sa agham sa panahong Romano ay ang mga Griyego.
- ___ 4. Latin ang wika ng mga Romano noon.
- ___ 5. Ang mga kontribusyon ng mga Romano ay naging sandalan ng ilang bansa sa Asya at Europa.

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Venn Diagram. Magtala ng tatlong pagkakatulad at dalawang pagkakaiba ng Rome sa Greece.

Module 2: Worksheet #6

Layunin: Napapahalagahan ang mga ambag ng Kabihasnang Roma sa iba't – ibang larangan at pamumuhay ng tao sa kasalukuyan.

Larawang ito, aalamin ko. Panuto: Ibigay ang kontribusyon ng bawat isa sa pagpapanatili ng kaayusan at kaunlaran ng Kabihasnang Romano.

1. Mga Lansangan

3. Makatang Romano

2. Batas

4. Paniniwala

PANAPOS NA PAGESUSULIT

Panuto: Tama o Mali. Isulat sa patlang ang Tama kung ang pangungusap ay wasto. Kung mali ang pangungusap, palitan ang salitang nakasalungguhit para maiwasto ang pangungusap.

- _____ 1. Kinilala sa tawag na *Hellenistiko* ang pinaghalong kultura ng mga Romano at Griyego na yumabong sa panahon ng Pax Romana.
- _____ 2. Ang unang nasusulat na koda ng batas Romano ay napagtagumpayan ng mga *patrician* sa panahong ipinaglaban nila ang kanilang mga karapatan.
- _____ 3. *Latin* ang wika ng Kabihasnang Romano na naging basehan ng ilang bansa sa Europa.
- _____ 4. Si *Zeus* ang pinakamataas na diyos ng mga Romano noon.
- _____ 5. Sa disensyong arkitektural, dalawa ang naiambag ng mga Romano – ang arko ng tagumpay at *basilica*.
- _____ 6. Gumawa ang mga Romano ng *aqueduct* upang dalhin ang tubig sa lungsod at sa kasalukuyan maraming kanal ang ipinagawa upang maging madali ang agos ng tubig.
- _____ 7. Ang *Colosseum* ay isang pampublikong gusali na libingan ng mga emperador ngunit sa kasalukuyan ay isa ng simbahan.
- _____ 8. Sa kabuuan, ang mga *batas Romano* ang saligan ng mga sistemang legal ng maraming mga bansa.
- _____ 9. *Monoteismo* ang umiiral na paniniwala noon ng kabihasnang Romano.
- _____ 10. Ang tanging masasabing naging ambag ng mga Romano sa agham ay sa larangan ng *astronomiya o pag-aaral sa kalawakan*.

Module 3: Worksheet #7A

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga kaganapan sa kabihasnang klasikal ng Mesoamerica.

Panuto: Basahin ang mga sumusunod na pahayag. Isulat/ilagay ang tamang sagot sa loob ng crossword puzzle sa ibaba.

- Ito ay tawag sa mga nomadikong tribo na ang orihinal na pinagmulan ay hindi tukoy, sila ay tumungo sa Lambak ng Mexico sa pagsapit ng ika-12 siglo C.E.
- Ang tinaguriang **"God of the Feathered Serpent"** ng lipunang Maya.
- Ito ang tawag sa pinuno sa lipunang Maya na katuwang ng mga pinuno ang mga kaparian sa pamamahala sa mga pamayanang urban na sentro rin ng kanilang pagsamba sa kanilang mga diyos.
- Ang nilikha ng mga Aztec upang madagdagan ang lupang tinataniman na kung saan tinabunan ng lupa ang mga sapa at ito ay naging artipisyal na pulo at tinawag na mga floating garden.
- Ang pinakamahalagang diyos ng araw ng mga Aztec dahil sila ay mga magsasaka na taimtim na umaasa sa mga puwersa ng kalikasan at sinasamba ang mga ito bilang mga diyos.

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Basahing mabuti ang bawat tanong at piliin ang wastong sagot mula sa pagpipilian. Letra lamang ng wastong sagotang isusulat sa sagutang papel.

- Nasa sentro ng Mexico Valley ang isang maliit na isla sa gitna ng lawa ng Texcoco. Kailan itinatag ng mga Aztec ang pamayanan ng Tenochtitlan?
a. 1323 b. 1324 c. 1325 d. 1326
- Ano ang kahulugan salitang Inca na hango sa pangalan ng pamilyang namuno sa isang pangkat ng tao na nanirahan sa Andes?
a. Imperyo b. Kaharian c. Lungsod d. Pamayanan
- Bakit humina at bumagsak ang ekonomiya ng kabihasnang Mayan?
a. Nawalan nga mga kagamitan sa pagtatanim ng mga produkto.
b. Nagdulot ng suliranin sa magiging pinuno na mamumuno sa tribu.
c. Pagkaubos ng yaman ng mga lungsodestado dahil sa digmaan at pagkaubos ng mandirigma.
d. Pagkawala ng sustansya ng lupa na nagdulot ng suliranin sa suplay ng pagkain.

4. Sila ay tinaguriang mahuhusay na inhenyero at tagapagtayo ng mga estruktura tulad ng mga kanal o aqueduct, mga dam, gayundin ng sistema ng irigasyon, liwasan, at mga pamilihan.

- a. Aztec
- b. Inca
- c. Mayan
- d. Aztec, Inca At Maya

5. Batay sa graph ng populasyon ng mga Aztec, ilang bahagdan ang naubos na katutubong populasyon ng Mesoamerica sa loob ng 160 taon dahil sa epidemya ng bulutong, pang-aalipin, digmaan, labis na paggawa, at pagsasamantala?

- a. 65 hanggang 75 na bahagdan
- b. 75 hanggang 85 na bahagdan
- c. 85 hanggang 95 na bahagdan
- d. 95 hanggang 100 na bahagdan

Module 3: Worksheet #7B

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga Ambag sa Pag-unlad ng Klasikal na Lipunan sa America

Panuto: Lagyan ng tsek (✓) ang hanay kung saang kontinente matatagpuan ang mga sumusunod na makasaysayang lugar.

Mga Lugar	North America	South America
1. <i>Machu Picchu</i>		
2. <i>Pueblo</i>		
3. <i>Temple of the Sun</i>		
4. <i>Great Serpent Mound</i>		
5. <i>Pyramid of Kukulcan</i>		

Panuto: Gumagawa ang mga tao ng iba't ibang estruktura sa iba't ibang dahilan. Bilugan kung ano ang dahilan ng pagtatayo ng mga sumusunod na estruktura.

1.	2.						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Templo</td> <td>Libingan</td> <td>Imbakan</td> </tr> </table>	Templo	Libingan	Imbakan	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Obserbatoryo</td> <td>Imbakan</td> <td>Tahanan</td> </tr> </table>	Obserbatoryo	Imbakan	Tahanan
Templo	Libingan	Imbakan					
Obserbatoryo	Imbakan	Tahanan					
3.	4.						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Alay sa mga Diyos</td> <td>Panakot sa mga kalaban</td> <td>Kumakatawan sa mga tanyag na tao/pinuno</td> </tr> </table>	Alay sa mga Diyos	Panakot sa mga kalaban	Kumakatawan sa mga tanyag na tao/pinuno	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Para sa mga seremonyang panrelihiyon</td> <td>Libingan ng mga hari</td> <td>Moog</td> </tr> </table>	Para sa mga seremonyang panrelihiyon	Libingan ng mga hari	Moog
Alay sa mga Diyos	Panakot sa mga kalaban	Kumakatawan sa mga tanyag na tao/pinuno					
Para sa mga seremonyang panrelihiyon	Libingan ng mga hari	Moog					

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Panuto: Lagyan ng bituin (★) ang pangkat na inilarawan sa bawat bilang.

Paglalarawan	Aztec	Inca	Maya	Mocg	Olime	Paglalarawan	Aztec	Inca	Maya	Mocg	Olime
1. May nalinang na wika na tinawag na Quechua.						6. Nakapagtayo ng mga pyramid kabilang ang Temple of the Sun					
2. Unang Nakagawa ng kalendaryo sa America.						7. Nakilala sa paglilok ng malalaking estatwang ulo na gawa sa bato					
3. Nakagawa ng mga ornamenting gawa sag into, tanso, at mamahaling baton na nahukay sa mga libingan ng mga pinuno.						8. Paraan ng pagbibilang at pagtatala na tinawag na quipu.					
4. Ang sentro ng bawat lungsod ay isang pyramid na ang itaas na bahagi ay dambana para sa mga diyos.						9. Nakalinang ng Sistema na matematika na gumagamit ng zero.					
5. Nakalinang ng Sistema ng pagsula na binubuo ng 800 na simbolo o glyph.						10. Gumawa ng mga causeway o itinataas na daanan para madaling maipagtanggol ang kanilang lugar.					

Panuto: Isulat sa patlang ang **TAMA** kung ang pahayag ay **WASTO** at isulat ang salitang **MALI** kung ito ay **DI-WASTO**.

- _____ 1. Ang **chinampas** ay mga artipisyal na pulo na kung tawagin ay mga floating garden.
- _____ 2. Sa **Kabihasnang Mayan** ay may mahuhusay na inhinyero at tagapagtayo ng mga estruktura tulad ng mga kanal o aqueduct, mga dam, gayundin ng sistema ng irigasyon, liwasan, at mga pamilihan.
- _____ 3. Nakilala ang mga **Adena** sa paglilok ng malalaking estatwang ulo na gawa sa bato.
- _____ 4. May dalawang uri ng kalendaryo ang Mayan, ang kalendaryong solar at relihiyosong kalendaryo.
- _____ 5. Ang mga **Adena** ay tinawag na mound builders dahil sa paglalagay nila ng mga buntong lupa para matabunan ang libingan ng kanilang yumao.
- _____ 6. Madaling ipagtanggol ng **Aztec** ang kanilang lungsod dahil ang mga daanan nito ay sa pamamagitan ng mga causeway o itinataas na daanan.
- _____ 7. Ang **Pyramid of the Sun** ay ginawa ng mga Olmec.
- _____ 8. Ang **Pyramid of Kukulcan** ay patunay ng mataas na kaalaman ng mga Mayan sa arkitektura, inhenyeriya, at matematika.
- _____ 9. Mahilig ang **Anasazi** sa mga pista at palaro. Pinakapaborito nilang laro ang **pok-ta-pok**, isang uri ng larong basketball.
- _____ 10. Dahil sa ambag ng mga **Olmec**, nagkaroon sila ng malaking impluwensiya sa ibang pang sibilisasyon sa America.

Module 3: Worksheet #8A

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga kaganapan sa kabihasnang klasikal ng Africa.

Panuto: Basahin ang mga mga sumusunod na pahayag. Pumili ng tamang sagot sa loob ng kahon at isulat ang tamang sagot sa patlang.

GHANA	SAVANNA	CARAVAN
	RAINFOREST	MALI

1. Ito ay isang uri ng kagubatan kung saan sagana ang ulan at ang mga puno ay malalaki, matataas, at may mayayabong na dahon_____.
2. Ito ay nasa hangganan ng rainforest na isang bukas at malawak na grassland o damuhan na may mga puno_____.
3. Sa kalakalang Trans-Sahara ano tawag sa pangkat ng mga taong magkakasamang naglalakbay_____.
4. Ito ang unang estadong naitatag sa Kanlurang Africa. Sumibol ang isang malakas na estado sa rehiyong ito dulot ng lokasyon nito sa timog na dulo ng kalakalang Trans-Sahara_____.
5. Ito ang tagapagmana ng Ghana. Nagsimula sa estado ng Kangaba, isa sa mahalagang outpost ng Imperyong Ghana_____.

Triple Venn Diagram. Isa-isahin ang pagkakatulad at pagkakaiba ng *Imperyong Ghana, Mali, at Songhai*. Isulat sa Venn Diagram ang sagot.

Panuto: Basahin ang mga mga sumusunod na pahayag. Pumili ng tamang sagot sa loob ng kahon at isulat ang tamang sagot sa patlang.

Berber	Oasis	MansaMusa
Silangang Africa		Kanlurang Africa

1. Siya ang namuno sa Imperyong Mali noong 1312 na yumaman sa pamamagitan ng kalakalan. _____.
2. Sino ang nagdala ng relihiyong Islam sa Hilagang Africa?-_____.
3. Saan bahagi ng Africa naging tanyag ang kahariang Axum?_____.
4. Saan bahagi ng Africa nakilala ang tatlong imperyo imperyo ng Ghana, Mali, at Songhai na siyang naging makapangyarihan dulot rin ng pakikipagkalakalan sa mga mamamayan sa labas ng Africa?_____.
6. Ang ay lugar sa disyerto kung saan may matabang lupa at tubig na kayang bumuhay ng halaman at hayop._____.

Module 3: Worksheet #8B

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga Ambag sa Pag-unlad ng Klasikal na Lipunan sa Africa

Panuto: **Bilugan** ang hindi kabilang sa bawat bilang.

1. Sunni Ali: Timbuktu, Gao, Djenne, Morocco
2. Sinaunang Africa: Songhai, Maya, Axum, Mali
3. Mga Pinuno sa Sinaunang Kaharian sa Africa: SundiataKeita, Dia Kossoi, Itzamna, Al Bakri
4. Pangunahing produkto sa Sinaunang Africa: asin, ginto, ivory, tela
5. Mga naging sentro ng kalakalan sa Sinaunang Africa: Timbuktu, Axum, Walata, Mexico

Panuto: Tukuyin ang mga rehiyong ekolohikal sa Africa. Piliin ang sagot sa loob ng kahon.

rainforest, baybavin, Sahara, Sahel, savanna

1. Ang rehiyong ito ay tinawag na _____ kung saan karamihan ng mga tao sa Africa ang naninirahan.

2. Matatagpuan ang _____ Hilagang Africa. Ito ang pinakamalalag na diyerto sa buong mundo

3. Ang mga _____ ay mga kapatagan na may mataas na damuhan. Dito gumagala ang maraming uri ng hayop sa Africa.

4. Ang rehiyong _____ ay tuyong damuhan na matatagpuan sa timog Sahara.

5. Ang mga _____ ay masusukal na kagubatan na sakop ang halos 1/5 Africa.

Panuto: Gumagawa ang mga tao ng iba't ibang estruktura sa iba't ibang dahilan. Tukuyin kung ano ang dahilan ng pagtatayo ng mga sumusunod na estruktura. **Bilugan ang letra ng tamang sagot.**

- a. Markahan ang teritoryo
- b. Ipaalala ang mga tagumpay sa labanan
- c. Parangal sa hari

- a. Obserbatoryo
- b. Pook-sambahan
- c. Tahanan ng mga pari

- a. maging daungan ng barko
- b. maging tahanan ng hari
- c. maging sentro ng kalakalan

Panuto: Lagyan ng tsek (✓) ang mga patlang kung ang pangungusap ay *tama* at ekis (X) kung *hindi*.

- _____ 1. Mga elepante, ivory (ngipin at pangil ng elepante), sungay ng rhinoceros, pabango, at pampalasa o rekado ang karaniwang kinakalakal ng kaharian ng Axum sa Mediterranean at Indian Ocean.
- _____ 2. Isang resulta ng malawakang kalakalan ng Axum ay ang pagtanggap nito ng Islam.
- _____ 3. Ang mga kamelyo ay nagbibigay ng ligtas at mabilis na paraan ng transportasyon para sa mga mandirigma sa Imperyong Ghana.
- _____ 4. Nagkaroon sa Ghana ng malaking pamilihan ng iba-ibang produkto tulad ng ivory, ostrich, feather, ebony, at ginto.
- _____ 5. Ang Imperyon Mali ay yumaman sa pamamagitan ng kalakalan katulad ng sa Ghana.
- _____ 6. Nagpatayo si Mansa Musa ng mga mosque o pook-dasalan ng mga Muslim sa mga lungsod ng imperyo.
- _____ 7. Noong 1255, ang malalaking lungsod pangkalakalan tulad ng Walata, Djenne, Timbuktu, at Gao ay naging bahagi ng Imperyong Mali.
- _____ 8. Sa pakikipagkalakalan sa Algeria, nakapagtatag ng ugnayan ang Songhai sa iba pang bahagi ng Imperyong Islam.
- _____ 9. Iginalang at pinahalagahan pa rin ni Sunni Ali ang mga mangangalakal at iskolar na Muslim na nananahan sa loob ng kaniyang imperyo kahit hindi niya tinanggap ang relihiyong Islam.
- _____ 10. Ang mga imperyong Ghana, Mali, at Songhai ay naging makapangyarihan dahil sa kalakalan. Pangunahing produkto nila ay tela, salamin, tanso, at bakal.

Module 3: Worksheet #9A

Layunin: Naiisa-isa ang mga kaganapan sa sinaunang kasaysayan at kultura ng mga pulo sa Pacific at Timog-Silangang Asya.

Panuto: Basahin ang mga mga sumusunod na pahayag. Isulat/ilagay ang titik ng tamang sagot sa patlang.

HANAY A	HANAY B
1. _____ Ito ay matatagpuan sa gitna at timog na bahagi ng Pacific Ocean na nasa silangan ng Melanasia at Micronesia.	A. Animismo
2. _____ Ito ay matatagpuan sa hilaga at silangang baybay-dagat ng Australia.	B. Austronesian
3. _____ Ito ay maliit nap ulo at matatagpuan sa hilaga ng Melanasia at sa silangan ng Asya.	C. Mana
4. _____ Tumutukoy sa sinaunang relihiyon ng mga Micronesian, ang mga rituwal para sa mga makapangyarihang diyos ay kinapapalooban ng pag-aalay ng unang ani.	D. Micronesia
5. _____ Ito ay nangangahulugang "bisa" o "lakas". Sa mga sinaunang Polynesian, ito ay maaaring nasa gusali, bato, bangka, at iba pang bagay.	E. Micronesia
	F. Polynesia

Pagsagot sa Chart. Punan ng impormasyon ang talahanayan.

ISLA	KAHULUGAN	KABUHAYAN	RELIHIYON
<i>Polynesia</i>			
<i>Micronesia</i>			
<i>Melanasia</i>			

PANAPOS NA PAGSUSULIT

Panuto: Piliin ang tamang sagot sa bawat tanong. Isulat ang titik ng tamang sagot sa sagutang papel.

1. Ito ay matatagpuan sa gitna at timog na bahagi ng Pacific Ocean na nasa silangan ng Melanasia at Micronesia.
 - a. Micronesia
 - b. Monolesia
 - c. Polynesia
 - d. South America
2. Ang sentro ng pamayanan Polynesia ay ang tohua. Saan ito matatagpuan?
 - a. kadalasang nasa gilid ng mga bundok.
 - b. Kadalasang nasa gilid mga ilog.
 - c. Kadalasang nasa gilid ng mga puno
 - d. Kadalasang nasa lahat ng parti ng lupain.
3. Ano ang pangunahing kabuhayan ng mga Micronesian.
 - a. Pagsasaka
 - b. Pangangaso
 - c. Pangingisda
 - d. Pagkakaingin
4. Ito ay nangangahulugang "*bisa*" o "*lakas*". Sa mga sinaunang Polynesian, ito ay maaaring nasa gusali, bato, bangka, at iba pang bagay.
 - a. Atoll
 - b. Mana
 - c. Taro
 - d. Tapo
5. Ang ay tumutukoy sa mga taong nagsasalita ng mga wikang nabibilang sa Malayo-Polynesian. Ito ang pinakamalaking pamilya ng wika sa daigdig.
 - a. Austronesian
 - b. Melanesian
 - c. Micronesian
 - d. South American

Module 3: Worksheet #9B

Layunin: Nasusuri ang mga Ambag sa Pag-unlad ng Klasikal na Lipunan sa mga Pulo sa Pacific

Panuto: Uriin. Piliin ang di-kabilang sa pangkat.

1. Ang Polynesia ay binubuo ng:
 - a. Tonga
 - b. New Zealand
 - c. Austral Islands
 - d. Marianas Islands
2. Mga pangunahing tanim sa Micronesia:
 - a. breadfruit
 - b. saging
 - c. niyog
 - d. taro
3. Mga alituntuning hinubog ng mga mandirigma sa Melanesia:
 - a. katapangan
 - b. paghihiganti
 - c. katapatan
 - d. karangalan
4. Yamang-dagat ng Polynesia:
 - a. kabibe
 - b. tuna
 - c. hipon
 - d. octopus
5. kabuhayan sa Melanesia:
 - a. Pag-aalaga ng baboy
 - b. Pangangaso ng mga Marsupial at ibon
 - c. Pangingisda
 - d. Pagmimina

Panuto: Isulat sa patlang kung ang pahayag ay *tama* o *mali*.

- _____ 1. Karamihan sa mga Polynesian ay mga mandaragat kaya mahalaga ang *canoe* sa pang-araw-araw na buhay.
- _____ 2. May kaalaman sa paggawa ng simpleng palayok ang mga lipunan sa Melanesia.

- _____ 3. Ang hibla mula sa puno ng rimas sa Polynesia ay ginagawang tela na tinatawag ng *tapa*.
- _____ 4. Sa Micronesia, ipinagpapalit ng mga taga-high-lying island ang turmeric na ginagamit bilang gamot at pampaganda.
- _____ 5. Isa sa karaniwang produktong kinakalakal ng mga Polynesian ay ang mga gawa nilang bangka.

Panuto: Kumpletuhin ang mga pangungusap. Pumili ng angkop na salita sa loob ng kahon.

<i>Mana</i>	<i>Polynesia</i>	<i>Harina</i>	<i>Animismo</i>
<i>Melanesia</i>	<i>Pera</i>	<i>Micronesia</i>	<i>Tohua</i>
<i>Pakikipagkalakalan</i>		<i>mandirigma</i>	

Ang tatlong subrehiyon sa Oceania ay ang (1) _____, (2) _____, at (3) _____. Ang mga Polynesian ang unang nanirahan dito. Ang sentro ng pamayanan nila ay ang (4) _____ na kadalasan nasa gilid ng mga bundok at nakapaligid sa tirahan ng mga pari at mga banal na estruktura. Naniniwala sila sa banal na kapangyarihan o (5) _____. Ang mga maliliit na pulo at atoll na matatagpuan sa hilaga ng Melanesia at sa silangan ng Asya ay tinatawag na Micronesia. Nagtatanim sila ng mga produkto na sagana sa asukal at sa starch na maaaring gawing (6) _____. Sa Palau at Yap, bato at shell ang ginagamit bilang paraan ng palitan. Gumagamit din ang Palau ng batong ginawang (7) _____. Sa kabilang dako, ang mga sinaunang pamayanan sa Melanesia na maaaring nasa baybaying-dagat o sa dakong loob pa ay pinamumunuan ng (8) _____. Kadalasang tagumpay sa digmaaan ang pangkaraniwang batayan ng mga Melanesian sa pagpili ng pinuno. Naniniwala rin sila sa (9) _____. May sariling katangian at kakanyahan ang mga isla sa Pacific. Nakabatay ang kanilang pamumuhay sa (10) _____ sa iba-ibang isla at kontinente.

Panuto: Bilugan ang **TTTT** ng tamang sagot.

- Sentro ito ng pamayanan sa Polynesia na napaliligiran ng tirahan ng mga pari at mga banal na estruktura.
 - canoe
 - kava
 - Hopi
 - tohua
- Ang mga dahon ng halamang ito ay ginagamit sa paglala ng mga panapin, damit, layag, at iba pang kagamitan sa loob ng bahay.
 - rimas
 - breadfruit
 - hamlet
 - yam
- Anong tawag sa hibla ng punong rimas na ginagawang tela?
 - sago palm
 - mana
 - tapa
 - shellbead
- Sa Melanesia, ano ang tawag sa paraanng pagtatanim na sinusunog muna ang kagubatan bago taniman?
 - swidden horticulture
 - sistemang kaingin
 - hamlet
 - artipisyal na pulo
- Isang inuming hindi alkohol na gawa sa ugat ng halmang paminta ang paboritong inumin ng mga matatandaat kadalasang ginagamit sa mga seremonya?
 - tapu
 - kava
 - atoll
 - starch

6. Mula sa balat ng anong puno ang paggawa ng telang tapa sa Fiji?
a. Mulberry b. Strawberry c. Blackberry d. Raspberry
7. Anong katangian ang mamamalas sa mga Melanesian sa mga maskara, pigura, at kagamitang panseremonya na gawa sa kahoy, talukab ng pagong, at kabibe na pininturahan ng itim, pula, o puti?
a. matiyaga b. masipag c. maparaan d. artistiko
8. Ilarawan ang layag ng canoe ng mga Micronesian.
a. triyanggulo na may mahabang tali c. triyanggulo na naililipat sa magkabilang dulo
b. magkabilaang parihaba d. parisukat na natitiklop
9. Anong bumubuo sa sining ng mga Micronesian?
a. palamuting yari sa mga kabibe c. mga mascara at pigura
b. mga produktong mula sa kahoy d. lahat ng nabanggit
10. Ito ang nagdala ng kapayapaan, edukasyon, mga pagpapahalagang tulad ng monogamy, pagtigil ng kanibalismo, pang-aalipin, aborsyon, at pagkitil sa buhay ng sanggol.
a. Animismo b. Jainismo c. Kristiyanismo d. Islam

Source: SDO-Pasig Modules and Worksheets

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

Appendix N: Matrixes for Statistical Tests and Computations

CRONBACH'S ALPHA

Respondent #	A. CONTENT										B. PROCESS											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	36	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
4	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	33	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	37	
5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
6	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	37	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	38	
7	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
8	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
9	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
10	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
11	3	4	3	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	35	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
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45	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	39	3	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	35	
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50	3	3	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	4	34	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	
TOTAL	192	193	189	192	193	194	192	191	196	196	192.8	196	191	195	194	197	194	194	197	196	195	194.9
Variance	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	4.93	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	3.54
(Σs²y)	1.22										(s ² x)	0.90										(s ² x)
VARIABLES			Values			Internal Consistency			VARIABLES			Values			Internal Consistency							
# of items (K)			10			GOOD			# of items (K)			10			GOOD							
Sum of the item variance (Σs ² y)			1.22						Sum of the item variance (Σs ² y)			0.90										
Variance of total score (s ² x)			4.93						Variance of total score (s ² x)			3.54										
Cronbach's Alpha (α)			0.84						Cronbach's Alpha (α)			0.83										

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Respondent	C. PRODUCT										D. AFFECT/ENVIRONMENT										TOTAL		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10			
1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	38	270
3	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	39	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	38	276	
4	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	37	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	254	
5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
6	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	39	265	
7	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	272	
8	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
9	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
10	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	276	
11	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	270	
12	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
13	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
14	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
15	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
16	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
17	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
18	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
19	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
20	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
21	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
22	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
23	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
24	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
25	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
26	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
27	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
28	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
29	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	37	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	38	272	
30	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	39	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	272	
31	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	38	258	
32	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
33	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
34	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	38	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	39	267	
35	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	36	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	38	270	
36	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	280	
37	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	276	
38	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	39	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	39	267	
39	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	39	263	
40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	270	
41	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	278	
42	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	3	3	36	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	39	255	
43	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	35	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	32	246	
44	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	35	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	266	
45	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	35	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	258	
46	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	32	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	244	
47	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	270	
48	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	37	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	256	
49	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	38	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	262	
50	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	40	268	
TOTAL	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	13421	
Variance	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	
(r^2)	0.96										0.42												
	VARIABLES					Values		VARIABLES					Values		VARIABLES					Values			
	# of items (K)					10		# of items (K)					10		# of items (K)					10			
	Sum of the item variance ($\sum s^2$)					0.96	GOOD	Sum of the item variance ($\sum s^2$)					0.42	GOOD	Sum of the item variance ($\sum s^2$)					1.57			
	Variance of total score (s^2)					3.69		Variance of total score (s^2)					1.57			Variance of total score (s^2)					1.57		
	Cronbach's Alpha (α)					0.82		Cronbach's Alpha (α)					0.81			Cronbach's Alpha (α)					0.81		

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

T-TEST

Respondent	SCORES	
	PRE	POST
1	13	21
2	11	19
3	10	20
4	12	22
5	11	21
6	12	24
7	9	16
8	5	15
9	13	24
10	12	22
11	10	19
12	4	14
13	16	25
14	9	16
15	12	23
16	6	15
17	0	13
18	14	24
19	11	21
20	20	25
21	20	25
22	11	20
23	13	23
24	19	25
25	15	24
26	11	20
27	12	23
28	10	18
29	8	17
30	5	15
31	6	19
32	10	18
33	9	19
34	10	20
35	12	21
36	7	18
37	12	22
38	10	19
39	9	17
40	5	13
41	11	18
42	17	21
43	17	23
44	12	18
45	12	20
46	14	21
47	13	19
48	14	19
49	10	17
50	10	15
51	5	13
52	5	14
53	10	16
54	11	13
55	11	18

55	11	18
56	6	14
57	9	18
58	6	16
59	8	15
60	8	17
61	13	22
62	6	15
63	6	17
64	6	15
65	10	18
66	13	22
67	13	24
68	7	15
69	9	16
70	12	22
71	6	14
72	7	17
73	11	19
74	8	16
75	8	17
76	12	22
77	13	23
78	9	19
79	10	20
80	13	25
81	9	17
82	7	15
83	10	19
84	14	25
85	3	13
86	4	15
87	13	24
88	6	14
89	5	13
90	8	16
91	7	17
92	15	25
93	6	14
94	6	15
95	13	22
96	8	16
97	8	18
98	13	24
99	12	22
100	8	17
101	6	15
102	6	16
103	12	21
104	8	16
105	10	19
106	10	20
107	9	18
108	11	21
109	14	25
110	4	14

111	7	16
112	12	21
113	10	19
114	5	13
115	7	15
116	10	18
117	7	15
118	8	17
119	11	22
120	15	25
121	11	20
122	8	17
123	12	23
124	10	20
125	9	19
126	6	15
127	10	20
128	12	22
129	5	17
130	9	18
131	9	15
132	11	21
133	12	23
134	7	15
135	12	23
136	10	20
137	6	13
138	12	22
139	11	20
140	13	25
141	9	16
142	16	25
143	12	24
144	8	18
145	12	24
146	10	22
147	14	25
148	14	24
149	8	16
150	8	18
151	10	23
152	12	24
153	8	17
154	14	25
155	11	23
156	15	25
157	11	23
158	12	24
159	9	21
160	10	21
TOTAL	1600	3077

T-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means				
	PRE	POST	SD-Pre	SD-Post
Mean	10.00	19.23		
Variance	11.07	12.80	3.33	3.58
Observations	160	160		
Pearson Correlation	0.88			
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0.050			
df	159			
t Stat	-68.11			
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.00			
t Critical one-tail	1.65			
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00			
t Critical two-tail	1.97			

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

PEARSON-R

Respondent	SCORES	
	OVER-ALL	POST
1	38	21
2	35	19
3	36	20
4	38	22
5	38	21
6	40	24
7	33	16
8	33	15
9	33	24
10	38	22
11	36	19
12	32	14
13	40	25
14	34	16
15	38	23
16	33	15
17	32	13
18	40	24
19	38	21
20	40	25
21	39	25
22	37	20
23	39	23
24	40	25
25	39	24
26	37	20
27	38	23
28	35	18
29	34	17
30	33	15
31	36	19
32	35	18
33	36	19
34	38	20
35	39	21
36	35	18
37	38	22
38	35	19
39	35	17
40	31	13
41	36	18
42	38	21
43	39	23
44	35	18
45	37	20
46	37	21
47	35	19
48	35	19
49	34	17
50	33	15
51	30	13
52	33	14
53	35	16
54	35	19
55	33	18
56	32	14
57	36	18
58	33	16
59	34	15
60	36	17
61	38	22
62	33	15
63	34	17
64	32	15
65	36	18
66	37	22
67	40	24
68	33	15
69	34	16
70	37	22
71	32	14
72	35	17
73	36	19
74	33	16
75	35	17
76	38	22
77	38	23
78	34	19
79	37	20
80	39	25
81	33	17
82	32	15
83	36	19
84	40	25
85	32	13
86	34	15
87	39	24
88	33	14
89	32	13
90	35	16
91	35	17
92	40	25
93	32	14
94	33	15
95	39	22
96	34	16
97	36	18
98	39	24
99	37	22
100	33	17
101	33	15
102	33	16
103	38	21
104	34	16
105	36	19
106	37	20
107	34	18
108	37	21
109	40	25
110	31	14
111	35	16
112	37	21
113	35	19
114	31	13
115	35	15
116	37	18
117	34	15
118	35	17
119	39	22
120	40	25
121	36	20
122	33	17
123	38	23
124	36	20
125	35	19
126	34	15
127	37	20
128	38	22
129	34	17
130	36	18
131	33	15
132	39	21
133	39	23
134	34	15
135	39	23
136	36	20
137	33	13
138	39	22
139	35	20
140	40	25
141	34	16
142	40	25
143	38	24
144	33	18
145	40	24
146	38	22
147	40	25
148	40	24
149	34	16
150	36	18
151	39	23
152	40	24
153	35	17
154	40	25
155	39	23
156	40	25
157	38	23
158	39	24
159	36	21
160	38	21
TOTAL	5737.75	3077

	OVER-ALL	POST
OVER-ALL	1	
POST	0.96	1

CURRICULUM VITAE

JENNIFER AQUINO RAYCO

LICENSED PROFESSIONAL TEACHER

I am a Licensed PROFESSIONAL TEACHER (LPT) with outstanding teaching skills, problem solving, analytical and presentation skills. Flexible with keen attention to details, hardworking, passionate, patient, persuasive and concise communicator with very strong commitment to integrity, confidentiality and excellence.

CONTACT INFORMATION

- #38 Don. Perfecto Street, Alcantara Subdivision, San Pablo City, Laguna.
- jennifer.rayco@deped.gov.ph
- 0919-407-7833
- June 9, 1976 Female
- Single

EDUCATION:

- PLSP GRADUATE SCHOOL -IN PROGRESS**
MAEd Major In Educ. Mgt. 2021-present
- PUP GRAD. SCH. / SAN PABLO COLLEGES**
Master in Eco. / MBA- unit earner 1998-2003
- UNIVERSITY OF SANTO TOMAS (UST)**
BS in Commerce Major in Economics 1997
- LAGUNA COLLEGE**
Paseo de Escudero St. San Pablo City 1993
- SAN PABLO CENTRAL ELEM. SCHOOL**
Rizal Avenue, San Pablo City 1989

SKILLS:

- Objectivity, Confidentiality and Thoroughness
- Reporting and Presentation Skills
- Communication and Interpersonal Skills
- Integrity and Innovation
- Teamwork and Leadership

CHARACTER REFERENCES:

- DR. JOEL CABAEL**
Pamantasan ng Lunsod ng San Pablo
VP for Extension
- DR. ELMER C. ESCALA**
Col. Lauro D. Dizon MIHS
Head Teacher I- AP Dept.

WORK EXPERIENCE:

TEACHER 1 / OHSP COORDINATOR
COL. LAURO D. DIZON MEMORIAL INTEGRATED HIGH SCHOOL
Brgy. VI-A, Mavenda St. San Palo City
June 9, 2015- Present

TEACHER / ASST. SCHOOL REGISTRAR
ACADEMIA DE SAN IGNACIO DE LOYOLA
Schetelig Avenue, corner Vesco Subd. San Pablo City
June 1, 2007 - May 31, 2014

INSTRUCTOR II
DALUBHASAAN NG LUNSOD NG SAN PABLO
Brgy. San Jose, San Pablo City
June 9, 1998 - May 31, 2007

FIELD INTERVIEWER
DEPARTMENT OF LABOR AND EMPLOYMENT, REGION 4A
quezon Avenue
April 1997 - March 31, 1998

SEMINARS ATTENDED:

- SLAC- SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELL 10 Sessions Oct. 2021 - July 1, 2022
- The Role of GCED in Rebuilding Communities: "Peaceful World and Empowered Learners", Feb. 4, 2022
- Division Online Training in Araling Panlipunan Virtual INSET 2022 Feb. 2-4, 2022
- Learners' Needs and Teaching Strategies Institute of Global Professionals Jan. 30, 2022
- The Impact of a Good Leader in a Society Institute of Global Professionals Jan. 30, 2022
- 2022 International Day of Education with the theme " Changing Course, Transforming Education" Jan. 24, 2022
- National Webinar In Understanding DepEd Order No. 66 s. 2007 and the Need to Publication and Authorship Aloysian Publication Sept. 25, 2021
- VINSET 2.0- Virtual INSET for Teachers ICTS-EdTech Aug. 30-Sept. 3, 2021
- Alagang Sol "Resilience, Hope & Inspiration" Personality Development: Online Workshop for DepEd Division of San Pablo City Teaching and Non-teaching Personnel Jul. 26, 2021
- 21st Century Education: The 4Cs: Communication, Collaboration, Creativity, Critical Thinking) by Akadasia May 19, 2021
- Orientation on the Interim Guidelines on the Preparation, Submission, & Checking of School Forms for the SY:2020-2021 May 11, 2021
- REGIONAL Orientation on the Use of PIVOT Leap & Gabay May 10, 2021
- HEROES 2021: Akadasia's Teacher Up-skilling Program "Creating Your First Online Course" Apr. 20, 2021
- Webinar sa Pananaliksik at Pagsusulat ng Kasaysayang Pampook Extension Webinar Series (UPLB-ÖSS) Saturday School Mar. 13, 20,27, 2021
- Division Online Training in Araling Panlipunan Virtual INSET 2021 Feb. 23-26, 2021
- HEROES 2021: Akadasia's Teacher Up-skilling Program "An Introduction to Online Teaching" Jan. 24, 2021
- ONLINE TRAINING OF TEACHERS, SCHOOL HEADS, & SUPERVISORS ON THE USE OF E- LEARNING APPROACH (Date: August 25-28, 2020-Batch 1

The Use of Differentiated Instructional Materials (DIMs) In Teaching World History in In-Person Classes of Grade 8 Learners

- Online Training of Secondary Teachers, School Heads, and Regions and Divisions Non-teaching Personnel on the Provision of Remote Psychological First-Aid to Learners using the SEES Manual, Supplemental Modules and Guideline Notes for Online and Remote PFA Delivery Jul. 23, 2020
- Capacity Building for Teachers and school Leaders Focused on Development & Utilization of I.D.E.A Lesson Exemplar Jul. 13-15, 2020
- HTML Foundation - DepEd EdTech Unit Jul. 24-26, 2020
- TinkerCad 3D Development - DepEd EdTech Unit Jul. 22-23, 2020
- Webinar Sessions About ADOBE Photoshop Essentials DepEd EdTech Unit Jul. 22-23, 2020
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (The Last Mile School Open Educational Resources (OER) Webinar Session) Deped-ETU UNDP Jun. 19, 2020
- Free Wi-Fi Internet Access in Public Places Project (The Last Mile School Open Educational Resources (OER) Webinar Session) Deped-ETU UNDP Jun. 18, 2020
- #SAFERKIDSPH (The Last Mile School Open Educational Resources (OER) Webinar Session) Deped-ETU UNDP Jun. 17, 2020
- Our Values Photo-Story Teaching Guide (The Last Mile School Open Educational Resources (OER) Webinar Session) Deped-ETU UNDP Jun. 16, 2020
- Webinar Sessions About Digital Design Creation Using CANVA Deped-ETU Jun. 15, 2020
- EDUAPPS must have for Teachers Deped-ETU Jun. 11-12, 2020
- Webinar sessions About Digital Design Creation "CANVA for Education Workshop" - Deped-ETU May. 20, 2020
- Webinar Training About Autodesk and Adobe Photoshop for Beginners Workshop" - Deped-ETU May. 13-15, 2020
- Webinar Training on the Use and Curation of Open Educational Resources (PROFICIENCY PROGRAM) - Deped-ETU May. 11-12, 2020
- Google Educator Groups (GEG Philippines) Webinar Session (G-Suites in Education) - Deped-ETU Apr.. 28, 2020
- Open Educational Resources (ADVANCED PROGRAM)
 1. Offline Learning Management System (MOODLE)
 2. AR and VR in Education
 3. 2D Comics Creator
 4. Gamified Powerpoint TemplatesDeped-ETU Apr.. 27 & 29, 2020
- Webinar Training About the Use & Curation of Open Educational Resources (BASIC PROGRAM- Deped-ETU Apr.. 22, 2020

I hereby certify that the above information given are correct to the best of my knowledge and ability.

Jennifer A. Rayco